
On diagnostic codes

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Preamble

The title of this thesis joins an integral part of clinical practice and a cornerstone of any computer language. While diagnosis codes represent a systematic answer to causes of disease and death; a diagnostic code may both refer to the content of a script and the dual nature of clinical practice. Since the earliest evidence of clinical practice, diagnostics has evolved from a practice that concluded manual inspection, palpation and functional assessment to standards evolving in a system that is heavily dependent on computers. This thesis explores the boundaries of diagnostics in a digitized reality.

*Adapted from *The Meaning of Meaning: A Study of the Influence of Language upon Thought and of the Science of Symbolism*. Charles Kay Ogden & Ivor Armstrong Richards. Harcourt, Brace & World, Inc. New York (1925); p. 11.

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Preface

This thesis was written to complete the Graduate programme in Biostatistics and Bioinformatics at The Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences at University of Copenhagen and thereby fulfill the requirements for obtaining a PhD degree in agreement with the ministerial Order on the PhD Programme at the Universities and Certain Higher Artistic Educational Institutions (PhD Order).

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For countless valuable discussions, timely insight, and firm trust, I thank family (immediate and extended), friends, colleagues, and the academic advisors. Individually and in concert you have expanded horizons, induced perspective; and encouraged me to find my own trajectory in this model of reality called science and the corner of reality known as clinic practice.

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List of manuscripts

1. * Haue AD, Armentaros JJA, Holm PC, Moseley PL, Køber LV, Bundgaard H, Brunak S. Temporality in ischemic heart disease multi-morbidity. *Manuscript in preparation.*
2. * Haue AD, Holm PC, Banasik K, Lundgaard AT, Muse VP, Roder T, Westergaard D, Chmura P, Siggaard T, Christensen AH, Weeke PE, Sørensen E, Ostrowski SR, DF Gulbjartsson, Holm H, Iversen KK, Køber LV, Ullum H, Bundgaard H, Brunak S. Risk stratification of 72,249 patients with ischemic heart disease: a retrospective study linking prior multi-morbidity, biochemical data, and genetics. *Manuscript submitted.*
3. * Holm PC, Haue AD, Banasik K, Brunak S, Bundgaard H. PMHnet-alpha: a neural network-based discrete-time survival model for mortality prediction in ischemic heart disease. *Manuscript in preparation.*
4. † Rodríguez CL, Mazonni G, Haue AD, Eriksson R, Biel JH, Cantwell L, Westergaard D, Belling KG, Brunak S. Polypharmacy and drug dosage modifications: a longitudinal analysis of 3.5 million electronic health records. *Manuscript in revision.*
5. † Aguayo-Orozco A, Haue AD, Jørgensen IF, Westergaard D, Moseley PL, Mortensen LH, Brunak S. Optimizing drug selection from a prescription trajectory of one patient. *Manuscript in revision.*
6. † Siggaard T, Reguant R, Jørgensen IF, Haue AD, Lademann M, Aguayo-Orozco A, Hjaltekin JX, Jensen AB, Banasik K, Brunak S. Disease trajectory browser for exploring temporal, population-wide disease progression patterns in 7.2 million Danish patients. *Nat Commun.* 2020 Oct 2;11(1):4952. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18682-4>.

*: Main manuscripts

†: Contributory manuscripts

Summary

Introduction As the digitized reality is transforming modern medicine, data volumes and variety are growing considerably while the visions for healthcare are also being revised. Yet it remains an open question how to convert this wealth of data into clinically actionable evidence that is becoming even more needed in an ageing population. In this thesis, I present six original studies that investigate the potential of Danish healthcare data as a platform to perform data-driven research. The thesis has a strong focus on multi-morbidity in ischemic heart disease (IHD) and the applied methods range from classical regression models to machine learning methods. Multi-morbidity in IHD is both characterized with respect to the temporality between diagnoses and by analyzing more fine-grained healthcare data, such as electronic health records (EHRs) and genetic data. The practical consequences of multi-morbidity are also studied based on analyses of polypharmacy in an in-hospital setting and in the general population. Finally, the thesis presents an example sharing research results as a web tool made available to others without sharing person-sensitive data.

Manuscript 1: Temporality in ischemic heart disease multi-morbidity. This study characterizes multi-morbidity in IHD using The Danish National Patient Registry (NPR) data from IHD patients in the period years 1994–2018. Multi-morbidity is characterized by application of a new version of the so-called disease trajectory program that establishes temporal associations between diagnoses. The study showcases differences between disease trajectories containing conditions that are solely risk factors, and conditions that can be both risk factors and complications. The study argues that disease trajectories can be used to systematically assess the temporality in multi-morbidity, which is important, yet often an underappreciated aspect, of multi-morbidity.

Manuscript 2: Risk stratification of 72,249 patients with ischemic heart disease: a retrospective study linking prior multi-morbidity, biochemical data, and genetics. In this study, multi-morbidity in IHD is addressed by characterizing distinct patient subgroups obtained by application of a cluster algorithm to diagnosis codes. In a cohort of roughly 75 000 patients, patient subgroups are identified based on similarities between patient-specific vectors that represent all diagnoses registered in NPR up to 24 years before IHD onset. Data from EHRs and Copenhagen Hospital biobank (CHB) are included to assess phenotypic differences in these patient subgroups obtained by application of the cluster algorithm. The patient subgroups associate with different progression rates as well as biochemical and genetic differences, indicating that the patterns captured by the cluster algorithm are biologically relevant.

Manuscript 3: PMHnet-alpha: a neural network-based discrete-time survival model for mortality prediction in ischemic heart disease. This study presents `PMHnet-alpha`, which is a neural network-based survival model for prediction of all-cause mortality in IHD patients. `PMHnet-alpha` is based on a derivation cohort of approximately 40 000 IHD patients with verified coronary pathology according to The Eastern Danish Heart Registry (EDHR) data. Roughly 600 input features extracted from EDHR, NPR, EHRs, and CHB, including diagnoses, blood tests, and polygenic scores are the basis for development of `PMHnet-alpha` that outperforms the GRACE2.0 risk score. `PMHnet-alpha` is also subjected to explainability analysis where predictive values of input features are ranked and characterized as positive or negative depending on how they affect the prediction.

Manuscript 4: Polypharmacy and drug dosage modifications: a longitudinal analysis of 3.5 million electronic health records In this study, polypharmacy is studied with reference to co-medication pairs that are defined by a combination of two distinct drugs where the likelihood of a dosage adjustment is more likely during concomitant treatment episodes than when administered as a monotherapy. By extracting information on drug regimens from EHRs from about one million in-hospital patients in the period years 2008–2016, the study presents 3993 co-medication pairs that were cross-references with 15 publicly available drug-drug interaction databases. We argue that the analysis provides evidence for up to 600 previously undescribed drug-drug interactions which were identified as co-medication pairs and not present in at least one of the drug-drug interaction databases.

Manuscript 5: Optimizing drug selection from a prescription trajectory of one patient. This study addresses polypharmacy by analyzing data from The Danish National Prescription Registry (DNPR) in the period years 1995–2019 comprehensively. The study presents the so-called prescription trajectories that map the prescription patterns from more than seven million people present in DNPR. Prescription trajectories contain up to seven distinct redeemed drugs that are more likely to be redeemed in one specific order. In the study, we argue that the analysis can support optimized treatment decisions by analyzing differences between people subjected to many changes in treatment regimens which can hopefully lead to more individualized care.

Manuscript 6: Disease trajectory browser for exploring temporal, population-wide disease progression patterns in 7.2 million Danish patients. This study presents The Danish Disease Trajectory Browser, which is a web application that enables users to explore data from NPR in the period years 1994–2018 based on results from the disease trajectory program. Thus, the study exemplifies newer possibilities for sharing research results. In the browser, users can search for one or more diagnoses and search results will be displayed in the form of disease trajectories. The browser has an array of search filters that users can apply to refine searches as well as an interface that allows to navigate the search results and modify the visual representation. Search results can be exported in the form of graphical representations of disease trajectories and summary statistics.

Summary in Danish

Introduktion Den digitale udvikling påvirker til stadighed moderne medicin. Det betyder også at volumen og kompleksiteten af sundhedsdata vokser med stor hastighed. Imidlertid er det fortsat overvejende et ubesvaret spørgsmål, hvordan denne flod af data bedst omsættes til klinisk beslutningsstøtte. I denne afhandling præsenterer jeg seks originale studier, som udforsker danske sundhedsdatas potentiale i forhold til datadrevet forskning. Afhandlingen har stærkt fokus på multimorbiditet blandt patienter med iskæmisk hjertesygdom (IHD) og de anvendte metoder omfatter både klassiske regressioner og maskineindlæring. Multimorbiditetet blandt patienter med IHD bliver først karakteriseret med hensyn til den temporalitet der er mellem diagnoser og ved hjælp af mere finkornede data så som elektroniske patientjournaler (EPJ'er) og genetiske data. De praktiske konsekvenser af multimorbiditet bliver også undersøgt i studier baseret på polyfarmaci blandt indlagte patienter såvel som i den almene befolkning. Endeligt indeholder afhandlingen et eksempel på interaktiv deling af forskningsresultater.

Manuskript 1: Temporality in ischemic heart disease multi-morbidity. Denne artikel karakteriserer multimorbiditet blandt patienter med IHD ved hjælp af Landspatientregistret (LPR) for patienter diagnosticeret med IHD i perioden år 1994–2018. Multimorbiditet bliver karakteriseret ved anvendelse af en ny version af det såkaldte sygdomstrajektorieprogram, som etablerer temporale sammenhænge mellem diagnoser. Artiklen beskriver sygdomstrajektorier, der indeholder tilstande som udelukkende er risikofaktorer, og tilstande der optræde som risikofaktorer såvel som komplikationer. Vi argumenterer for at sygdomstrajektorier kan anvendes til systematisk at belyse temporale sammenhænge, som typisk er ekskluderet fra traditionelle studier af multimorbiditet.

Manuskript 2: Risk stratification of 72,249 patients with ischemic heart disease: a retrospective study linking prior multi-morbidity, biochemical data, and genetics. I denne artikel bliver multimorbiditet blandt patienter med IHD studeret ved at karakterisere patientsubgrupper etableret ved anvendelse af en clusteralgoritme. I en kohorte med cirka 75 000 IHD identificer vi patientsubgrupper baseret på similaritet mellem patientspecifikke vektorer, som repræsenterer alle diagnoser registreret i LPR op til 24 år før debut af IHD. Data fra EPJ'er samt genetiske data fra Copenhagen Hospital Biobank (CHB) er inkluderet for at afgøre om der er fænotypiske forskelle mellem patientsubgrupperne. Vi finder associationer mellem patientsubgrupperne og forskelle i progressionshastigheder samt forskelle i resultater af blodprøveanalyser og genetik, hvilket indikerer at clusteralgoritmen finder biologisk relevante mønstre.

Manuskript 3: PMHnet-alpha: a neural network-based discrete-time survival model for mortality prediction in ischemic heart disease. Denne artikel præsenterer `PMHnet-alpha` som er et kunstigt neuralt netværk, der er udviklet til at beregne dødeligheden blandt patienter med IHD. `PMHnet-alpha` er baseret på en kohorte, der tæller cirka 40 000 IHD patienter med verificeret coronarpatologi i henhold til data fra Østdansk Hjerteregister (ØDHR). Knap 600 variable fra ØDHR, LPR, EPJs og CHB, inklusive diagnoser, blodprøver, og polygeniske risikoscorer danner grundlag for at udvikle `PMHnet-alpha` som forudsiger dødeligheden mere præcist en GRACE 2.0 risikoscoren gør. Endeligt bliver variable kvantificeret og rangeret i henhold til deres prædiktive værdi.

Manuskript 4: Polypharmacy and drug dosage modifications: a longitudinal analysis of 3.5 million electronic health records. I denne artikel bliver polyfarmaci beskrevet med reference til lægemiddelpar, defineret som en kombination af to forskellige lægemidler med stor sandsynlighed for en dosisændring i den ene lægemiddel, når de bliver administreret samtidigt. Ved hjælp af information vedrørende behandlingsregimer fra EPJ'er for over en million indlagte patienter i perioden år 2008–2016, identificerer studiet 3993 lægemiddelpar som blev sammenholdt med data fra 15 forskellige lægemiddelinteraktionsdatabaser. Vi argumenterer for at op til 600 af de identificerede lægemiddelpar repræsenterer potentielt ubeskrevne lægemiddelinteraktioner.

Manuskript 5: Optimizing drug selection from a prescription trajectory of one patient. Denne artikel adresserer polyfarmaci ved at præsentere en samlet analyse af data fra Lægemiddelregistret i perioden år 1995–2019. Artiklen introducerer såkaldte recepttrajektorier, som kortlægger mønstre for medicinske behandlinger blandt mere end syv millioner borgere. Recepttrajektorier indeholder op til syv forskellige lægemidler karakteriseret ved at recepterne bliver indløst i en bestemt rækkefølge. I artiklen argumenterer vi for at recepttrajektorier på sigt kan understøtte optimerede beslutninger vedrørende behandling blandt andet ved at analysere recepttrajektorier for borgere som ofte får ændret medicin. Med tiden vil dette princip forhåbentlig kunne understøtte mere individualiserede medicinsk behandling.

Manuskript 6: Disease trajectory browser for exploring temporal, population-wide disease progression patterns in 7.2 million Danish patients. Denne artikel præsenterer The Danish Trajectory Browser, som er en internetapplikation, der gør brugere i stand til at udforske LPR data fra perioden 1994–2018 baseret på resultater fra sygdomstrajektorieprogrammet. Med andre ord eksemplificerer studiet nogle af de fornyede muligheder der er for at dele forskningsresultater. I browseren kan brugere søge på en eller flere diagnoser, og søgeresultatet vil blive vist som sygdomstrajektorier. Browseren har en række muligheder for at præcisere søgningen i henhold til en række søgefiltre; og tillige en visning der gøre det muligt at navigere i søgeresultaterne og modificere den visuelle repræsentation. Endeligt kan søgeresultaterne blive eksporteret fra browseren som grafik eller tabeller indeholdende deskriptiv statistik vedrørende sygdomstrajektorierne for den fremsøgte population.

Part I

SYNOPSIS

0 | Objectives and overview

The overall objective of this thesis is to present my contributions to the research projects that I have been engaged in during the past three years. The studies are rooted within the tradition of bioinformatics and have a strong focus on multi-morbidity in ischemic heart disease (IHD). The thesis is based on six original investigations; three of which were particularly focused on multi-morbidity in IHD. These studies are also the main studies of the thesis as indicated in the List of manuscripts.

The hypothesis is that data-driven models based on comprehensive analyses of Danish healthcare data are of value in patient phenotyping and that they can complement classical epidemiological studies. Accordingly, the three main objectives of the thesis are:

1. to present an overview of IHD, the main phenotype of interest, along with the medical classification systems that comprise the foundation for patient phenotyping using electronic patient record data,
2. to describe the analyses and strategies that were carried out to transform massive amounts of Danish healthcare data into models reflecting complex biology, and,
3. to discuss strengths and limitations of the models, focusing on multi-morbidity in IHD, the clinical utility and perspectives on future directions.

Chapters 1 through 6 are the synopsis and comprise the first part of the thesis. Chapter 1 gives a description of multi-morbidity in IHD as well as an introduction to the medical classification systems and terminologies that were used to structure the data. The data sources containing individual-level patient data that were the foundation for conducting the studies are presented in chapter 2. Chapter 3 provides an overview of the employed methodologies, which ranged from concepts rooted in classical epidemiology to methods originally developed to analyze molecular data as well as machine learning methods. Principles and regulations regarding person-sensitive data are briefly described in chapter 4, while chapter 5 summarizes the results of the original investigations. Last, chapter 6 presents the main conclusions, discusses strengths and limitations and puts the the investigations into perspective.

The six full-length manuscripts are presented in separate chapters in the second part corresponding to chapters 7 through 12. The main studies of the thesis centered on multi-morbidity in IHD are presented in chapter 7 (manuscript 1), chapter 8 (manuscript 2), and chapter 9 (manuscript 3). The studies presented in chapter 10 (manuscript 4), chapter 11 (manuscript 5), and chapter

12 (manuscript 6) were included since I was involved in identifying case stories that also included examples from the cardiovascular field. Thus, these studies represent a defining aspect of engaging in data-driven research and in particular bioinformatics and biomedical data sciences.

The third part contains the appendices. The first appendix (appendix A) contains supplementary material related to the synopsis. Appendix B corresponds to the supplementary material to manuscript 2, while appendices C and D has the supplementary material for manuscripts 4 and 5, respectively. The only supplementary figure in manuscript 1 is available in the same chapter as the full-length manuscript, while the supplementary material for manuscript 6 is available online. Supplementary tables for manuscripts 2 and 4 that are not included in the thesis due to size limitations are available upon request. Appendix E lists my current publications and preprints.

Equations and figures that are labeled with the prefix *A* in the synopsis indicate that they are available in appendix A. Cross-references including literature references are clickable throughout the thesis and link to the relevant pages in the file.

1 | Introduction

This chapter gives an overview of IHD in the context of multi-morbidity that is compatible with the main body of work presented in the thesis. The aim is to link the clinical presentation of the individual IHD patient with the available resources that support nationwide studies of IHD. Section 1.1 describes IHD and the concepts of multi-morbidity and polypharmacy. Section 1.2 introduces the medical classification systems that were the basis in this thesis for studying multi-morbidity in IHD. Finally, strengths and limitations of research based on medical classification systems are discussed in section 1.3.

1.1 Diagnostics in a web of multiple causes and consequences

1.1.1 Ischemic heart disease is a common, chronic, multi-factorial disease

Worldwide, IHD affects more than 125 million people[1]–[3]. It is a multi-factorial disease that is most commonly caused by myocardial infarction (MI), which denotes a pathological condition where prolonged cardiac ischaemia leads to myocardial necrosis[4]. IHD pathology is characterized by a chronic inflammatory condition within the walls of the coronary arteries known as atherosclerosis which may lead to reduced blood flow to the heart, i.e. ischemia. Major risk factors for development of IHD include increasing age, smoking, high levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, low levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, hypertension and diabetes[5], [6]. The human chromosome 9p21 is the most widely recognized genetic risk factor among a total of more than 170 genetic risk loci, most of which display pleiotropy with other diseases[7], [8].

Cardinal symptoms in IHD are ischemic equivalents such as chest pain that usually lasts more than 20 minutes, dyspnea, and may also include nausea, vomiting, sweating, and fatigue[4]. An array of different diagnostic modalities exists, where the urgency of the clinical presentation and available resources jointly dictate the timing and choices. The diagnostic criteria include weighed assessment of dynamics in symptoms, biochemical profile (i.e. cardiac enzymes), electrocardiographic (ECG) changes and conclusively findings at imaging. Since the development of selective injection of contrast media into the coronary arteries in 1958, coronary arteriography (CAG) has evolved into the diagnostic gold standard while management of risk factors and revascularization using coronary artery by-pass grafting (CABG) or percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) have revolutionized the treatment and improved survival rates profoundly (Figure 1)[1], [10].

Figure 1: Decline in cardiovascular diseases in relation to scientific advances. CABG: Coronary artery by-pass grafting. PCI: Percutaneous coronary intervention. MI: Myocardial infarction. NHBPEP: National High Blood Pressure Educational Program. CASS: Coronary artery surgery study. TIMI: Thrombolysis in myocardial infarction. NCEP: The National Cholesterol Education Program. GISSI: Gruppo Italiano per la Sperimentazione della streptochinasi nell'INfarto Miocardico. ISIS-2: The Second Study of Infarct Survival. SAVE: Survival and Ventricular Enlargement Trial. ALLHAT: Antihypertensive and Lipid-Lowering Treatment to Prevent Heart Attack Trial. From [9].

To date, the Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events (GRACE) has provided the data foundation for one of the most widely used risk scoring schemes for IHD patients[11]. GRACE refers to a large multi-national registry, where patients with acute coronary syndrome were recruited from 14 different countries over the period from years 1999 to 2009. Data from GRACE comprise the foundation for a risk score of the same name that estimates short- and long-term mortality in patients with acute MI. The GRACE risk score has been updated several times and expresses the risk of six month mortality on a scale of 1 to 372, where a score of 1 is considered minimal risk[12]–[14].

Recent advances within genetic research have also paved the way for development of polygenic scores (PGSs) that have fueled perspectives within the precision medicine agenda, including more precise risk estimates[15]. There is already data supporting the hypothesis that polygenetic predictors can be used to identify individuals at increased risk of IHD and other multi-factorial diseases equivalent to that of genetic predictors of monogenic diseases. Further, it has been stipulated that the increasing interest in recycling population-wide healthcare data combined with continuous expansion of computational capacity, present endless opportunities of broadly integrating genetic data into clinical decision making[16], [17]. Ideally, principles that integrate conventional pathology obtained from CAGs and other clinical examinations combined with deep phenotypes harvested from

human data collections will increase healthcare quality for the individual[18]. However, the specific strategies that will translate these perspectives into clinical practice have not been fully established yet and accordingly much explorative work is being conducted within this field[19].

1.1.2 Ischemic heart disease often co-exists with other common chronic diseases

Up to 85% of IHD patients are co-morbid, broadly defined as a phenotype comprised of more than one chronic disease [9], [20], [21]. Co-morbidity and multi-morbidity are often used interchangeably. Technically, co-morbidity describes the phenotype with reference to an index disease, whereas multi-morbidity denotes the phenotype without reference to a particular index disease[22], [23]. In this thesis, I have chosen to use the term multi-morbidity in IHD to ensure consistency and stress that at any point in time several conditions may be equally important[24].

The importance of multi-morbidity has been articulated for more than 50 years[25]. Back then, there was already a focus on the consequences of failure to classify and analyze multi-morbidity owing to the potential causal role of multi-morbidity in prognosis and therapeutic effects. In randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and other types of clinical studies, unacknowledged multi-morbidity may confound or modify the results, making efficient methods for measuring multi-morbidity an unmet need[26]. Nevertheless, there is no consensus regarding multi-morbidity measures and the existing tools for measuring multi-morbidity vary greatly in validity, reliability and importantly, target population[26].

Historically, the most widely used co-morbidity measure is the Charlson co-morbidity index (CCI), which was derived from the correlation of 19 selected diseases with mortality among cancer patients. In a cohort of 685 breast cancer patients, the investigators found that only age and co-morbidity were risk factors of co-morbid death, i.e. death from other causes than metastatic disease[27]. Although there does not exist any specific multi-morbidity score for IHD patients, the evidence that multi-morbidity associates with the prognosis and burden of the individual patient is endless and in practice, CCI is widely used irrespective of main phenotype[28]. In acknowledging the prognostic interdependency of seemingly distinct diseases, it has been suggested that delivery of IHD healthcare should become more multidisciplinary rather than primarily designed to target one condition at a time[20], [29]. Examples of multidisciplinary approaches include integration of knowledge across different medical specialties and enhanced focus on patient preferences within a framework that is targeted treatment of IHD and other co-existing chronic conditions, i.e., multi-morbidity[9].

A common therapeutic consequence of multi-morbidity is a condition known as polypharmacy, referring to the simultaneous usage of multiple drugs by a single patient[30]. And generally, there is a knowledge gap regarding benefits, risks, and intensity of treatment in cardiovascular patients, with an increasing prevalence as well as age[31]. Major concerns with polypharmacy are that it increases the risk of adverse reactions, reduces the likelihood of compliance, and there is very limited evidence regarding the long-term consequences of the drugs that are often prescribed life-long[30], [32]. In fact, the increasing complexity of medical therapy is gaining attention in so-called adaptive platform trials, where multiple therapeutic interventions may be compared in the same trials[33].

1.2 Classification systems harmonize healthcare data

1.2.1 Classification systems for medical causes and consequences

Originally being the backbone of comparable mortality statistics dating back as long as to 1893, the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD) has turned into an important resource in healthcare systems which are increasingly influenced by advances in information technology[34]. One inherent advantage of the ICD terminology is that it is generalizable across many different healthcare systems, as it is used in many countries[35]. Since 1994, the 10th version of the ICD system (ICD-10) has been the official diagnostic reporting system between Danish hospitals and the Danish health authorities[36]. The hierarchical structure of the classification system is comprised of 21 chapters that largely correspond to different functional-anatomical body systems. For example, chapter IX corresponds to the Diseases of the circulatory system. Each chapter can be divided into blocks that are further segmented into diagnosis codes at different resolutions, e.g. level 3 and 4 codes with level 4 codes being the most specific. Level 4 codes amount to a tabular listing of more than 155 000 distinct diagnosis codes (Figure 2).

The screenshot shows the ICD-10 Version:2019 web interface. The left sidebar displays a hierarchical tree of ICD-10 categories, with 'IX Diseases of the circulatory system' expanded to show 'I25 Chronic ischaemic heart disease'. Under 'I25', 'I25.1 Atherosclerotic heart disease' is selected and highlighted. The main content area on the right displays the details for I25.1, including its description, exclusions, and sub-categories like 'Coronary (artery):' with sub-items: atheroma, atherosclerosis, disease, and sclerosis. Other ICD-10 codes like I24.9, I25.0, I25.2, I25.3, I25.4, I25.5, I25.6, I25.8, and I25.9 are also visible in the list.

Figure 2: A search in the ICD-10 terminology for IHD where the level 3 ICD-10 code chronic IHD was selected as indicated by the arrows in the panel on the left side. ICD-10 chapters, blocks, level 3 and level 4 codes are listed in the panel on the left. Descriptions of the selected level 3 and 4 codes are available on the right side. ICD-10: International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, 10th version. IHD: Ischemic heart disease. Retrieved from <https://icd.who.int/browse10/2019/en#/I25>.

The Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System was originally developed as a tool to correctly interpret data on drug utilization[37]. Like ICD-10 codes, the ATC Classification System has a hierarchical structure, where groups at five different levels are used to classify each drug at increasing specificity. The groups range from the 1st level codes that consist of 14 anatomical groups specifying the primary organ system of action, to the 5th level codes, which specify the active chemical substance of a given drug[38]. In contrast to the ICD-10 terminology that has one unique code per diagnosis; the ATC Classification System may have more than one code for one drug. In cases where a single chemical substance has multiple routes of administration, this is standard. Similarly, although non-standard, chemical substances with more than one approved indication may also have more than one ATC code (Figure 3).

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B BLOOD AND BLOOD FORMING ORGANS

B01 ANTITHROMBOTIC AGENTS

B01A ANTITHROMBOTIC AGENTS

B01AC Platelet aggregation inhibitors excl. heparin

Acetylsalicylic acid preparations specifically intended for use as antithrombotic agents are classified in this group. This exception from the basic principle of only one code for each route of administration is made because of the extensive use of acetylsalicylic acid both as an antithrombotic agent and as an analgesic. Whether an acetylsalicylic acid product should be classified in this group or in N02BA, should be decided at the national level based on the main indication of the product.
Lysine acetylsalicylate is classified at the same 5th level as acetylsalicylic acid.
Sulfipyrazone is classified in M04AB. Alprostadil is classified in C01EA and G04BE.
Combinations of acetylsalicylic acid and statins are classified in C10BX.
Combinations of acetylsalicylic acid, ACE inhibitors and statins are classified in C10BX.
Combinations of acetylsalicylic acid and beta blocking agents are classified in C07FX.
Prostaglandines are classified in this group while other agents used for pulmonary arterial hypertension are classified in C02KX or in G04BE.

The DDDs are based on prophylaxis of thrombosis. The DDDs of acetylsalicylic acid and carbasalate calcium are given as 1 tablet independent of tablet strength. This is due to the great variations between different countries in the dosages/strengths recommended for prophylaxis of thrombosis.
The DDD of iloprost is based on treatment of peripheral vascular disease.
The DDD of vorapaxar is based on the content of one tablet (2.08 mg).
The DDD of selexipag is based on treatment of pulmonary arterial hypertension.
For combinations products, see list of DDDs for combinations, www.whocc.no.

ATC code	Name	DDD	U	Adm.R	Note
B01AC06	acetylsalicylic acid	1	tablet	O	Independent of strength

[List of abbreviations](#)

Last updated: 2020-12-17

Figure 3: Search results in the ATC Index for the 5th level ATC code B01AC06 which is acetylsalicylic acid corresponding to its indication as an antithrombotic agent. Green insert indicates 1st through 4th ATC Index levels. The description below explains the reason for the exemption that acetylsalicylic acid may also be classified in the chemical subgroups N02BA that contains salicylic acid. In this case, the indication determines the ATC code. ATC: Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical. Retrieved from https://www.whocc.no/atc_ddd_index/.

1.2.2 Classification systems that reflect clinical practice and examination

The Nomenclature, Properties and Units in Laboratory Medicine (NPU) terminology, represented by NPU codes, index analyses within clinical laboratory sciences. NPU codes have been used since 1987 and are owned by the International Federation of Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine and International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry. Since 1987 the number of available examinations from clinical laboratories has increased from a few hundreds to more than 30 000 different types of tests[39]. NPU codes were developed to convey information regarding the property of a studied object, i.e. the patient. The three essential elements of an NPU code are (i) the system, (ii) the component, and (iii) the kind-of-property. For example, an NPU code for troponin is NPU18583 which is defined by P—Troponin I, cardiac muscle; subst.c.= ? nmol/L. The component is "Troponin I, cardiac muscle". Anything before the component refers to the system (P in this case for plasma) and anything after refers to the kind-of-property, which in this case is the concentration measured in nmol/L. Importantly, NPU codes do not provide any information regarding the correctness of the measurement also meaning that reference intervals are defined locally at the clinical laboratory where the analyses are being performed[39].

Clinical examinations and procedures are yet another aspect of medical care that is being organized according to a terminology. For example, the Nordic Medico-Statistical Committee (NOMESCO) was established in the early 1980s to compare the frequencies of surgical activities in the Nordic countries. The first NOMESCO Classification of Surgical Procedures (NCSP) was published in 1996 and contains 20 chapters. Every NCSP code consists of three letters and three digits. The first letter of the NCSP code corresponds to the chapter. Similar to the case for ICD-10 and ATC codes, NCSP chapters are arranged according to functional-anatomic body systems. For example, the NCSP code for PCI is FNG05, where F indicates that it is surgery performed on the heart of major thoracic vessels and N specifies that it is performed on the coronary arteries[40]. In reporting from the Danish healthcare system, procedure codes are generally more reliable than diagnosis codes[41].

1.3 Strengths and limitations of medical classification systems in research

In many healthcare systems around the world, ICD-10 and ATC codes are an efficient means of comparing death statistics, drug usage, and handling billing purposes. Similarly, NPU and NCSP codes are instrumental administrative resources. Recently, the value of healthcare data derived from other sources than RCTs has been referred to as real-world evidence and is gaining attention as a resource to define other endpoints than all-cause mortality[42]. Potentially, this is highly valuable in an ageing population where factors such as quality of life and therapeutic efficacy are becoming increasingly important aspects of healthcare[31]. Although classification systems and clinical terminologies are necessary in this respect, they are not particularly designed to reflect differential diagnostic didactic nor to encompass the true complexity of multi-morbidity. In other words, there is no guarantee that a patient who has been assigned a diagnosis code also was subjected to adequate diagnostic examination. This also applies to ATC codes in the sense that if a person has redeemed a prescription for a drug, there is no evidence of compliance, i.e. whether or not the per-

son took the drug as prescribed. Similarly, an NCSP code as such has no information regarding the conclusion of the procedure that it describes. Essentially, in isolation no terminology provides any information regarding the true phenotype, where increasing prevalences of multi-morbidity and polypharmacy complicate matters even further. Moreover, even in the simplest cases, diagnostics remain an incomplete representation of reality and still automatized diagnostic systems are not used routinely[43], [44]. Yet, the classification systems presented in section 1.2 have become important tools to classify data points and harmonize healthcare data across countries. These efforts are particularly important in order to transform as much data as possible in to a foundation for improved medical treatment[42]. The adaption of ICD-10 and ATC world-wide has particularly been driven by the World Health Organization (WHO) leadership driving the ICD[45]. The systems are also being updated continuously reflecting a medical field that is constantly undergoing development. For example, ICD-11 in which the ATC codes are embedded, has been designed for use in a digital world and planned to come into effect in 2022[46].

The aphorism “garbage in, garbage out” has resonated behind software ever since the earliest days of computer power[47]. And its implication remains the same. Thus, to make up for the fact that diagnostics in the classical sense was not performed over the course data-driven studies, including the ones presented in this thesis; successful adaptation of medical classification systems is absolutely necessary to generate valuable data-driven models. In fact, it has been suggested quite recently to create more data-driven and mechanistically oriented disease classification systems that would match the aims of the precision medicine agenda better[48]. By discriminating between apparently similar phenotypes, using a wide range of data (e.g. registry, molecular, and genetic data) the diagnostic process may become much more individualized and in effect support better treatment decisions. A concrete attempt is the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) that now increasingly makes its way into healthcare systems[49]. The work in this thesis has a similar aim and perspective.

2 | Materials

This chapter gives an overview of the data sources that were the basis for exploring the potential of conducting data-driven research in the setting of Danish healthcare data. Section 2.1 introduces the basic structures within the Danish healthcare system of relevance to studies presented in this thesis, while section 2.2 describes the relevant nationwide registries and section 2.3 presents the sources of deeper phenotypic and genetic data.

2.1 The Danish healthcare system as a research resource

Two of the essential aspects of the Danish healthcare system is that redistribution of taxes covers about 85% of the healthcare and the role of personal identification numbers[36]. Personal identification numbers are ten-digit numbers that since 1968 have identified every Danish citizen uniquely. The Danish Civil Registration System (CRS) administers all personal identification numbers[50]. Personal identification numbers function as unique identifiers of citizens across all public sectors including healthcare services[51]. Thus, in medical research based on Danish healthcare data, CRS facilitates linkage of different data sources given the study has been approved appropriately (cf. section 4). In addition to the linkage function, CRS contains information such as date of birth, sex and status (e.g. alive, dead, or emigrant) of the individual citizen. Figure 4 shows the data sources that were linked via CRS in this thesis prior to analysis.

Figure 4: Overview of data foundation and resources ordered by year of first observation in resource. †: Foundation for Danish healthcare data infrastructure. *: Nationwide registries. •: Regional healthcare data with deeper phenotypic data. ‡: Genetic data. CRS: The Danish Civil Registration System. DAR: The Danish Registry of Causes of Death. NPR: The Danish National Patient Registry. EDHR: Eastern Danish Heart Registry. BTH: BigTempHealth (EHRs from Eastern Denmark). CHB: Copenhagen Hospital Biobank. EHRs: Electronic health records

2.2 Data from millions of people over multiple decades

2.2.1 The Danish National Patient Registry

The Danish National Patient Registry (NPR) was established in 1977 and is one of the oldest nationwide healthcare registries in the world[36]. It was established with the primary aim of continuous monitoring of hospital and healthcare service utilization for the Danish Health Authority. NPR contains data related to all discharges from Danish hospitals, which are reported in the form of time-stamped patient contacts reflecting that activities within Danish hospitals are structured according to the so-called *danske kontaktmodel*[52]. A patient contact contains information such as duration and type of contact (e.g., in-hospital, out-hospital or emergency room visit), diagnosis codes assigned during the contact, type of diagnosis code, codes that document procedures performed during the contact and a myriad of other types of structured administrative information. One contact may span a few hours or several years, depending on the contact type and reason[53].

In NPR, registrations are reported in accordance with Sundhedsvæsenets Klassifikationssystem (SKS), which is organized in chapters corresponding to different aspects of healthcare.⁴ For example, chapter D corresponds to the ICD-10 classification and chapter K contains NCSP codes. Yet other chapters contain Danish classification systems. One such example is chapter U that contains codes for non-surgical procedures such as radiologic examinations[40]. Diagnosis codes are unique to NPR in the sense that it is mandatory to report at least one diagnosis code for every single contact. In contrast, not all contacts have a relevant procedure code, which is obvious for contacts where not procedures were performed. However, it was not until year 2000 that it was required by the hospitals to report the performed procedures to the Danish health authorities[36]. Historically, the diagnosis codes have been used most extensively in research. They can either be assigned as a primary or non-primary diagnosis. Primary diagnosis codes refer to the diagnosis that best describes the reason for the contact and non-primary codes may compliment that description making them highly relevant in the context of multi-morbidity[36], [50].

2.2.2 The Danish Registry for Causes of Death

In Denmark, completion of death certificates has been mandatory by law since 1871. It was not until 1970 that deaths among citizens dying in Denmark were registered in individual electronic records in DAR. Until then the data from death certificates were archived on punched cards. Data in DAR originates from death certificates which can only be written by a physician. Today The Danish Registry for Causes of Death (DAR) is maintained by the Danish Health Authority. Death certificates that dates back before 1994 are archived in the Danish National Archives. Variables in DAR include manner (i.e. natural, accident, violence, suicide, and uncertain), time, place, and causes of

⁴The full SKS is available at <https://medinfo.dk/sks/brows.php> [Danish].

death[54]. Underlying and contributory causes of death have been classified according to international classification systems since 1948 where they have been maintained by WHO. This means that causes of death are now being classified by ICD-10 codes. Before 1948 causes were registered using Danish and Scandinavian disease classifications. The registry was centrally validated until 2002 and since then, the registry has relied solely on information from the medical doctor who has verified the death[54]. There is some overlap between data in CRS and DAR as the time of death is a variable that is available in both CRS and DAR. The other variables related to death are unique to DAR[51], [54].

2.2.3 The Danish National Prescription Registry

The Danish National Prescription Registry (DNPR) contains data on all individual prescriptions dispensed at any Danish community pharmacy from 1994 and onwards. DNPR is a subregistry of Register of Medicinal Product Statistics, which is maintained by the Danish Medicines Agency. DNPR is administered by Statistics Denmark. The four main variable categories are variables related to the user (i.e. the citizen or patient), the prescriber (i.e. the treating physician), the drug and the pharmacy. Only redeemed prescriptions are entries in DNPR. Dispensed drugs are registered in accordance with the global ATC Classification System that is equivalent to chapter M of SKS. Over-the-counter (OTC) drugs are only entries in DNPR if they were dispensed as prescriptions[55].

2.3 Deeper data characterize patients with greater precision

A key element of this thesis is to explore the potential of the Danish healthcare data by analyzing it comprehensively. Deeper phenotypic data was therefore analyzed in addition to the nationwide registries presented in section 2.2. In broad terms, deep phenotypes are based on individual-level information that is more fine-grained than the information in for example healthcare registries[19], [56].

2.3.1 The Eastern Danish Heart Registry

The Eastern Danish Heart Registry (EDHR) is a subset of the Danish Heart Registry that was established in 2000. It contains data on all patients who have been subjected to CAG, PCI, coronary artery bypass grafting or heart valve surgery in Denmark. EDHR contains data from invasive cardiac procedures performed at a hospital in Eastern Denmark (equivalent to the Capital Region and Region Zealand) and patients younger than 14 at time of the procedure are excluded from the registry. Currently, EDHR contains data on about 100 000 unique patients many of whom have multiple entries in the registry. Each entry is described with up to 70 variables. The variables cover information on e.g., demographics, dispositions, prognostic factors, findings (e.g. coronary pathology), therapeutic consequences, and procedure-related complications[57].

2.3.2 Electronic Health Records from Eastern Denmark

The EHR data used in the studies presented in this thesis originated from BigTempHealth (BTH), which denotes a research project based on EHRs from Eastern Denmark in the period years 2006 to 2016. The term *EHR data* is used to describe any routinely collected healthcare data, that are not necessarily archived in a health-registry, a biobank or a similar specialized institution[19]. Ideally, EHR data would contain continuous and for practically purposes complete monitoring of all patients during hospitalization[56], [58].

Biochemical tests, in-hospital prescriptions and free text originating from the raw clinical notes are the three components that make up BTH. The biochemical data were originally stored in the two databases Labka and BCC, covering The Capital Region and Region Zealand, respectively[59]. The biochemical tests were indexed using NPU codes or local systems and reference ranges were provided by the laboratory that performed the analyses. The prescription data available in BTH were originally archived in the three systems Electronic Patient Medication 1, 3 and OpusMedicine, covering The Capital Region and Region Zealand, respectively. Analogously to the prescription data in DNPR, the prescription data in BTH were indexed according to the ATC Classification. In contrast to the data in DNPR, the prescription data obtained from EHRs also contain information on the drug dosages of the individual dispensation. The clinical notes include unstructured data, where clinical variables such as blood pressure, height and weight can be extracted by text mining. Similarly, allergies and symptoms can in principle be identified in this part of the data.

2.3.3 Copenhagen Hospital Biobank

Copenhagen Hospital Biobank (CHB) was established in 2009 to make use of residual blood samples that were previously discarded. It was initiated at Rigshospitalet and later expanded to include samples from all public hospitals in the Capital Region of Denmark. CHB contains genetic data obtained from blood that was originally drawn for blood-type testing or red cell antibody screening[60]. The genetic analyses performed on these samples are currently being conducted in collaboration with deCODE genetics[61]. Since the biological material is leftover from routine tests, study participants should in principle be asked for informed consent prior to inclusion. However, the biobank has a dispensation from the general rule requiring consent. In effect, study participants are not asked for informed consent prior to inclusion but can opt out at any time. Samples from patients younger than 18 years are excluded. Likewise, one patient can maximum be included once meaning that samples from patients who are already included in CHB are discarded. As of February 2020, genetic data were available on about 155 000 patients[60]. At the time of writing, this has now exceeded 300 000 patients. The analyses are performed only if studies are approved by the relevant authorities (cf. section 4).

3 | Methods

The chapter is organized in five sections, which give an overview of the methods that were employed in the studies that this thesis is based on. Section 3.1 explains differences between data- and hypothesis-driven research of general relevance for the objectives of the thesis. The following four sections give an overview of the applied data-driven methods. Each of these four sections present different approaches for studying multi-morbidity employing data-driven models. The disease trajectory approach, which focuses on the temporality of multi-morbidity, is presented in section 3.2. The section includes an expansion of this methods for studying polypharmacy. Section 3.3 presents a strategy for identification of multi-morbidity subgroups, whereas section 3.4 presents a risk prediction model developed using artificial neural networks (ANNs). Finally, section 3.5 describes a Bayesian logistic regression model that was used to analyze polypharmacy.

3.1 Data, science, and scientific models evolve over time

The increase in data volumes, variety, and velocity at which they are generated challenge the classical conception of a scientific method, comprised of an observation, leading to the formulation of a rejectable hypothesis, that can be tested in a repeatable experiment[62], [63]. This development has led to a distinction between hypothesis- and data-driven research. Historically, the vast majority of clinical studies has been conducted as hypothesis-driven studies. The value of data-driven studies is still somewhat controversial and they tend to be criticized as they inherently represent the standpoint that massive amounts of existing data in themselves are important resources for generating scientific models[63].

Classically, clinical studies are characterized as either experimental or observational (Figure 5). Any study design has a set of strengths and limitations and each design is appropriate for answering different question types[64]. RCTs are considered the gold standard in establishing evidence for treatment effects as it is the study design where bias is most actively eliminated and further a design that may prove causality[65].

A core component in several kinds of clinical studies is the notion of an exposure, e.g. smoking and an outcome, e.g. IHD (Figure 5). Often clinical studies are designed to measure that particular strength of the association between an exposure and a predefined outcome[66]. Informally, one could define risk as the probability that an event will happen within a certain period of time[67]. The

Figure 5: Classification of clinical research. Adapted from[64].

relative risk (RR) is a classical metric used to quantify a risk (Equation 3.1). Formally RR quantifies the strength of an association between an exposure and an outcome (Table 1). Importantly, RRs do not establish causality, but in a properly designed study a causal component within the association between an exposure and an outcome might be deemed likely. If it is easy to identify two groups where the only difference is whether or not they have been exposed to an agent, the causal relation can in principle be identified easily[66]. However, the presumed association might as well reflect a mediator, an interaction or be confounded by factors such as age, sex, temporal changes in diagnostic criteria, or methods[68], [69].

Table 1: 2x2-contingency table (left) and formula for relative risk (right)

		Outcome	
		+	-
Exposure	+	A	B
	-	C	D

$$RR = \frac{A/(A + C)}{C/(B + D)} \quad (3.1)$$

All studies presented in this thesis were observational and presented models that were conducted in a data-driven setting. Relative risks were computed to identify associations, only. While observa-

tional studies provide no evidence of causality their internal advantage is that they are ... *conducted in the natural habitat of the target population*.⁵ In practical terms, this means that in comparison to patients included in RCTs, those included in observational studies are often more representative of the underlying population. The reason is that patients included in RCTs are typically homogeneous due to highly specific in- and exclusion criteria that often dominate such trials[70]. In addition, observational studies are gaining attention consequent to the exponential growth in data volumes, where some argue that biology is too complex for hypotheses and pre-defined outcomes, that are necessary in classical clinical studies. Historically, observational studies have also dominated the literature[64]. It has been argued that ideally, hypothesis- and data-driven methods together have the capacity to make science more successful when conducted in parallel; where the former discover mechanisms while the latter harmonize information as data complexity increase[63]. If true, observational studies may perhaps change appearance in the classical classification of clinical research making data-driven research an integral part of modern medicine.

3.2 Comprehensive analysis of nationwide health registries

The introduction to the disease trajectory approach is divided into three. Section 3.2.1 introduces the original idea of temporal disease trajectories, including the components of the individual program, while section 3.2.2 explains a bias in the original disease trajectory methodology (given the nature of the data), that my work with this method was centered on. Finally, section 3.2.3 presents an elaboration of the original disease trajectory concept by defining prescription trajectories.

3.2.1 Describing multi-morbidity using temporal disease trajectories

Disease trajectories defined as time-ordered series of diagnoses were originally developed as a data-driven model for studying disease progression patterns based on comprehensive analyses of nationwide healthcare data[71]. Since the original publication in 2014 where the input data was the entire NPR from 1996–2010, the underlying method has been employed to study several different phenotypes, including sepsis, cancer, and dementia[71]–[74]. The overall aim with disease trajectories is to develop a model that maps the temporality in multi-morbidity using diagnosis codes as well as other data. The results are often represented in a single connected network (Figure 6).

According to the original 2014 approach, disease trajectories can be computed using a program that has two steps. The first step identifies directional, diagnostic co-occurrences and the second step builds linear disease trajectories[71]. A diagnostic co-occurrence refers to two diagnoses (D1, D2) with a significant association, meaning that for patients who have been assigned the diagnosis D1, the RR for being assigned the diagnosis D2 within five years from discharge for diagnosis D1

⁵*The book of why: The new science of cause and effect.* Judea Pearl & Dana Mackenzie. Basic Books. New York (2018); p. 150.

Figure 6: An example of a disease trajectory network that describes multi-morbidity in IHD. Circles represent diagnoses (ICD-10 codes) and arrows represent a temporal relation between the two adjoining diagnoses. Colors correspond to ICD-10 chapters. ICD-10: International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, 10th version. IHD: Ischemic heart disease. Downloaded from <http://dtb.cpr.ku.dk> using the query I25. The figure was generated by the tool described in manuscript 6. Search specifications are available in figure A.1 in appendix A.

is significantly higher than that of a matched control group of patients who have not been assigned the diagnosis D1 (Equation A.1). The direction is then defined using a χ^2 -test that tests for statistical significance between the number of patients who have diagnosis D1 assigned before diagnosis D2; diagnosis D2 assigned before diagnosis D1; and diagnosis D1 and D2 assigned at the same contact. If diagnosis D1 is more likely to be assigned before D2, we write 'D1 \rightarrow D2' and denote it a directional diagnosis pair, which corresponds to a length two trajectory indicating that it consists of two diagnoses. The linear trajectories can subsequently be summarized as a network by piecing together directional diagnostic co-occurrences, that share diagnoses. For example, the two length two trajectories D1 \rightarrow D2 and D2 \rightarrow D3 can be combined into the length three trajectory D1 \rightarrow D2 \rightarrow D3. Length two and length three refer the number of distinct diagnoses in the trajectories[71]. In reading a disease trajectory network from left to right, the diagnoses (represented by circles) occurring first will be related to other diagnoses (represented by arrows) in a directional manner, that can be quantified by the RR computed in the first step of the program (Figure 6). Further details are available in equation A.1 in the appendix A.

3.2.2 Targeting disease trajectories multi-morbidity in ischemic heart disease

The primary aim with the novel version of the disease trajectory program was to optimize the definition of temporality, while still analyzing NPR comprehensively. This aim can be broken into two tasks. One was to consistently adjust for confounding factors in the disease trajectory program. For example, there has been a profound increase in the number of patients who are assigned diagnosis codes for dyslipidemia and hypertension in the years 1995–2015 (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Distributions for year (left) and age (right) of selected diagnoses in NPR. Left, x-axis: Date at first diagnosis in NPR stratified by five selected diagnoses. Left, y-axis: Number of codes per year (value arbitrary). Right, x-axis: Age at diagnosis stratified according to the same five diagnosis. Right, y-axis: Number of codes per age (value arbitrary). Color legend: Color, diagnosis and ICD-10 code of selected diagnoses. ICD-10: International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, 10th version.

The other task was to adjust for the fact that most of the diagnosis histories (i.e. all diagnoses assigned to an individual over the course of a lifetime) are incomplete in the NPR data dump analyzed in the studies presented in this are incomplete consequent to the fact that it only covers roughly 25 years. In this context, is it important be aware of the fact that NPR is administrative, meaning that one bias results from changes in coding practice over the years consequent to e.g. the introduction of the Diagnosis-Related Group system in 2002[36]. Another factor that challenges the task is that age is a primary risk-factor for many of the classical multi-morbidities associated with IHD[75]. Consequently, many of the diagnoses are typically assigned within a few years and many manifestations of multi-morbidity are potentially not strongly related in a directional manner (Figure 7).

To adjust for these biases and factors related to the fact that multi-morbidity is endemic in some populations a series of linear regression models (LRs) were employed to define the temporal order (i.e., direction) of diagnosis pairs (D1, D2) assigned to IHD patients. In the LRs the dependent variable was the age at diagnosis and the independent variables were the diagnosis pair, the type of diagnosis, discharge date, type of patient, year of birth, and sex. Diagnosis pairs that were related in a directional manner were defined with reference to the P-value of the main effect for the diagnosis

pair. For those pairs, we used the fitted age at diagnoses D1 and D2 to define the temporality, e.g. $D1 \rightarrow D2$ for diagnostic co-occurrences (cf. section 3.2.1) if the fitted age at diagnoses for D1 was younger than that of D2 and the regression co-efficient for the diagnosis pair was significant.

3.2.3 Prescription trajectories model multi-morbidity in the general population

The overall goal with the prescription trajectories was to transform individual-level data on redeemed prescriptions from an entire Danish population into multi-morbidity patterns. The study was, in other words, inspired by the disease trajectory program. In the context of multi-morbidity in IHD there is especially one important difference between disease and prescription trajectories, which is related to the nature of the data foundation. NPR was the data foundation for the disease trajectories whereas the input data for the prescription trajectories was DNPR and thus not hospital data but data from community pharmacies, including prescriptions originating from primary care (cf. section 2.2). Accordingly, prescription trajectories can in theory support analyses of multi-morbidity in IHD by including data regarding the medical treatment of multi-morbidity that often is a matter of polypharmacy.

Figure 8: Conceptual figure of people at risk of redeeming prescriptions at different time points. Four different time points are depicted horizontally and four different risk groups defined from redeemed prescriptions are depicted vertically. Over time, people who redeem a prescription of a drug will change risk group. For example, all black people are at risk of redeeming prescription P_1 at time t_1 . The observation time for a person can also end. For example, the observation time for one green person ends before time t_n . Adapted from manuscript 5.

Figure 8 illustrates the grouping of study participants that was the foundation for establishment of prescription trajectories. Individuals in DNPR were grouped based on the sequence with which they redeemed a prescription of two distinct drugs (P_1 , P_2). These groups were defined by the order with which the prescriptions were redeemed: P_{00} indicate that neither prescription P_1 nor P_2 was

redeemed over the study period, P_{12} indicate that prescription P1 was redeemed before prescription P2 and P_{02} indicate that only prescription P2 was redeemed in the study period (Figure 8).

Significant prescription pairs were then defined by establishing a Poisson regression model for each prescription pair. The number of people who had redeemed a prescription for P2 was the dependent variable. The independent variables were age, sex, calendar year and whether a binary variable indicating whether the study participant had redeemed a prescription for P1 prior to redeeming P2. Like other regression models, a Poisson regression can be solved using maximum likelihood estimates and significance can be assessed using the Wald statistics[66], [76]. The interpretation of the RR was that it expresses the risk of redeeming a prescription for P2 after P1 relative to people who had not redeemed the prescription for P1. Longer prescription trajectories were pieced together from significant prescription pairs by application of the same principles as described in section 3.2.1.

3.3 Cluster analysis to define ischemic heart disease subgroups

This section describes a strategy for studying multi-morbidity in IHD patients that is based on cluster analysis. In contrast to the disease trajectory approach described in section 3.2, the study of multi-morbidity based on cluster analysis only included multi-morbidities that were diagnosed before IHD onset. Section 3.3.1 describes the underlying concept for application of cluster analysis in the context of multi-morbidity used in this thesis. Next, section 3.3.2 describes the mathematical concepts that cluster analysis relies on. Section 3.3.3 describes how cluster analysis was applied to the entire spectrum of multi-morbidities present in an IHD cohort, that was identified in NPR and finally section 3.3 exemplifies how the physiological relevance of the clusters was assessed.

3.3.1 A model where multi-morbidity and text documents share properties

The premise of this model of multi-morbidity was that the set of diagnosis codes assigned to a particular patient in a cohort can be considered a text document, where diagnosis codes correspond to the words in the document. Analogously, the cohort was considered a set of different text documents (i.e. text corpus), where the degree content overlap between the different documents differ. The idea is then to group patients based on the similarity in diagnosis codes, just like text documents can be sorted with respect to their theme based on the content of words. In this analogy, different manifestations of multi-morbidity among the patients in the cohort correspond to different text themes. This strategy for studying multi-morbidity originates from information retrieval and has been previously adopted in studying diabetes subgroups[77].

In broad terms, information retrieval is a discipline defined by the process of finding material with a specific piece of information from a larger set of information such as a data set. Classical information retrieval tasks refer to the task of finding specific documents from a larger collection which is usually stored on computers[78]. In the study of multi-morbidity that was based on these principles, the initial task was to identify patients (classically documents) in a cohort (classically a text corpus) that shared certain characteristics. The idea was that the resulting patient subgroups

could form the basis for a more precise segregation of high- and low-risk patients. A certain risk group would then correspond to finding a specific piece of information in classical information retrieval tasks[78].

In classical information retrieval tasks a scaling factor is often introduced to reduce the effect of unspecific words. For example, the term "and" is an unspecific feature as it is relatively abundant and is not very appropriate for discriminating between documents. In the case of multi-morbidity in IHD patients, a diagnosis code for hypertension could correspond to "and" in being very frequent among IHD patients but not very discriminative, i.e. largely uninformative.

The term frequency-inverse document frequency (tf-idf) is an example of a scaling factor that scales all features according to the number of occurrences (i.e., number of times it is assigned to a single patient) and the total number of occurrences in the entire data set. Thus, it dampens the effect of relatively uninformative terms[78]. Assuming that the principles from classification of text documents also apply to diagnosis codes in classification of patients, the tf-idf scaling factor was introduced to reduce the effect of relatively unspecific diagnosis codes. Mathematically, the tf-idf scaling factor is the product of the term frequency and the inverse document frequency and can be expressed by

$$\text{tf-idf} = \text{tf}_{t,d} \cdot \text{idf}_t \quad (3.2)$$

where $\text{tf}_{t,d}$ is the normalized frequency of a diagnosis code in the entire cohort and idf_t is the inverse of the ratio between the number of patients who are assigned that particular diagnosis code and the total number of patients in the cohort[77], [78]. Equations and further details for computation of $\text{tf}_{t,d}$ and idf_t are available in equations A.2, A.3, and A.4 in appendix A.

3.3.2 A mathematical graph representation of ischemic heart disease patients

A graph is a mathematical object that can be used to represent a class of entities[79]. It is defined by a triple consisting of a vertex set, an edge set and a relation that associates each edge with two vertices. It is not a requirement that the vertices are distinct as is the case in figure 9, where all nodes are connected by exactly two vertices.

Figure 9: A graph with vertices (circles), edges (lines) and n natural groups.

To model multi-morbidity in IHD, the Markov cluster (MCL) algorithm was applied to diagnosis codes from IHD patients, that conceptually corresponded to analyzing the words of different text documents in a text corpus. That is, in this model IHD patients corresponded to a class of entities. The overall aim was then to test for natural groups within this class, i.e, define multi-morbidity in a data-driven model by application of an unsupervised clustering algorithm to the entire set of diagnosis codes assigned prior to IHD onset.

IHD patients were represented based on their diagnosis codes and using a graph where vertices corresponded to patients and edges represented patients belonging to the same subgroup. Thus, in the graph represented in figure 9, there is one cluster as all the nodes are related via a finite number of edges. Yet, it is also reasonable to argue that some of the nodes are more connected than others, illustrating that there may be natural groups within the graph. An example of such a group could be the nodes labelled I, J and H as it appears relatively detached from the other nodes (Figure 9). Many clustering algorithms have been developed, likely reflecting that the notion of a natural group is highly diverse; while also reflecting that cluster analysis is currently being applied in many different fields, including biology, communication, and computer science[80]. In sum and in broad terms, cluster analysis is concerned with finding ways to look at the data that enable a better understanding of mechanisms rather than finding the correct answer[81]. In the case of multi-morbidity in IHD, cluster analysis is about finding ways to look at the data that, for example, allow to understand better why symptom burden and disease progression vary between patients.

3.3.3 A cluster algorithm minimizes a cost function

The operational requirements for most clustering algorithms, including the MCL algorithm are (i) that the data are structured in a matrix where data points (observations) are related to data features (variables) and (ii) that there is a measure of similarity (qualitative features) or distance (quantitative features) between all data points[82]. When clustering algorithms are applied to healthcare data a matrix is usually having the individual patients (observations) as rows and different features (e.g. diagnosis codes) as columns [83], [84]. Before the matrix can be used as input to a clustering algorithm, it is typically optimized to better represent the data. In the study presented in manuscript 2, each patient was represented as a vector of the tf-idf scaled diagnosis codes.

The second operational requirement for a clustering algorithm is that the similarity between observations in the matrix is quantified either using a similarity or distance function, such as the cosine, Jaccard, and Hamming functions[80]. The cosine similarity was computed to quantify the similarity between the tf-idf scaled vectors. It is defined by an angle between two vectors which is equal to the dot product of the two vectors divided by the product of their lengths was used

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{x_i \cdot x_j}{\|x_i\| \cdot \|x_j\|} \quad (3.3)$$

where θ is the angle between the two vectors x_i and x_j . Finally, the MCL clustering algorithm was applied to the matrix that that represented the cosine similarities between the tf-idf scaled patient vectors.

Mathematically, the objective of the MCL algorithm is to partition a graph by minimizing a cost function, that is associated with the weight of the edges. The algorithm then works by identifying the graph partition that minimizes the cost function. Conceptually it works by stochastically simulating a sequence of random walks of length k in a graph, so similar regions in the graph will stay connected, while dissimilar regions will be partitioned in different clusters. The algorithm optimizes such that the length of k will minimize the cost function. That is, the sequence of random walks will change the distribution of edges in a graph, such that vertices in dense regions (i.e. regions with many edges) will stay connected and vertices in sparse regions (i.e. regions with fewer edges) will not stay connected. The basic premise is that dense regions in the graph will contain relatively many paths of length k . Consequently, there will be relatively many walks in dense regions of the graph and fewer in sparse regions. Accordingly, following simulation and those regions will be considered similar[85].

Generally, additional data sources are necessary in the subsequent cluster characterization, as a comparison between subgroups obtained from cluster analysis comes with an extreme Type I error inflation rate, i.e. the risk of rejecting a true null-hypothesis is high because the seemingly difference is due to graph partition and thus a circular argument[86]. In effect, patient subgroups obtained by application of the MCL algorithm were characterized using biochemical and genetic data to evaluate the biological relevance of the patterns recognized by the algorithm. Obviously, patients who share disease patterns do not necessarily need to be genetically similar. That will depend on the disease in question, e.g. polygenic and multifactorial diseases.

3.3.4 Characterization of clusters using survival analysis

The aim with cluster analysis in the setting of clinical research is often to identify distinct subgroups possibly characterized by different etiologies. In our cluster-based study of multi-morbidity in IHD, the physiological relevance of the clusters was assessed by different means. One of the strategies was to assess if there were differences in risk of disease progression between patients in the different clusters. Thus, clusters were used as covariates in a survival model where secondary ischaemic events and death from non-IHD causes were defined as two outcomes of interest. In broad terms, survival analysis refers to the type of analysis where the outcome of interest is *time-to-event* and is represented using survival curves, that describe the relation between number of survived subjects at different time-points (Figure 10). When there is more than one outcome of interest, the outcomes may be considered competing risks[87]. In the study presented in manuscript 2 the two outcomes were treated as competing risks as only one of the outcomes could occur in a single patient. In the study, clusters were also characterized using PGSs that were prepared from the raw genetic data in CHB by collaborators in the author group as well as the results from blood tests. Since I was not directly involved in these analyses, they are not described in this section.

One of the strengths with survival analysis is that information from censored study participants is included in the model. Censoring refers to instances where the exact survival time of a study participant is unknown. Classical examples of censoring are that study participants are either diagnosed before the observation period began or are still alive when the observation period ended. Left-censoring applies to situations where the true survival time cannot be longer than the observed

Figure 10: Two survival curves and a risk table. Survival curves for patient subgroup A and B. X-axis: Time from start of follow-up to event, e.g. secondary ischemic events. Y-axis: Survival probability. Risk table: Number of patients in each subgroup at risk at time-points 0 through 5. The number of patients at risk at a given timepoint is the number of patients where neither the outcome has occurred nor have they been censored at the timepoint that is being evaluated. Underlying data from study presented in manuscript 2.

survival time. For example, there is left-censoring if the outcome of interest is time until disease onset and study participants are not screened continuously. In the case of NPR, most diagnoses are left-censored if time of diagnosis is used as a proxy for disease onset. Explicitly, a patient who has been assigned a diagnosis code for e.g. hypertension in NPR will most likely have developed hypertension before the point in time where it is registered in NPR. Conversely, right-censoring applies to cases where the true survival time is minimum as long as the observed survival time. Hence, if the outcome of interest is death, data will be right-censored unless all study subjects die during the follow-up period. Right-censoring is the most typical type of censoring in survival analysis[87].

The Cox proportional hazard (Cox PH) model is a semi-parameterized model and among the most widely used models for analysis of survival data[88]. This was also the model of choice in characterizing the patient subgroups obtained from application of the MCL algorithm. A central component of Cox PH is the baseline hazard function, also referred to as the conditional failure rate. Cox PH is semi-parameterized because the baseline hazard function is never specified[89]. Instead it is assumed that the baseline hazard is independent of the covariates also coined the proportional hazard assumption[87]. The Cox PH function is represented by the product of two terms, where

the first term is the baseline hazard function and the second term represents a linear combination of the explanatory variables. Mathematically it is given by the formula

$$h(t, X) = h_0(t) \cdot e^{\sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i X_i} \quad (3.4)$$

where h_0 is the baseline hazard function and X_i represents the explanatory variables. The baseline hazard function can be represented by a survival curve (Figure 10). The common interpretation is that the hazard function yields the risk which is quantified as the hazard in this analytical framework[87]. The hazard at a certain point in time (e.g. t_n) is equal to the chance of survival at t_0 given the study participant has survived the duration of time t_n . Hazards are commonly expressed as hazards ratios (HRs) in comparing for instance a treatment and a placebo group[89].

3.4 Data-driven predictions of mortality in ischemic heart disease

This chapter explains the principles of ANNs, which are introduced in this thesis as a method for analyzing *time-to-event* data based on hundreds of input features. Section 3.4.1 introduces the concept of ANNs and section 3.4.2 presents a model of explainability that responds to some general critique against the usage of ANNs and other machine learning methods in clinical research.

3.4.1 A conceptual introduction to artificial neural networks

Originally, ANNs and the units they contain were developed to model information processing in the brain[90]. Accordingly, ANNs are built of neural units called artificial neurons. Neurons are typically described using the parameters weights and a bias term. In this context a bias is a threshold and determines how easy it is for the neuron to produce a certain output given its input[91]. Formally, the total, weighted input to a neuron in layer i x_i can be expressed as the weighted sum of incoming outputs from the previous layer

$$x_i = \sum_{j \in N-(i)} w_{ij} \cdot y_j + w_i \quad (3.5)$$

where $w_{ij} \cdot y_j$ corresponds to weighted sum of the inputs from the previous layer and w_i is the bias term of a neuron in layer i . The weighted sum of inputs from the previous layer is then passed through a non-linear activation function, such as the sigmoid shaped logistic function,

$$\frac{1}{1 + e^{-x_i}} \quad (3.6)$$

to produce the output of a neuron in layer i that serves as input to the next layer[92].

Multi-layer perceptrons are a class of ANNs that structurally are described by referring to three types of layers: the input layer that receives information to be processed, the output layer that delivers the computational result, and in between, one or more hidden layers (Figure 11). The hidden

and output layers are all comprised of a set of artificial neurons that process the data from the preceding layer. The model architecture of an ANN refers to e.g. the number of hidden layers in a ANN termed the depth of the ANN and also the relation between the neurons in the different layers[92].

Figure 11: Schematic representation of an ANN with two hidden layers. Artificial neurons are represented as boxes and colors indicate if the neurons belong to the input layer, output layer, or hidden layers. Input neurons are light blue (bottom). Output neurons are grey (top). ANN: Artificial neural network. Adapted from manuscript 3.

A defining property of ANNs is that they learn from examples during development as weights and bias terms are tuned gradually in response to external stimuli (i.e. inputs). That is, ANNs of this kind learn from examples[92]. Before developing an ANN, a data set is typically split into a training set and a test set used for internal and external validation, respectively[92]. The former is used for internal validation to quantify and estimate the performance of the model. The test set is used to assess if the network works well on novel data or has been over-fitted on the training set (cf. section 3.4.2).

One of the most widely applied learning algorithms is stochastic gradient descent (SGD), which is an algorithm that minimizes the cost function which is termed loss or objective function. In supervised learning, the cost function measures the difference between the actual output and the desired output[91], [93]. In principle, SGD solves the cost function by identifying the global minimum. In other words, the SGD works by minimizing the cost function. To avoid over-fitting, regularization of the data is often performed prior to model training. Regularization works by adding a penalty term to the cost function which ensures that it is not too complicated and hence prone to remember the data rather than learning some generalizable patterns in the data[94].

Technically, SGD works by repeatedly applying the so-called update rule to weights and biases in a given network, which is exemplified for the weight w_k here

$$w_k \rightarrow w'_k = w_k - \eta \frac{\delta C}{\delta w_k} \quad (3.7)$$

where C denotes the cost function and the change in the value of a weight w_k to w'_k reflects testing if the cost function decreases when changing a weight. The update rule then tests if the cost function C decreases when changing a weight w_k as indicated by $w_k \rightarrow w'_k$. The term η refers to the learning rate and is often explained as a "step-size". Step-size and ANN depth are yet other examples of so-called hyperparameters and ANN development is in part about optimizing the hyperparameters to reduce the cost function.

3.4.2 Ranking input features based on level of information

A common critique against the usage of ANN in modern medicine is that they appear as black boxes in the sense that an ANN does not provide an explanation of *why* a certain input leads to a certain output, for example why the risk of death for a patient is estimated to be a certain value[95]. An obvious counterargument is that clinical decisions similarly appear as black boxes as they do not always generalize between cases. Another argument in favor of ANNs is that several methods for explaining the output of any machine learning model, including ANNs now exist[96]. This aspect of machine learning is called interpretability or explainability. An example of such method is the so-called SHapley Additive exPlanations value (SHAP value) named after the Nobel Prize-winning economist Lloyd Stowell Shapley[97].

The underlying idea of the SHAP value is borrowed from cooperative game theory. Here the Shapley value is a method that assigns payouts to players depending on their contribution to the total payout[98]. Analogously, the SHAP value can be used to measure the individual feature importance in an ANN, based on the informative value of that feature. The idea is that changing an informative feature will also change the output considerably; whereas the opposite is true for less informative features[99].

SHAP values refer to the results of differences between the output from the actual (baseline) model (i.e. an ANN), and the output of a new, explanatory model. The SHAP value for a given input feature measures how much that feature contributed to the model output in the context of its interaction with the other features. So, the SHAP value for a given feature is calculated by comparing the output of the actual model with the output of a model without that specific feature. The SHAP value is the difference between these two outputs. Thus, SHAP values are relative to the input data and can be used to interpret the model globally as well as interpretation of the individual predictions[99]. An important property of SHAP values is that they are additive, meaning that the importance of several input features can be pooled[100].

Aside from this kind of explainability analysis, model performance quantified using calibration and discrimination are also relevant in evaluating a survival model based on an ANNs[101], [102]. Model calibration refers to the ability of the model to predict future outcomes compared to the observed outcomes, whereas model discrimination refers to a measure of the ability of the model to separate outcomes. That is, a model can be well-calibrated and at the same time have a poor discrimination if it predicts eight failures within a time period but the predicted subjects who fail do not correspond to the observed subjects who fail[103]. The classification performance, i.e. discrimination of the algorithm developed in manuscript 3, was evaluated using the time-dependent area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (tdAUC). The receiver operating characteristic curve describes the tradeoffs between benefits and cost, i.e. true positives and false positives, where the goal is to maximize the former and minimize the latter[101], [104].

3.5 A probabilistic map of in-hospital drug dosage alterations

Bayesian hierarchical logistic regression was applied to establish a model of polypharmacy, where estimated likelihoods of drug-dosage alterations were used as proxies for potential drug-drug interactions. Since the method represents a statistical paradigm that is fundamentally different from the frequentist paradigm centered on the null hypothesis, this chapter is dedicated to introducing the fundamentals of Bayesian statistics. Section 3.5.1 describes the components that comprise a Bayesian regression model and section 3.5.2 gives an overview of the application of such models in the context of EHRs.

3.5.1 Bayesian models can be decomposed into three distributions

A defining attribute of Bayesian statistics is that a joint probability distribution is given to all observed and unobserved variables[105]. This contrasts to a frequentist paradigm, where it is assumed that the effect of unobserved variables is constant. Consequently, Bayesian models are flexible and addition of data to the model may change the model parameters. Generally, Bayesian models are gaining attention due to an increasing amount of software that has been developed to perform the regression[106]. Conceptually, a Bayesian model quantifies a degree of (un-)certainty, which can be updated upon addition of new data, i.e. evidence[107]. Bayesian models can be decomposed into three parts that may be probability distributions[105]. These are a prior distribution, a likelihood distribution and a posterior distribution (Figure 12).

Bayesian statistics is rooted in Bayes' theorem from which a conditional probability can be derived without knowledge of the joint probability. Mathematically Bayes' theorem is expressed by

$$p(B|A) = \frac{p(A|B)p(A)}{p(B)} \quad (3.8)$$

where $p(B|A)$ expresses the probability of B, given A. The theorem states that this probability is equal to the product of the probability of A given B and the probability of A divided by the probability of B. In other words, Bayes' theorem states that the probability of B given A is proportional to

Figure 12: A schematic representation of a Bayesian logistic regression model. Upper row represents the three different distributions. Middle row represents a Bayesian logistic regression, that is the foundation for obtaining the joint distribution also coined the posterior distribution, which is represented in the bottom row. Adapted from [107].

the probability of A given B, i.e.

$$p(B|A) \propto p(A|B)p(A) \quad (3.9)$$

As indicated in figure 12, a Bayesian logistic regression model can be established by application of Bayes' theorem to a data set, where the likelihood $p(A|B)$ is the binomial (n, θ) and θ is equal to the sum of the covariates. The prior reflects the level of information that is assumed to be in the data. It corresponds to $p(A)$ in Bayes' theorem and represents the prior beliefs about the relation between a set of variables and the outcome of interest. If the data is representative of the population that is being modelled, the prior will have a small variance. Conversely, the prior will have a large variance in cases where for example the data set is relatively small and thus not likely to be strongly related to the outcome of interest. Generally, priors are characterized based on their level of information ranging from informative (small variance) to diffuse or weakly informative (large variance). Importantly, the priors contain model subjectivity and are selected by the investigator although different priors can be compared [105], [108].

In a Bayesian logistic regression model, the goal is to model a posterior distribution that is as close to the true posterior as possible. The optimization can be performed using different algorithms, e.g., Markov Chain Monte Carlo sampling (MCMC) [109]. The algorithm estimates the posterior

distribution by randomly sampling a sequence of values from the likelihood distribution, that define the probability of a new point relative to the current point. At increasing sample size, this simulation will, if successful, approach the true posterior and the model has converged. Due to the stochastic nature of MCMC, convergence must be evaluated in the post processing step. This step can be done, using different methods, but is outside the scope of this thesis[109], [110].

3.5.2 Application of Bayes' theorem to electronic healthcare data

In the Bayesian model presented in manuscript 4, the outcome of interest was dosage alteration of a drug as a binary outcome; i.e. if a drug dosage alteration likely (yes/no) given a set of conditions. First, a set of variables in the data that were assumed to be explanatory variables were identified. Those included sex, age, reason for hospitalization (i.e. primary diagnosis code), year of hospitalization, and hospital. Each variable had a weakly informative prior defined by the normal distribution. Furthermore, the response was allowed to vary within each patient to account for individual heterogeneity. Ultimately, the parameter of interest is the posteriors, corresponding to the probability of B given A (Equation 3.9). In other words, the task was to find the posteriors for the model parameters that best represented the data, while accounting for unknown factors[105].

The parameter of interest in our Bayesian model was the probability of a dosage change relative to the current dosage. Samples were generated from a binomial distribution. The final model was evaluated using three different methods and the posterior was summarized using the highest density interval (HDI), which is an interval that describes the lower and upper bound for 95% of the posterior distribution[110]. Importantly, HDIs summarize the posterior distribution without reference to any fictional experiment which is the case for confidence intervals that represent a core component of the frequentist approach[111].

4 | Data protection and privacy

All studies presented in this thesis contain personal data, broadly defined as any data related to an identified or identifiable person[112]. Therefore, a short introduction to the regulations that permit and guard such research is given here. Section 4.1 describes the ethical aspects and section 4.2 presents the legal aspects as well as data management principles.

4.1 Informed consent and institutional permissions

A key principle of medical practice is informed consent. It refers to patient acceptance of a medical treatment or intervention based on information from the health care provider regarding the risks, benefits and alternatives of a given medical procedure or intervention. Informed consent also applies to situations where a patient is a study participant[113]. Ethically there is a distinction between register-based research projects, which utilize data from sources where data collection is completed and projects that prospectively collect data including human biological material, such as blood samples. This distinction is important in terms of required permissions. Explicitly, it is not possible to opt out of Danish healthcare registries as those are held by the Health Data Authority, while it is possible to opt out of biobanks, where samples are taken in the course of treatment. The opt-out principle that applies to samples from CHB relies on an exemption from the medical informed consent[60].

In Denmark, approvals from e.g., The National Committee on Health Research Ethics, the Data Protection Agency, the Danish Health Authority or the Danish Patient Safety Authority are required before a research project can be conducted. Approvals from the Data Protection Agency and the Danish Health Authority are necessary to conduct studies that analyze registry data [114]. In addition, studies that analyze biological material and EHRs are required to be approved by The National Committee on Health Research Ethics and the Danish Patient Safety Agency.

4.2 Legal regulations and data management

The digital revolution has led to an increase in the volume of personal data, where the digital fingerprint of the individual is being generated faster and at a resolution that is increasing continuously[115]. Thus, the concept of personal data has also evolved and questions regarding data ownership upon informed consent are not trivial. Today, what were formerly principles stated in a European Union directive are now regulated by law in the so-called The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which was introduced in 2018[112]. The overall aim of the GDPR is to balance potential commercial, political and scientific value with the the rights and freedoms of natural persons. The principle of ownership of data about oneself and minimization of the risk of harm arising from data falling in the wrong hands is particularly important to protect with GDPR[115]. Accordingly, there are two different aspects with different implications that are important to remember in the context and discussion of informed consent and legal regulation (e.g. GDPR). First, one consent cannot take the place of the other. That is medical informed consent and GDPR are independent. Secondly, informed consent can be obtained properly, without adequate GDPR consent to data processing, and vice versa[115].

The FAIR Data Principles have been developed to improve the infrastructure that supports the reuse of research data[116]. At the intersection of GDPR and the FAIR Data Principles lies the delicate balance of strengthening a scientific and technological bases, for improving health research while also ensuring safety[112]. In contrast to GDPR, application of the FAIR data principles are not a law, but rather a recommendation for enhanced data management. The FAIR principles do not comprise a goal in itself, but rather considered key to achieve the ambitions within health research while avoiding risks to data subjects. The four principles that comprise the FAIR Data principles are findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. That is, data should be rich in metadata (findability), the study protocol ought to be accessible (accessibility), the data are described using common terminology so external actors can engage in the work with minimal effort (interoperability), and the data and metadata ought to be described at an accuracy that allows for future studies (reusability)[116]. In this context, metadata are any non-primary material containing information on the data that is being analyzed[117].

The FAIR Data Principles were both used indirectly on a daily basis during the past three years but also applied in relation to the publication process. In one study we adhered to the FAIR Data Principles by using the workflow tool *Snakemake* to integrate the pipeline[118]. Figure 13 exemplifies an overview of the data preprocessing generated from *Snakemake*. Similarly, *GitLab* was used for version controlling of software in some of the pipelines[119]. Finally, the results of the study presented in manuscript 6 are somewhat special as they represent the increasing interest in not only peer-reviewed presentation of research results, but also making them available as a resource, in this case a web application[115], [120].

Figure 13: A directed acyclic graph for data preprocessing that shows an attempt to adhere to the FAIR Data principles. Each box represents a rule comprised of in- and output files, a script, necessary resources (i.e. required memory and maximum running time) and potentially also a log file. The box `targets` indicates the destination of the resulting and intermediate files. Colors are arbitrary. From the study presented in manuscript 2.

4.3 Summary of authority approvals

Approvals to analyze data from NPR in the studies presented in this thesis were obtained from the Danish Data Protection Agency (refs: 2015-54-0939 and SUND-2017-57) and the Danish Health Authority (refs: FSEID-00001627 and FSEID-00003092). BTH was approved by the Danish Patient Safety Authority [project number 3-3031-1731/1] and National Committee on Health Research Ethics [project ID 60833]. CHB use was approved by the Danish Data Protection Agency [file number 2007-580015; institutional file number RH2007-30-182 4129/I-suite 00678] and National Committee on Health Research Ethics [approval number 42 183 1708829]. Finally, the analyses of DNPR data were approved by the Danish Data Protection Agency (ref: SUND-2016-83) and the Danish Health Authority (refs: FSEID-00001627, FSEID-00003092, and FSEID-00003096)

5 | Results

5.1 A temporal analysis of multi-morbidity in ischemic heart disease

Up to 85% of IHD patients are multi-morbid meaning that notoriously IHD is a highly heterogeneous phenotype[9]. Although IHD risk factors and complications have been studied for decades, the temporal relationships between them are not fully known. For example, up until 2002, where results from The Framingham Heart Study suggested that coronary artery disease was the most common cause of heart failure, hypertension and valvular diseases had been considered the most common causes[121]. Similarly, the reduction in cardiovascular risk, including IHD, in patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes treated with certain glucose-lowering drugs underlines the complexity of multi-morbidity[122]. Despite these, often complicated, causal relationships most analyses of multi-morbidity in IHD patients are based on absences or presences of risk factors and complications leaving out a considerable amount of information regarding the temporal order of diagnoses[20], [21].

The study presented in manuscript 1 took advantage of the time-stamped diagnosis codes in NPR recorded in the period years 1994–2018 to shed light on the temporal relations between multi-morbidities in IHD, which are currently not fully known (Figure 14). The major focus of the study was to assess if the disease trajectory program could be better optimized to characterize the temporal relations of chronic conditions, particularly focusing on manifestations of multi-morbidity in IHD (cf. section 3.2.2). Study participants consisted in the 552 216 patients in NPR who had been assigned an ICD-10 code for agnina pectoris (I20), acute myocardial infarction (I21), or chronic IHD (I25) in the period years 1995–2018 at age >18 years.

Disease trajectories were used to disentangle IHD risk factors, complications and importantly assess differences in the age distributions for different IHD manifestations. For example, mean age at first diagnosis of myocardial infarction (ICD-10 code: I21) was 62.9 years for patients diagnosed with dyslipidemia and acute myocardial infarction. Similarly, mean age at first diagnosis of acute MI was 62.5 years for patients diagnosed with dyslipidemia, angina pectoris, and acute MI (Table 2). This indicates that in this population the presence of angina pectoris did not change the age distribution for age at diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction (Table 2). Moreover, IHD patients diagnosed with non-insulin-dependent diabetes (ICD-10 code: E11) and heart failure (ICD-10 code:

Figure 14: Conceptual figure illustrating time-stamped diagnosis codes in NPR. Vertically: Six different patients represented by their sequence of assigned diagnosis codes. Labels to the left of each patient indicate their age in year 1994 corresponding to the start of the observation period. Horizontal: Timeline indicating the ICD-10 period in the NPR data dump used. Each circle indicates an ICD-10 code and are labeled accordingly demonstrating that the same ICD-10 code can be assigned multiple times. For a list with ICD-10 descriptions, see table A.2 in appendix A. IHD: Ischemic heart disease. ICD-10: International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, 10th version. NPR: The Danish National Patient Registry. Adapted from manuscript 1.

150) generally had the same age when diagnosed with heart failure as patients diagnosed with non-insulin-dependent diabetes, angina pectoris and heart failure (Table 2). The results of the analysis also showed that atrial fibrillation (ICD-10 code: I48) was more likely to be assigned after myocardial infarction (I21) in IHD patients who were neither diagnosed with angina pectoris nor chronic IHD (ICD-10 code: I25). In contrast, for patients diagnosed with all three manifestations of IHD and atrial fibrillation, acute myocardial infarction was estimated to be diagnosed before atrial fibrillation (Table 2).

In broad terms, these results provide a framework for analyzing the temporal relations of multi-morbidity in IHD by application of the disease trajectory program. The disease trajectories comprise a tool for identifying conditions that are only risk factors or complications as well as conditions that can be risk factors as well as complications which was exemplified above with dyslipidemia and atrial fibrillation, respectively. In comparison to other analyses of IHD risk factors and complications, this study adds information regarding the temporal association within the multi-morbidity spectrum and further highlights differences in age distributions for IHD patients with different IHD manifestations. Ongoing work is centered on further methodological developments to establish trajectories for individual patients. The results of the study presented in manuscript 1 are described in greater detail in the full-length manuscript which is available in chapter 7.

Table 2: Summary statistics of selected disease trajectories.

Population	ICD-10 codes			Mean age in years			Counts	Adj. P	RR
	D1	D2	D3	D1	D2	D3			
All	E78	I21		60.8	62.9		76 334	<0.001	3.69
	E11	I20		61.0	63.0		61 333	<0.001	1.56
	E11	I50		65.6	70.4		42 023	<0.001	2.82
	I20	I50		68.0	71.4		84 955	<0.001	1.94
	E78	I20	I21	61.1	61.6	62.5	48 444		
	E11	I20	I50	64.2	65.6	69.3	23 431		
I21	I21	I48		73.3	76.3		11 871	<0.001	1.09
I20, I21, I25	I48	I21		69.4	71.2		26 273	<0.001	1.09

From manuscript 1.

5.2 A strategy to define more homogeneous ischemic heart disease patient subgroups

Traditionally, multi-morbidity has been quantified with reference to a few selected diseases and summarized in an index such as CCI. Some even argue that there does not exist any replicable profiles of multi-morbidity[27], [123]. To accommodate these limitations in future multi-morbidity classification systems, it has been argued that it is necessary to study it comprehensively, rather than purely assessing the presence of individual diseases in a binary fashion[9]. Studies that classify ischemic heart disease patients as well as heart failure patients based on application of cluster analyses to EHRs data have already been conducted[77], [124], [125]. Yet, cluster analysis in this domain is still relatively unexplored where the analyses are often limited to few diagnoses and thus only analyze a fraction of the available healthcare data volumes. Thus, there is a need to explore the potential of EHRs in this domain.

To this end, the study presented in manuscript 2 addresses multi-morbidity in IHD based on a flexible clustering analysis of multi-morbidity by application of the MCL algorithm to the diagnosis codes of 74 249 IHD patients identified in NPR (Figure 15). The physiological relevance of the clusters (i.e. patient subgroups) obtained by application of the MCL algorithm was assessed based on an enrichment analysis with respect to the diagnosis codes, a comparison of the subgroups that included estimates of risk for disease progression; and characterization derived from blood test results and PGS obtained from EHRs and CHB, respectively.⁶

Application of the MCL algorithm to the entire set of diagnosis codes assigned prior to IHD onset resulted in identification of high- and low-risk patient subgroups. Patient subgroups were classified as high- or low-risk based on survival analysis. For example, among three of the male subgroups

⁶For an in-depth description of the enrichment analyses as well as analyses of the biochemical and genetic data please refer to the full-length manuscript available in chapter 8.

Figure 15: Conceptual figure of the patient representation in the cluster analysis. The entire cohort is illustrated to the left and the vectors for five patients are illustrated on the right. A sample of diagnosis codes are listed horizontally in the upper right. Black circles indicate that diagnoses were assigned before IHD onset (included in cluster analysis). Hollow circles indicate diagnoses which were assigned after IHD onset (not included in cluster analysis). t_0 : IHD onset. IHD: Ischemic heart disease. Adapted from manuscript 2.

(total of 31), mean age at IHD onset ranged between 54.9 and 62.4 years. These three patient subgroups were also characterized by different risks of disease progression, as the patients in one subgroup associated with reduced risk of progression (i.e. primary outcome) when compared to the the risk of the patients who were not in this subgroup. In contrast, the two other subgroups associated with increased risk of progression (Table 3). The results of the enrichment analysis showed that one of the subgroups characterized by increased risk of disease progression was enriched for diabetes whereas the other was enriched for more unspecific diagnoses such as diastasis of the muscle. Interestingly, the subgroup characterized by reduced risk of disease progression was enriched for acute MI. The distributions of PGS for total cholesterol (TC) and LDL cholesterol levels were significantly different in this subgroup with positive effect directions (Table 3). That is, patients in this subgroup generally had higher PGS for TC and LDL levels than the patients who were not in this subgroup.

In sum, the study presented in manuscript 2 exemplified that application of the MCL algorithm to the entire multi-morbidity spectrum of IHD patients can be used to discriminate between high- and low-risk IHD patients. Further, the study illustrates how, potentially, more homogeneous patient subgroups can be used to identify subgroups with genetic associations where PGS have positive or negative effect sizes (Table 3). In comparison to other cluster analyses of cardiovascular phenotypes, we developed a flexible approach that analyze input data in a data-driven manner based on the analogy to text documents[125]. Further, the characterization of the clusters involved addition of data sources and thus presents a pragmatic solution to reduce the impact of an inflated type I error rate[86], [124]. Potentially the methods presented in this study can be further optimized and outperform traditional multi-morbidity scores. In its current form, the discrimination of the subgroups is equally as good as CCI overall and in some subgroups, it is better. The results are presented more elaborately in the full-length manuscript, which is available in chapter 8.

Table 3: Summary statistics and characteristics for selected male clusters.

Cluster	Mean age Years at index	HR, primary outcome			Main enrichment	PGS (effect direction)
		HR	95% CI	Adj. P		
4.M01	58.5	0.93	0.87 to 0.99	0.030	Acute myocardial infarction	TC(+), I25(-) LDL(+)
4.M02	62.4	1.51	1.40 to 1.62	<0.001	Diabetes	E11(+)
4.M25	54.9	1.38	1.15 to 1.65	0.030	Diastasis of muscle	

From manuscript 2.

5.3 Mortality in ischemic heart disease from a time-to-event machine learning algorithm

Today, IHD patient prognostication is being carried out with risk prediction tools that largely have remained unchanged for decades[83]. While the volumes and variety of data are increasing in complexity, risk scoring algorithms are commonly extrapolated from classical regressions that model linear relationships between a limited set of well-characterized predictive features[11]. Machine learning methods, such as ANNs comprise a potential methodological solution to the fact that the increasingly complex healthcare data require analytical capabilities that often exceed that of the human mind[95]. There are already promising results of patient risk prediction models developed using machine learning methods within the cardiovascular domain[126], [127]. However, there are still no examples of risk predictions models in IHD where input features are being included based on availability rather than assumptions regarding their predictive value.

Therefore, the study presented in manuscript 3 introduces $PMHnet\text{-}\alpha$, an ANN-based survival model developed by application of a generic approach that was originally described by Gensheimer et al[128]. Based on a derivation cohort identified in EDHR, $PMHnet\text{-}\alpha$ was developed to predict all-cause mortality in IHD patients from 596 input features (Figure 16). The premise of the study was that the summarized predictive value of many features with varying predictive value could comprise a prediction model with higher performance than the summarized predictive value of fewer, highly predictive features.

After model development, $PMHnet\text{-}\alpha$ achieved excellent performance and outperformed the GRACE 2.0 risk model in validation with a tdAUC of 0.869 at the one-year evaluation time point (Table 4). Using SHAP values, we were able to quantify the predictive importance of all 595 input features obtained from a combination of the different data types (Figure 16). The SHAP values enabled us to discriminate between the importance of different input features at a global and at a specific level. In a model based solely on diagnosis codes (ICD-10 codes), the diagnoses with the largest predictive values globally were diabetes (E11), acute myocardial infarction (I21), atrial fibrillation (I48), heart failure (I50) and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (J44). All of them reduced the chances of survival. In contrast, the presence of angina pectoris (I20), disorders of lipoprotein metabolism and other lipidaemias (E78), open wound of wrist or hand (S61) and routine examination of specific systems (Z01) increased the chances of survival. In the model that was trained on all 595 input features, age was, not surprisingly, the most predictive variable. Interest-

Figure 16: Overview of the development of PMHnet- α . A: Derivation cohort where the input features of four patients are illustrated as indicated by the four dashed lines. B: The different data types that were used as input features. C: A schematic representation of the PMHnet- α architecture. D: PMHnet- α output here illustrated by survival curves for four individual patients. From manuscript 3.

ingly, only troponins were among the most predictive features in evaluation of the performance at six months after index, whereas other biochemical tests taken before IHD onset were only among the most predictive features at the one-year and three-years evaluation timepoint. PMHnet- α is currently being validated at partner hospitals in Norway and Iceland, respectively.

Table 4: Validation and benchmarking of PMHnet- α .

Outcome	Without imputation		With imputation	
	PMHnet- α	GRACE 2.0	PMHnet- α	GRACE 2.0
Six-months all-cause mortality	0.876	0.770	0.883	0.770
One-year all-cause mortality	0.869	0.782	0.872	0.756
Three-years all-cause mortality	0.843	0.738	0.831	0.727

From manuscript 3.

Altogether, PMHnet- α exemplifies how data-driven studies can improve the performance of risk prediction both by analyzing non-linearly interacting features and also by including hundreds of features. Moreover, the study presents a solution to the common critique against machine

learning methods as $PMHnet-\alpha$ is an explainable model. For example, the SHAP analysis provided a framework for understanding why $PMHnet-\alpha$ based on diagnosis codes only had a similar performance to that of the GRACE 2.0 risk score. In contrast to other machine learning models within the cardiovascular domain, $PMHnet-\alpha$ was developed with essentially no a priori assumptions regarding potential predictive value[126]. We argue that this is an advantage in favour of $PMHnet-\alpha$ as the attribute makes it broadly applicable and presumably adaptable in to many different healthcare systems where data types and availability vary. This argument is presented more thoroughly in the full-length manuscript available in chapter 9, which is currently being prepared for submission.

5.4 Evidence of drug-drug interactions in electronic health records

Multi-morbid patients, including IHD patients, are commonly subjected to polypharmacy which is often rooted in the simultaneous prescriptions of life-long treatment regimens[31]. Polypharmacy puts patients at risk of adverse drug reactions and reduces the likelihood of compliance. Traditionally, it has primarily been quantified with reference to the number of drugs only and drugs are rarely prescribed to patients who are diagnosed with only one chronic disease[30], [32]. In effect, evidence regarding the true therapeutic effect of drugs in multi-morbid patients is lacking as they are typically excluded from RCTs[9], [30]. This is particularly important in the context of IHD, where there are a wealth of different options for drugs used in primary and secondary treatment[129].

Figure 17: Conceptual figure illustrating concomitant treatment episodes during a hypothetical hospital admission. Three different drugs are depicted. Drug A (blue) is prescribed in two different regimens. Drug B (pink) is prescribed in three different regimens. Drug C (green) is prescribed one time. Three different modifications were considered: Drug addition, dosage adjustment, and drug discontinuation. ADD: Average daily dose. D/C: Discontinuation. From manuscript 4.

The objective of the study presented in manuscript 4 was to analyze polypharmacy with reference to drug dosage alterations based on in-hospital prescriptions from 1 069 873 hospitalized patients in the period years 2008 to 2016. Drug dosage alterations were analyzed systematically by identifying concomitant treatment episodes, defined by a point in time where a patient was prescribed two different drugs. Concomitant treatment episodes with a significant likelihood of dosage adjustments were defined as co-medication pairs comprised of an index-drug and a co-drug (Figure 17). Co-medication pairs were characterized specifically with reference to selected examples and also collectively by cross-referencing the results with data from 15 publicly available drug-drug interaction databases[130].

A total of 920 distinct drugs administered over a period of eight years gave rise to identification of 77 494 concomitant treatment episodes. In the data, there were a total of 3993 co-medication pairs. Index drugs were dominated by drugs belonging to the anatomical classes nervous system (ATC 1st level: N), cardiovascular system (ATC 1st C), and alimentary tract and metabolism system (ATC 1st A). Drugs classified as antithrombotic agents (ATC 2nd level: B01) and ACE inhibitors (ATC 2nd level: C09) were among the drugs that most frequently appeared as index drugs. They were represented in 316 (7.9%) and 155 (3.8%) of the co-medication pairs, respectively (Table 5). As expected, acetylsalicylic acid and clopidogrel comprised an example of a co-medication pair. Thus, when acetylsalicylic acid was co-administered with clopidogrel a dosage change in acetylsalicylic acid was 2.24 times more likely than in cases where acetylsalicylic acid was administered as monotherapy. Similarly, clopidogrel was 1.52 times more likely to be dosages adjusted when co-administered with acetylsalicylic acid. Moreover, atorvastatin had an odds ratio of 1.31 for a dosage alteration when co-administered with clopidogrel. Thus the co-medication pairs represented expected as well as more surprising examples of dosage adjustments (Table 5).

Table 5: Examples of co-medication pairs from highly represented therapeutic subgroups.

Overview			Selected co-medication pairs			
ATC 2 nd	Index N	Co-drug N	Index drug	Co-drug	Odds ratio	95% HDI
A02	105	176	Pantoprazole	Terlipressin	2.26	1.88 to 2.79
B01	316	314	Acetylsalicylic acid	Clopidogrel	2.24	2.03 to 2.49
			Clopidogrel	Acetylsalicylic acid	1.52	1.39 to 1.67
			Enoxaparin	Liraglutide	1.78	1.23 to 2.61
C07	116	137	Metoprolol	Rifampicin	1.45	1.09 to 1.94
C09	155	150	Losartan	Quetiapine	1.32	1.10 to 1.57
C10	111	129	Atorvastatin	Clopidogrel	1.31	1.18 to 1.44
N07	56	52	Disulfiram	Pantoprazole	1.20	1.05 to 1.37

From manuscript 4.

Of the 3993 co-medication pairs, there were 3297 pairs that were already entries in a drug-drug interaction database. We argue that the remaining 696 drugs represent potential drug-drug interactions, given that the dosage adjustments are not rooted in clinical routines or guideline recommendations with other reationals than pure drug-drug interactions. Overall, the study presented in manuscript 4 exemplifies the potential importance of data-driven studies in this domain. The study adds to the literature by (i) presenting a model of actual in-hospital treatment patterns in

a population that is representative of patients hospitalized in Denmark and (ii) by capturing rarer therapeutic drug combinations that are not necessarily captured in smaller studies of polypharmacy. In this respect, cardiovascular drugs generally served as good positive controls during model interpretation both with respect to the quantity and quality, corresponding to the number content of the co-medications pairs. The results of the study are presented and discussed in greater detail in the full-length manuscript which is available in chapter 10.

5.5 Establishing a map of longitudinal, nation-wide prescription patterns

Most of the drugs that are prescribed as primary or secondary prevention in treatment of IHD and related multi-morbidity are being prescribed life-long[30]. Although the number of patients needed to treat to expect to prevent one adverse event are high; the process of *deprescription* is not standard in clinical care[131], [132]. Yet, there is only limited knowledge of the long-term consequences of polypharmacy, which is becoming even more prevalent in the ageing population[75]. Albeit these facts, very few studies have analyzed the long-term consequences of drugs used to treat multi-morbidity, including IHD[30], [32]. Based on prescription trajectories established from 7 255 919 people in DNPR, the study presented in manuscript 5 mapped longitudinal prescription patterns in an entire Danish population over the years 1995 to 2019.

This study transformed the individual level prescriptions in DNPR into 38 607 prescription trajectories of two distinct drugs that were most likely to be prescribed in a specific order. For example, the RR of redeeming digitalis glycoside after a beta blocking agent was 3.55 (95% CI: 2.30 to 5.47, $P < 0.001$) compared to patients with no prior redemption of a beta-blocking agent. This observation is consistent with intensification of arrhythmia treatment and thus served as a positive control. We also found that redemption of direct factor Xa inhibitors associated with a reduced risk of subsequent redemption of other anti-dementia drugs (RR: 0.41, 95% CI: 0.37 to 0.46, $P < 0.001$). This association between anti-coagulative therapy exemplifies that data-driven studies can assist in identifying associations that are unlikely to be identified in purely hypothesis-driven studies. Potentially this specific prescription trajectory even points to a role of antithrombotic agents in primary prevention of stroke. Prescription trajectories that contained two prescriptions were also pieced together to form prescription trajectories of up to seven different prescriptions. We used this strategy to map the order of anti-hypertensive treatments for patients being prescribed up to seven different drugs within this drug group (i.e. anti-hypertension drugs). For example, only in very few cases did people who were prescribed an aldosterone antagonists (C03DA) redeem a prescription on another anti-hypertensive drug afterwards. And this trend seemed to be irrespective of the previous redeemed prescriptions as there were few prescription pairs on the right side of boxes labeled C03DA (Figure 18).

Taken together, the prescription trajectories modelled polypharmacy in a novel manner and supported analyses of up to six different anti-hypertensive drugs prescribed to the same person over the course of 25 years (Figure 18). The results indicate that there is a considerable room for improvement when it comes to decisions regarding treatment regimens. It is of course important to

Figure 18: Alluvial plot illustrating the complexity of anti-hypertensive treatment. Each vertical bar represents an ATC level 4 code containing anti-hypertensive drugs. Grey ribbons that connect the vertical bars represent a prescription trajectory comprised of two prescriptions, where the RR risk of redeeming the drug on the left first is higher than redeemed the drug on the right first. The height of the vertical bars corresponds to the number of people who follow all the prescription trajectories going from one vertical bar to another (left to right). ATC: Anatomical Therapeutic and Chemical Classification. RR: relative risk. From manuscript 5.

interpret the results with caution. For example aldosterone antagonists are often considered an "add-on" drug in treatment of hypertension[133]. Also, any disease progression that could have been the rationale for changing treatment regimens were not included in the analysis. We argue that, given further model refinement, this concept of prescription trajectories can assist clinical decision making by identification of people where it is unlikely that they will respond sufficiently to first-line therapy. The full-length manuscript is presented in chapter 11.

5.6 Internet applications display perspectives with data-driven research

Most existing software developed to study healthcare data do either require users to upload their own data or limit users to query within a specific domain[134], [135]. It is paramount for data-driven research that the results of the analyses are being evaluated continuously as their usefulness often depends on proper examples [63]. The results described in sections above are presented with reference to relatively few examples that assist in interpretation of the model leaving out, potentially,

relevant information. To this end, we have developed The Danish Disease Trajectory Browser (DTB) which is an example of a software tool where users can decide which example to analyze.

The study presented in manuscript 6 introduces DTB which is a web application that makes the disease trajectory program available to anybody, including people without coding experience, given internet access, and at the same time establishing a platform for model critique and suggestions. The browser was developed as a tool that enables users to characterize a phenotype of interest using disease trajectories. A set of functionalities were added to the browser, including search filters, that for example enable users to search for disease trajectories computed from either males or females. As the browser only contains summary statistics it does not provide any access to personal data.

Figure 19: Screenshot from the DTB home page. The home page has three central elements: a search bar in the middle, an upper horizon ribbon and a vertical side panel to the right. In the search bar users can type in an ICD-10 code of interest, e.g. I25. Users can decide if the results of the query should be represented as a disease trajectory network or linear disease trajectories. The upper horizontal bar has a variety of different buttons that can be used to navigate the interactive phase that will replace the area with the search bar, when a query has been placed. The vertical side panel has the different search filters and options regarding layout and downloads. DTB: Danish Disease Trajectory Browser From manuscript 6.

DTB is made available at <http://dtb.cpr.ku.dk/> and lets users characterize a phenotype by providing access to nearly 25 years of data from more than seven million people. Users can query

DTB by specifying a case population in the form of level 3 ICD-10 codes, e.g. I25 for chronic IHD (Figure 19). The main result of the study was that the results of the disease trajectory program became publicly available with an interactive interface. Potentially, this may lead to future developments of the program that are based on input from a broad range of research communities. DTB has a user-friendly interface that was developed to support a graphical representation of temporal associations between diagnoses in NPR data. This is becoming more important than ever as large healthcare data are becoming increasingly difficult to manage and analyse because data volumes and variety are growing faster than ever. Search results are available for download as graphical representations or data tables with summary statistics. Moreover, a range of search filters can be applied to customize the query. Filters include number of diagnoses per trajectory, range for number of patients that should follow a trajectory for it to be included in the search, range for RRs and sex (males only, females only or both). The study exemplifies that the digital development and technologies provide new opportunities of sharing research results. This will obviously also make them more prone to external critique. We argue that in the long run, both researchers, clinicians, and patients will benefit from this level of transparency which hand-on usage and queries facilitates. To this end, DTB and other similar projects are only the beginning. The browser functionalities and interpretation of the disease trajectories are described in greater detail in the full-length manuscript, which is presented in chapter 12.

6 | Discussion

This thesis was based on a total of six original investigations where comprehensive analyses of Danish healthcare data were performed. The thesis was based on studies that take the temporality of disease occurrence in IHD patients into account as well as studies that analyzed multi-morbidity in IHD without considering the temporal relation. In this context, it is the first thesis conducted using Danish healthcare data that integrates data-driven investigations focused on multi-morbidity and polypharmacy, respectively. The main argument of the thesis is that it is necessary to study these two phenomena, i.e. multi-morbidity and polypharmacy, in parallel and ultimately in concert in order to translate the data sources that are growing into clinically actionable evidence.

Overall, I have presented an overview of IHD along with the data sources that comprised the foundation for the studies that the thesis was based on. Similarly, the data-driven methods that were employed to study multi-morbidity in IHD using Danish healthcare data have been presented. Finally, the results of the studies were briefly described and the full-length manuscripts are available in chapters 7 through 12.

The main conclusion from the studies is presented in section 6.1. Next, strengths and limitations of the models as well as some general considerations regarding data-driven research are discussed in section 6.2. Finally, section 6.3 briefly elaborates on potentials and future perspectives for the studies that formed the spine of this thesis.

6.1 Conclusion

The hypothesis of the thesis was that data-driven studies based on comprehensive analysis of Danish healthcare data are of value in patient phenotyping and that they can complement classical epidemiological studies. In chapter 1, I introduced the foundations for performing data-driven research using Danish healthcare system and briefly described some of the pioneering international initiatives in this respect. Based on this introduction, we can conclude that there is a need to rethink the strategies for studying IHD patients, as they now live longer and with more chronic diseases than they did years ago[9]. Similarly, the digitized reality fosters new options for studying IHD patients and translating the wealth of healthcare data into clinically actionable evidence.

The studies that this thesis is based on exemplify that that it is indeed possible to establish models of multi-morbidity in IHD, where Danish disease-spectrum wide healthcare data is analyzed

comprehensively. The results of the three main manuscripts contain rather different strategies for studying multi-morbidity in IHD using data-driven strategies as they include an analysis of the temporal order of IHD risk factors and complications (manuscript 1), a strategy for developing a data-driven multi-morbidity score (manuscript 2), and a risk prediction algorithm that outperforms a classical risk scoring scheme (manuscript 3).

The studies that were developed without focusing on a particular phenotype, further exemplify the potential of data-driven models. The studies that addressed polypharmacy present novel strategies for studying some of the consequences of multi-morbidity by focusing on drug-dosage adjustments and mapping nation-wide prescription patterns, respectively. By application of a data-driven strategy to drug prescriptions the studies identified treatment regimens that are likely to be overlooked in studies with pre-defined outcomes (manuscript 4) and described the complex prescription patterns at a nationwide scale (manuscript 5). In both cases, cardiovascular drugs were a rich source of positive controls while also exemplifying a field with key challenges owing as both treatment options and number of patients are increasing. In concert, the studies address the dual nature of multi-morbidity and multi-morbidity treatment. Last, DTB exemplifies how data-driven models can be made available to others and thereby enrich the scientific community while also being exposed to critique that eventually will improve tools for studying multi-morbidity (manuscript 6).

6.2 Strengths and limitations

All data-driven studies come with sets of strengths as well as limitations[63]. A major strength of the studies that this thesis is based on, is that they are largely representative of the patients treated in the Danish healthcare system. In other words, study participants were generally selected from complete population-wide data that have not been subjected to same strict exclusion criteria which is often the case in RCTs. This is also a limitation as interpretation of the results is not necessarily straightforward when the investigations were set out without a concrete hypothesis, but rather a general idea that data-driven studies will benefit the scientific community, including patients, in the long run[63], [65]. Yet, the importance of modelling strategies that include multi-morbid patients, who are often excluded from RCTs can only be underscored as clinical relevant differences between these patient populations is already evident[31], [70].

The aphorism “garbage in, garbage out” mentioned in chapter 1 is obviously also a critique against the studies presented in this thesis[47]. Explicitly, the majority of the studies presented in this thesis were based on data from secondary care. There are three major limitations to their usage. First, one could argue that NPR is not the optimal data source for studying multi-morbidities as they, for the most part, are managed in the setting of primary care. Thus, it is important to bear in mind that the temporal associations established using the disease trajectory program rely on the fact that the patients went to the hospital. Similarly, diagnosis codes in NPR do come with a certain degree of inaccuracies, both with respect to false positives and false negatives[136]. Last, the administrative nature of the diagnosis codes also mean that they are volatile for other reasons than reasons related to the phenotype (Figure 7). The studies present different strategies for reducing the impact of these limitations related to the input data, although it is nearly impossible to escape these limitations completely. In its current form, there is also another limitation with the disease as well as the

prescription trajectories, which is that the method does not distinguish between chronic and acute conditions or treatments, respectively. However, the majority of the examples presented in this thesis represent chronic conditions and thus the results indicate that the strategy can be used to study multi-morbidity in IHD.

In contrast to the registry data, the data in CHB has a stronger selection bias, as the genetic data originates from patients where it was necessary to perform blood-type testing or red cell antibody screening[60]. Thus, patients in CHB are not representative of patients in, for example NPR. In this respect, it is also worth mentioning the potential degree of technical missingness in a dataset such as BTH. In the study presented in manuscript 2, however, we did perform quality controls to assess if the patients in BTH were representative of the entire cohort.

The fact that the models presented in this thesis were generated in an environment that aims to produce transparent code is a general advantage. For example, DTB lets users gain hand-on experience with the disease trajectory program, which can then be optimized to fit needs and demands within specific subject-areas. On a day-to-day level the aim to produce transparent code and reproducible workflows is also crucial to model development and external validation. Explicitly, the code that was used to generate IHD subgroups based on application of the MCL algorithm has been transferred to Statistics Denmark for application on other data types. Similarly, external validation of `PMHnet-alpha` has been made easier technically owing to transparent workflows.

The overall strength of the studies presented in this thesis is that they acknowledge that multi-morbidity is a disease spectrum, rather than a matter of absence and presence of chronic diseases, that are managed individually[9]. For example, both the clustering analysis and `PMHnet-alpha` provide frameworks for studying e.g. diabetic patients with and without increased risk of mortality. This results from the fact that not all diabetes patients would cluster together, and similarly that the SHAP values for same feature would often vary between patients. However, the actual interpretation of these observations have, for now, only just begun.

6.3 Perspectives

There are two major perspectives with the studies presented in this thesis. One is translation of `PMHnet-alpha` into clinical practice and another is further model development, for example by taking socio-economic factors better into account. Another important perspective is to provide further evidence that these studies do in fact to complement classical epidemiological studies. The first perspective necessitates successful external validation followed by successfully addressing the ethical challenges that are an inherent part of machine learning in medicine[137]. Accomplishment of the second major perspective requires continued collaboration between bioinformaticians and clinicians so the explorative models can be optimized to answer concrete scientific questions and serve clinical needs. Here, it is crucial to identify the examples that can serve as an argument for the relevance of the models. In this respect, another perspective is also to optimize the Danish healthcare data for usage in data-driven models. For example, data from NPR and DNPR could be integrated to obtain a more precise estimate of IHD onset. This strategy has been adopted successfully in classical epidemiological studies[138].

At the current stage the studies also contribute as potential hypothesis-generating engines and importantly, a platform for improvement. For example, the cluster analysis presented a framework for identification of patient subgroups where PGS are more likely to associate with the aetiology than others, given their association with only some clusters. In fact, I did contribute to a collaboration with Statistics Denmark, where the objective is to migrate the clustering pipeline to their machines and test if the MCL algorithm identifies the same patient subgroups if prescription data rather than diagnosis codes is the input. Similarly, the presence of co-medication pairs that are currently undescribed in the literature are evidence that current modelling strategies, e.g. selection criteria, ought to be revised.

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List of abbreviations

ANN	Artificial neural network
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical
BTH	BigTempHealth
CABG	Coronary artery by-pass grafting
CAG	Coronary arteriography
CCI	Charlson co-morbidity index
CHB	Copenhagen Hospital Biobank
Cox PH	Cox proportional hazard
CRS	The Danish Civil Registration System
DAR	The Danish Registry for Causes of Death
DNPR	The Danish National Prescription Registry
DTB	The Danish Disease Trajectory Browser
ECG	Electrocardiogram
EDHR	The Eastern Danish Heart Registry
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GRACE	Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events
HDI	Highest density interval
HDL	High-density lipoprotein
HR	Hazard ratio
ICD	International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems
IHD	Ischemic heart disease

LDL	Low-density lipoprotein
LR	Linear regression
MCL	Markov Cluster
MCMC	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
MI	Myocardial infarction
NCSP	NOMESCO Classification of Surgical Procedures
NOMESCO	Nordic Medico-Statistical Committee
NPR	The Danish National Patient Registry
NPU	Nomenclature, Properties and Units
OTC	Over-the-counter
PCI	Percutaneous coronary intervention
PGS	Polygenic score
RCTs	Randomized controlled trial
RR	Relative risk
SGD	Stochastic gradient descent
SHAP value	SHapley Additive exPlanations value
SKS	Sundhedsvæsenets Klassifikationssystem
tdAUC	Time-dependent area under curve
tf-idf	term frequency-inverse document frequency
WHO	World Health Organization

Part II

FULL-LENGTH MANUSCRIPTS

7 | Temporality in ischemic heart disease multi-morbidity

Temporality in ischemic heart disease multi-morbidity

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Abstract

Importance: As electronic health data volumes and their diversity increase, phenotypes derived from data-driven models may prove clinically valuable for more accurately sub-categorizing patients with ischemic heart disease (IHD).

Objective: In this retrospective cohort study the objective was to study multi-morbidity in IHD based on a comprehensive analysis of nation-wide health registry data covering all hospital admissions.

Design: Retrospective cohort study of disease progression patterns in patients with IHD based on secondary healthcare data from The Danish National Patient Registry (NPR). Disease progression patterns were modelled as disease trajectories defined as time-ordered series of diagnoses. Relative risk scores derived from a series of Bernoulli trials were used to quantify the strength of diagnostic correlations, i.e., diagnostic co-occurrences (D1, D2). Subsequently, linear regression models were used to obtain directional diagnosis pairs, defined by two diagnoses D1 and D2 with a significant age difference between age at diagnosis D1 and D2. Directional diagnosis pairs were then used as basis for constructing disease trajectories of three diagnoses.

Setting: A nationwide study using secondary healthcare data.

Participants: All patients in NPR, who had been assigned a time-stamped ICD-10 code for angina pectoris (I20), acute myocardial infarction (I21) or chronic IHD (I25) in the period 1994-2018.

Exposures: None.

Main outcomes: None.

Results: In a cohort of 552 216 IHD disease patients, we identified 1 459 directional diagnosis pairs. IHD risk factors, e.g., dyslipidemia and hypertension always appeared as the first diagnoses in the directional diagnosis pairs, while there were both examples of directional diagnosis pairs where atrial fibrillation appeared as the first as well as the second diagnosis. Osteoporosis was among the diagnoses that appeared in most directional diagnosis pairs. In some cases, the order of the diagnoses was changed when comparing disease trajectories of two versus three diagnoses.

Conclusion and relevance: Disease trajectories can be used to characterize the longitudinal multi-morbidity landscape of IHD based on comprehensive analysis of nationwide healthcare registry data. It provides a framework for discovery of new associations and draws attention to circumstances under which a disease is a consequence of age rather than a complication to another disease.

Introduction

Ischemic heart disease (IHD) is a common, chronic, multifactorial disease that is one of the leading causes of death¹. Up to 85% of IHD patients are diagnosed with other chronic diseases (i.e. multi-morbid), which impact the disease course and severity of disease². However, replicable profiles of multi-morbidity are rare and the models do not generally focus on the temporality³. While evidence within the single-disease paradigm is extensive, studies designed to analyze the full multi-morbidity spectrum are few⁴⁻⁸. As age is a primary risk factor for manifestation of multi-morbidity and consequently is endemic in some populations⁹. Thus, multi-morbidity, including IHD and common IHD risk factors including conditions related to the metabolic syndrome and other cardiovascular diseases are typically diagnosed within few years making it non-trivial to unmask true etiology^{10,11}. For example, the risk of developing atrial fibrillation doubles for every decade of advanced age and is also a major risk indicator after myocardial infarction^{12,13}. Also, results of the Framingham Heart Study have suggested that IHD rather than hypertension and valvular disease, is the most common cause of heart failure¹⁴. Yet, clinical management of IHD often comes down to absence or presence of risk factors and co-morbidities, leaving out information related to the specific temporality of the disease history as a whole^{10,15}.

The reduction in cardiovascular risk, including risk of IHD, in patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes treated with certain glucose-lowering drugs is further evidence that multi-morbidity covers a phenotypic spectrum, where conventional diagnostics may fall short^{16,17}. Moreover, multi-morbid patients are generally under-represented in randomized controlled trials¹⁸. In turn, the literature supports the argument that improved understanding of multi-morbidity will facilitate improved healthcare delivery, which is becoming increasingly important in the ageing populations^{10,11,16,18-20}.

Temporal disease trajectories, defined as time-ordered series of diagnoses, were originally developed as a disease-agnostic model of disease progression patterns in the setting of nation-wide registry data and have recently been made available as a web application^{21,22}. The applicability of this method is evident, as it has been used to study e.g. sex-specific disease progression patterns, stratify sepsis patients, discriminate between distinct dementia subtypes and identify unique co-morbidity signatures among patients with chromosomal abnormalities²³⁻²⁵. However, the original disease trajectory program did not adjust for medical surveillance bias, which is often an aspect of nationwide cohort studies²⁶. Here, we present the results of a study that was set out to obtain a refined understanding of IHD by characterizing multi-morbidity in IHD using a novel version of the disease trajectory approach. An explicit focus was to correct for biases related to repeated diagnoses in nationwide registry data.

Methods

Data foundation and study population

The main data source was the Danish National Patient Registry (NPR), where healthcare data from all encounters with a Danish hospital have been recorded since 1977. The data includes contact type (i.e. in-patient, out-patient and emergency room visits), date of contact start (e.g. admission), date of discharge, diagnosis codes and diagnosis type (e.g. primary codes that best describe the contact reason and secondary codes that complement the description of the contact)²⁷. To obtain demographic data on patients such as date of birth, sex and status (dead or alive), data from NPR was linked to the Danish Civil Registration System (CRS) via the personal identification number²⁸. Since 1994, diagnoses in NPR have been reported using the International Statistical Classification of Disease and Health Related Problems 10th Revision (ICD-10), which has a hierarchical structure comprising ICD-10 chapters, code blocks, level 3 and level 4 codes²⁹.

The NPR dataset used in this study covers the period 1994-2018 and contains data from 7 179 538 people corresponding to more than 142 million admissions. It contains 4 565 distinct level 3 ICD-10 codes, which we here refer to as ICD-10 codes. Prior to analysis, level 4 codes were truncated to level 3 codes³⁰. Patients that were deceased by the end of the study period were assigned the code Y99 and date of death was obtained from CRS²⁸. To define the case population, all patients in NPR who had been assigned an ICD-10 code for angina pectoris (ICD-10 code: I20), acute myocardial infarction (ICD-10 code: I21) or chronic ischemic heart disease (ICD-10 code I25) in the period 1994-2018 were first identified. Next, patients who were assigned either of the diagnosis codes I20, I21, or I25 before the age of 18 years were excluded. Emigrants and tourists were also excluded, as their contacts with the Danish health-care system are likely to be sporadic and thus, not appropriate for modeling the temporality of IHD co-morbidities. All ICD-10 codes from chapters I-XIV assigned as a primary or secondary code (i.e., diagnosis types A, B or G) were included in the analysis. Codes assigned to less than 25 patients were excluded (Figure 1). Date of discharge in NPR was used to estimate age at first diagnosis (via linkage to CRS), identify pairs of diagnosis codes that were assigned to the same patient (i.e., diagnostic co-occurrences), define time-ordered directional diagnosis pairs and build disease trajectories.

Experimental model and identification of diagnostic co- occurrences

To study the temporal order of the entire spectrum of multi-morbidities in IHD patients, directional diagnosis pairs were computed and pieced together to form longer disease trajectories comprising three diagnoses. Disease trajectories were obtained by application of a modified version of the

disease trajectory program²¹. The two main steps in the program are (i) quantification of the overrepresentation of diagnostic co-occurrences between two diagnosis using relative risk (RR) and (ii) identification of directional diagnostic co-occurrences where the temporal order in which the diagnoses are assigned is statistically significant (i.e., directional diagnosis pairs).

The first step (i) consists of a binomial test procedure that was developed in the original version of the disease trajectory program. Here all patients discharged with assignment of a certain diagnosis (e.g. D1) are considered exposed²¹. Following a pre-filtering step that uses the mean probability of assignment of any diagnosis from all discharges with diagnosis D1 (i.e., mean probability parameter), RRs for the diagnosis pairs (D1, D2) were obtained by considering each discharge as a Bernoulli sample. The algorithm then tests for statistical significance of the diagnosis pairs (D1, D2) being assigned to the same patient within five years compared to the mean probability parameter for D1. For each patient that were assigned diagnosis D1 at discharge (i.e., exposed), 10 000 comparison groups were formed by sampling from groups that were matched by sex, year of birth and week of discharge to correct for e.g., seasonal variation in diagnosis codes and changes in coding practices. RRs were then calculated as the ratio of exposed patients who were assigned diagnosis D2 compared to the ratio of unexposed patients who were assigned diagnosis D2. The level of significance was set to 0.001 to guard against false positives due to the binomial test procedure. The algorithm was run using R v. 3.4.0, Python v. 2.7, Python v. 3 and C++v. 11^{21,22}.

Defining directional diagnosis pairs and building disease trajectories

The second step (ii) in the program establishes the directionality of diagnostic co-occurrences²¹. In contrast to previous versions of the disease trajectory program, a series of linear regression models (LRs) was introduced in this step. LRs were introduced to identify diagnostic co-occurrences (D1, D2) with a statistically significant difference between age at diagnoses D1 and D2, respectively. In cases where a patient was assigned the same ICD-10 code multiple times, only the earliest recorded diagnosis (with reference to end of contact) was included. In cases where a patient was assigned more than one diagnosis for the first time at the same contact, these instances would be included in the model.

The dependent variable for the LRs was age at diagnosis and the independent variables were the diagnosis pair from step (i) (D1, D2), the type of diagnosis (A or B/G corresponding to primary or non-primary diagnosis), discharge date, type of patient (in-patient or out-patient), year of birth, and sex. These covariates were included to account for the possibility of differences in baseline

characteristics at diagnosis due to factors not related to the pathogenesis, e.g., changes in coding practice over the years. The P-value of the main effect for the diagnosis pair variable was used to determine the significance of difference in age between D1 and D2, where the predicted age at diagnoses D1 and D2 defined disease directionality. P-values were adjusted using the Bonferroni method. Significance level was set to 0.05. The LRs were applied to all diagnostic co-occurrences identified in step (i) and fitted using Statsmodels in Python 3.6.10^{31,32}.

The temporal order of the diagnostic co-occurrences (e.g., D1 and D2) with statistically significant age difference was determined by the age at diagnoses D1 and D2 that were computed from the LRs. Due to the number of covariates, it would be cumbersome to obtain a predicted age for each subgroup, e.g., primary diagnosis, females, and outpatients for each discharge year. Therefore, the predicted age was calculated using only the coefficients for diagnosis pairs and type of diagnosis, as we observed that the covariate for the diagnosis type generally had the highest impact (smallest P-values) on the age difference (Supplementary figure 1). The predicted age was calculated for D1 and D2 when assigned as primary diagnoses and the diagnosis that was predicted to be assigned at the youngest age was defined as the first diagnosis in the directional diagnosis (equivalent to length two trajectories) pair. In cases where the predicted age of D1 was less than that of D2 the length two trajectory would be D1 → D2. Patients who were assigned diagnoses D1 and D2 were characterized by following the trajectory and the order would be the one determined by the LR.

To determine the directionality of disease trajectories containing three diagnoses, a similar approach to the directional diagnosis pairs was applied to sets of patients, who all were assigned diagnoses D1, D2 and D3. Diagnosis pairs with a significant directionality where diagnosis D2 of one pair was equal to diagnosis D1 of another pair were pieced together into a length three trajectory. The directionality of the disease trajectory was determined by extracting all patients with diagnoses D1, D2 and D3 and calculating the age of the three diagnoses. The age at diagnosis was calculated using the set of the three diagnoses (i.e., D1, D2 and D3) and type of diagnosis when assigned as primary diagnosis. The diagnoses were ordered by estimated age, from youngest to oldest age, e.g., the length three trajectory D1 → D2 → D3. As the directionality was recalculated for the disease trajectories, the directionality within a length two trajectory could change when combined with other diagnoses. In addition, length three trajectories could establish new directional associations, as their assemblage did not require the first and the last diagnoses to be a directional diagnosis pair (corresponding to diagnosis D1 and D3 in the example above). In the final analysis, only

trajectories computed based on sets of more than 50 patients were included; and patients with diagnoses D1 and D2 or D1, D2 and D3 were then said to follow the resulting trajectory.

Using disease trajectories to characterize different IHD populations

To assess if the temporal order of diagnoses was different between patients with different IHD manifestations, the cohort was split into seven groups defined by which IHD codes they were assigned. That is, one group was defined by having only I20, I21, or I25. Another group was defined by having two of the three codes, e.g. I20 and I21. A final group was defined by patients that were assigned I20, I21 and I25. These groups comprised a total of seven distinct index groups. Directional diagnoses pairs were now computed for each of these groups separately, following the same steps as described above (Figure 1).

Results

Cohort characterization and overview of the directional diagnosis pairs

The case population was comprised of a total of 552 216 patients (57.2% males) diagnosed with IHD (ICD-10 codes I20, I21 or I25) in the 1994-2018 period. Mean age at first IHD diagnosis was 65.9 years for males and 70.8 years for females (Table 1). The size of the seven index groups ranged from 65 302 to 117 493 patients. Using the entire set of diagnosis codes assigned to patients in the case population, a total of 16 712 diagnostic co-occurrences (D1, D2) were identified. Among all the diagnostic co-occurrences, there were 1 459 pairs with a statistically significant difference in mean age at diagnosis D1 and D2, respectively. Those directional diagnosis pairs were followed by 546 704 patients (Figure 1).

The directional diagnosis pairs that characterized the temporality of multi-morbidity in IHD were formed by a total of 408 distinct ICD-10 codes and generally, the temporal associations between IHD co-morbidities are highly diverse and dominated by other diseases of the cardiovascular system as well as metabolic diseases (Figure 2A and B). Among the 1 459 directional diagnosis pairs with a diagnosis code for IHD, 210 pairs contained a diagnosis code for either angina pectoris (ICD-10 code: I20), acute myocardial infarction (ICD-10 code: I21) or chronic IHD (ICD-10 code: I25). In 149 of these pairs (71.0%), the codes appeared as D2 consistent with the fact that IHD is a multi-factorial disease with a wide spectrum of etiologies and rarely the first manifestation of multi-morbidity (Table 2).

Directional diagnosis pairs add information about the cohort

As expected, essential hypertension (I10), non-insulin-dependent diabetes (E11), insulin-dependent diabetes (E10), atrial fibrillation (I48), heart failure (I50) and dyslipidemia (E78), were among the co-morbidities with the highest prevalence in the IHD cohort (Table 1). Not surprisingly, these diagnoses were also among the diagnoses that appeared in most distinct directional diagnosis pairs, indicating that they are diagnosed in a wide range of patient populations. Diagnoses that were prevalent in the cohort tended to be chronic conditions or manifestations of chronic disease, e.g., volume depletion (E86) (Table 2).

A quantitative summary of the directional diagnosis pairs revealed additional characteristics regarding IHD co-morbidities that were not captured by the crude co-morbidity counts. For example, insulin-dependent diabetes (E10), obesity (E66), and disorders due to the use of alcohol (F10) were among the most frequently occurring diagnoses in the directional diagnosis pairs, although they were not among the diagnoses that were assigned to most patients in the population. Similarly, although rarely described in the context of IHD, diverticular disease of the intestine (K57) and osteoporosis without pathological fracture (M81) were among the co-morbidities that associated with most diagnoses in a directional manner. Conversely, a condition that is not chronic such as pneumonia (J18) was among the diagnoses assigned to most patients, yet it was not among the most frequently occurring diagnoses in the directional diagnosis pairs (Tables 1 and 2).

Qualitative differences between risk factors, complications and diseases that can be both

Generally, IHD risk factors appeared as D1 in most directional diagnosis pairs, e.g., hypertension (I10) and non-insulin dependent diabetes (E11) whereas conditions that may be related to both the etiology of IHD and represent a complication were equally likely to appear as either D1 or D2, e.g., heart failure (I50). Interestingly, atrial fibrillation (I48) most often appeared as diagnosis D1, indicating that in this population in this context, atrial fibrillation was often established at one of the earliest hospital encounters. However, the estimated age of a diagnosis of atrial fibrillation was not older than that of IHD, e.g. I20 → I48 ($n = 80\,560$, $P < 0.001$). Patients following this directional diagnosis pair were also among the patients that were oldest when diagnosed with angina pectoris (ICD-10: I20). Among the ten most frequent directional diagnosis pairs containing I20, I21 or I25, there were considerable differences in the age distributions for age at IHD diagnosis. For example, the mean age at diagnosis for angina pectoris (I20) in the directional diagnosis pair E78 → I20 ($n = 114\,074$, $P < 0.001$) was 6.6 years below the predicted age at angina pectoris for patients following the trajectory I20 → I48 ($n = 80\,560$, $P < 0.001$) (Table 3).

Interestingly, we observed that the temporal relation between IHD and atrial fibrillation was not consistent across the different IHD subpopulations. For patients with a diagnosis code for acute myocardial infarction and no code for angina pectoris and chronic IHD I48 appeared as D1 in the directional diagnosis pair, I48 → I21 (n = 11 871, P < 0.001). In contrast, I21 → I48 appeared as a directional diagnosis pair when computed for the population who were indexed with diagnosis codes I20, I21 and I25 (n = 26 273, P < 0.001). This is consistent with the dual nature of atrial fibrillation that may be an age phenomenon as well as a disease complication. When the cohort was analyzed in its entirety, the diagnoses I21 and I48 did not comprise a directional diagnosis pair further pointing to the complexity of multi-morbidity in this domain (Table 4).

In contrast to the differing trend between acute myocardial infarction and atrial fibrillation, the age of the diagnoses for heart failure (I50) and acute respiratory failure (J96) was similar in the two index groups where it appeared with a significant age difference between age at diagnosis of heart failure and respiratory failure. Among patients indexed with I20 and I25, estimated age at I50 was 70.5 years and 75.0 years for acute respiratory failure (n = 3 882, p < 0.0001). For patients indexed with I20, I21, and I25 it was 70.0 years and 74.8 years, respectively (n = 5 161, P < 0.001) (Table 4). Taken together, these observations suggest a more indisputable temporal association between I50 and J96, than between I21 and I48 among IHD patients.

Comparison of length two and length three trajectories

Next, the 1 459 directional diagnosis pairs were combined into 4 729 length three trajectories, i.e., disease trajectories comprised of three diagnoses. Selected length two and three trajectories with shared diagnoses were then compared. Generally, the predicted ages for IHD in trajectories containing IHD risk factors, e.g., dyslipidemia (E78) and hypertension (I10) were younger than trajectories containing a diagnosis code for IHD and no risk factors. In contrast, among diseased patients, the predicted age at IHD was older primarily reflecting that older people are more likely to be diseased. However, in trajectories that contained death (Y99) and a code for common IHD risk factors e.g., E78 or I10, age at death was generally young (Figure 3). Moreover, for some diagnoses the predicted age at one diagnosis varied considerably between trajectories. For example, the predicted age at angina pectoris (I20) was below 60.8 years for patients diagnosed with dyslipidemia and angina pectoris (i.e., E78 → I20). In contrast, the predicted age at angina pectoris was 68.0 for patients diagnosed with angina pectoris and heart failure (i.e., I20 → I50). When combined into a length three trajectory, i.e., E78 → I20 → I50 it was primarily the age at diagnosis

of heart failure that changed. The predicted age at diagnosis of heart failure among patients diagnosed with angina was 70.2 whereas it was 68.3 for patients diagnosed with dyslipidemia, angina pectoris and heart failure (Table 3).

Interestingly, in some cases the length three trajectories revealed that the order of the diagnoses was not constant when comparing length two trajectories and length three trajectories, e.g., $D1 \rightarrow D2$ and $D3 \rightarrow D2 \rightarrow D1$, respectively. For example, in the population of patients who had been assigned the diagnosis code for coxarthrosis (M16) and acute myocardial infarction (I21), the predicted age for coxarthrosis was younger than that of acute myocardial infarction (predicted ages 70.9 and 71.4 for M16 and I21, $P < 0.001$). However, for patients who had been assigned the diagnoses code for dyslipidemia (E78), coxarthrosis (M16) and acute myocardial infarction (I21) the order was reversed, i.e., the predicted age of I21 was younger than that of M16 (predicted ages 68.6 and 67.7 for M16 and I21). Again, this indicates the dual nature of coxarthrosis that might be a component of the metabolic syndrome or simply age-related degeneration (Table 3). In addition, the length three trajectories captured temporal trends in the cohort that length two trajectories did not identify. For example, albeit the length three trajectory $I10 \rightarrow I20 \rightarrow I25$ was followed by 105 652 patients, the diagnostic co-occurrence of I10 and I25 was not among the directional diagnosis pairs. The number of patients following the trajectory $I10 \rightarrow I20 \rightarrow I25$ corresponded to 66.1% of the patients following the trajectory $I10 \rightarrow I20$ ($n = 162\,376$, $P < 0.001$). A similar trend was observed when comparing the diagnoses E78 and I48 (no diagnostic co-occurrence) with patients following the trajectory $E78 \rightarrow I20 \rightarrow I48$ ($n = 32\,248$), corresponding to 28.3% of patients who followed the trajectory $E78 \rightarrow I20$ ($n = 114\,074$) (Table 3).

Discussion

We have presented a strategy for analyzing the temporal order of IHD co-morbidities based on trends in nation-wide registry data of more than 500 000 IHD patients observed over a period of 24 years. By first establishing directional diagnosis pairs from diagnostic co-occurrences and then piecing together disease trajectories, we present a data-driven characterization of multi-morbidity based on nationwide health registry data. The directional diagnosis pairs captured temporal associations related to multi-morbidity that are usually omitted in a purely hypothesis-driven model. For example, the disease trajectory program identified osteoporosis as one of the co-morbidities that appeared in most directional diagnosis pairs. Similarly, there were cases where atrial fibrillation was diagnosed before IHD as well as after, consistent with the fact that it can represent an age phenomenon as well as a disease complication. Finally, the disease trajectories served as a tool to

identify cases where coxarthrosis was more likely to be a component of metabolic syndrome as opposed to an age-related degeneration in a single organ system (Table 2).

The study has several strengths and limitations. Generally, the disease trajectory approach offers a novel strategy to identify temporal trends in the complex multi-morbidity landscape of IHD. We argue that this strategy can complement traditional studies, where multi-morbidity is assessed in a binary fashion, depending on their presence or absence¹¹. An inherent limitation with NPR is that disease history of the individual patient is not complete, meaning that all data is conditioned on the fact that the patient went to the hospital. Similarly, there will of course be cases where the true age at first diagnosis was earlier than 1994 and hence will not be captured in the analysis. We assume that for patients with many contacts before 1994 this will apply to most diagnoses that are then likely to be registered at the same contact in the observation period. For patients with only few contacts before the start of the study that are close in time to 1994 this will only have limited impact on the results. Further, due to differences in year of birth for study participants combined with the broad inclusion criteria, differences in disease directionality may be confounded by factors not related to etiological differences. Ultimately, future studies will also include data from the Danish ICD-8 period, i.e., before 1994. In contrast to previous versions of the disease trajectory algorithm, we present a strategy where these confounders are adjusted for. In its current form the method can only define a direction in a predefined population in the sense that the direction is determined using the entire distribution for the population and not for the individual patient. Further studies are needed to determine the actual order of diagnoses in the individual patient and thereby disentangle the true mechanism in cases where one condition may both appear as a risk factor and a complication.

In sum, we believe that the potential to conduct large-scale studies in nationwide registry data goes far beyond the more restrictive, classical usage. However, in its current state, the Danish disease trajectories are influenced by the inherent limitations within NPR and other health registries rooted in the universal healthcare in other Nordic regions, such as medical surveillance bias. So, additional studies that incorporate other data types are needed to identify the disease trajectories that reflect differences in disease progression patterns attributable to etiological difference. We believe that the value of studying nationwide health registry data comprehensively outweighs the limitations and calls for future collaborations between basic and physician scientists.

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Tables

Table 1: Case population demographics and the 15 co-morbidities assigned to most patients

	Number of patients	Mean age at IHD (SD)	Number of patients dead at end of study		Mean number of directional diagnosis pairs
Total	552 216	68.5 (13.6)	309 353	56.0%	25.5
Males	315 628	65.9 (13.8)	170 964	54.2%	24.9
Females	236 588	70.8 (14.0)	138 389	58.5%	26.2
Index groups					
I20	117 493	63.0	38 923	33.1%	15.8
I21	65 302	73.9	51 598	79.0%	79.0
I25	105 924	75.1	78 991	74.6%	74.6
I20, I21	14 346	69.7	9 667	67.4%	67.4
I20, I25	96 133	66.5	46 068	47.9%	47.9
I21, I25	66 293	69.1	36 648	55.3%	55.3
I20, I21, I25	86 725	65.0	47 458	54.7%	54.7
Co-morbidities (ICD-10 code)					
Hypertension (I10)	251 039	67.7 (12.8)	118 814	47.1%	36.4
Heart failure (I50)	167 004	72.3 (12.0)	126 528	74.9%	39.5
Dyslipidemia (E78)	155 054	63.4 (11.5)	54 836	35.4%	35.6
Atrial fibrillation (I48)	147 222	72.6 (11.5)	100 324	67.4%	39.1
Pneumonia (J18)	141 405	72.0 (12.3)	106 599	74.4%	41.2
Senile cataract (H25)	125 838	74.0 (11.7)	75 528	59.6%	39.4
Non-insulin-dependent diabetes (E11)	101 658	67.2 (12.3)	59 958	58.6%	45.3
Other hearing loss (H91)	100 901	74.6 (11.7)	64 726	63.5%	35.2
COPD (J44)	94 788	70.2 (11.0)	68 000	70.9%	42.6
Cystitis (N30)	79 628	73.4 (11.8)	56 203	73.4%	45.5
Dorsalgia (M54)	64 968	63.8 (14.1)	25 895	39.0%	39.1
Stroke (I64)	61 671	73.3 (11.8)	47 887	77.0%	42.4
Anemia (D64)	61 247	73.3 (11.8)	46 811	77.6%	50.8
Other disorders of the urinary system (N39)	59 255	71.9 (12.4)	37 633	63.5%	49.4
Atherosclerosis (I70)	58 965	70.5 (11.3)	45 135	76.5%	48.2

Table 2: Diagnoses that appear in at least 25 directional diagnosis pairs (D1 → D2)

ICD-10	Description	Number of trajectories per diagnosis			Number of distinct patients per trajectory with diagnosis		
		Total	D1	D2	Total	D1	D2
I10	Hypertension	121	114	7	249 649	249 465	54 968
I25	Chronic ischemic heart disease	96	87	9	353 322	352 979	51 051
E11	Non-insulin-dependent diabetes	86	85	1	101 321	101 308	2 525
I20	Angina pectoris	73	41	32	309 547	285 000	276 615
I48	Atrial fibrillation	51	42	9	145 190	138 136	96 937
E10	Insulin-dependent diabetes	50	49	1	43 216	43 129	34 639
I50	Heart failure	48	21	27	167 079	148 460	158 490
E78	Dyslipidemia	45	39	6	154 621	154 524	27 434
I21	Acute myocardial infarction	44	12	32	230 853	184 560	198 225
M62	Other disorders of muscle	41	41	0	38 545	38 545	0
E66	Obesity	40	40	0	44 196	44 196	0
H25	Senile cataract	39	13	26	124 817	103 373	117 926
E86	Volume depletion	37	1	36	58 420	47 418	56 735
K57	Diverticular disease of intestine	32	3	29	38 545	25 995	46 086
M81	Osteoporosis without pathological fracture	29	7	22	37 628	28 579	34 909
D64	Other anemias	27	1	26	61 041	46 547	60 171
F10	Mental and behavioral disorders due to use of alcohol	27	27	0	28 545	28 545	0
J44	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	27	24	3	89 647	88 385	16 020
J96	Respiratory failure, not elsewhere classified	27	1	26	40 802	32 128	40 425
I46	Cardiac arrest	26	0	26	20 145	0	20 145
N92	Excessive, frequent, and irregular menstruation	25	24	1	14 512	14 512	36 162

Table 3: Summary of selected disease trajectories

Length two trajectories								
ICD-10 D1	ICD-10 D2		Age, D1	Age, D2	Adj. P	Counts	RR, D1, D2	
I10	H54		67.3	67.4	< 0.001	2 926	1.89	
E78	I20		60.8	62.9	< 0.001	76 334	4.36	
I20	I50		68.0	71.4	< 0.001	84 955	1.94	
I20	I48		68.2	69.9	< 0.001	80 560	1.34	
M16	I21		70.9	71.4	< 0.001	17 316	2.61	
I10	Y99		73.3	79.6	0	119 140	-	
N97	I10		34.3	41.9	< 0.001	516	3.02	
Length three trajectories								
ICD-10 D1	ICD-10, D2	ICD-10, D3	Age, D1	Age, D2	Age, D3	Counts	RR, D1, D2	RR, D2, D3
E78	I20	I50	63.7	63.9	68.3	32 309	4.36	1.94
E78	I20	I48	65.1	65.4	68.3	30 248	4.36	1.34
E78	I21	M16	65.1	65.4	68.3	30 248	4.36	2.61
I10	I20	I25	62.6	64.6	64.7	105 652	1.93	4.28
E78	I20	I48	65.1	65.4	68.3	30 248	4.36	1.34

Table 4: Summary of selected disease trajectories for different index populations

Index codes	Counts Total	ICD-10 D1	ICD-10, D2	Age, D1	Age, D2	Adj. P	Counts Trajectory	RR, D1, D2
I21	65 302	I48	I21	73.3	76.2	< 0.001	11 871	1.09
I20, I21, I25	66 293	I21	I48	69.4	71.2	< 0.001	26 273	1.09
I20, I25	110 479	I50	J96	70.5	75.0	< 0.001	3 882	1.68
I20, I21, I25	66 293	I50	J96	70.0	74.8	< 0.001	5 161	1.68

Figure captions

Figure 1: Study flowchart. Preprocessing of registry data to construct disease trajectories by identification of directional disease pairs. Grey: Identification. Blue: Screening. Green: Inclusion and outcome. NPR: The Danish National Patient History. IHD: Ischemic heart disease. ICD-10: International Statistical Classification of Disease and Health Related Problems 10th Revision.

Figure 2: Graphical summary of directional diagnosis pairs. Chord diagrams displaying the directional relations for selected directional diagnosis pairs. ICD-10 codes that comprise directional pairs are marked in the periphery and ribbons indicate a directional diagnosis pair. (A) All directional diagnosis pairs containing an ICD-10 code for IHD and one of the 35 ICD-10 codes that were assigned to most patients. (B) All directional diagnosis pairs that did not contain an ICD-10 code for IHD and followed by more than 20 000 patients. Width of ribbon corresponds to the number of patients that follow a directional diagnosis pair. Number of patients in A: 463 689. Number of directional diagnosis pairs in A: 35. Number of patients in B: 356 162. Number of directional diagnosis pairs in B: 64. Number of distinct patients in A and B: 331 469. Only directional diagnoses pairs without Y99 (death) and more than three months between estimated age at D1 and D2 are depicted. Color key according to ICD-10 chapter. IHD: Ischemic heart disease. ICD-10: International Statistical Classification of Disease and Health Related Problems 10th Revision.

Figure 3: Overview of selected length two and three trajectories ordered by age at diagnoses. A: Scatter plot illustrating the mean age at diagnoses D1 and D2 for the 25 directional diagnosis pairs that most patients followed arranged by mean age at D1 (decreasing going down). Each horizontal line segment corresponds to a directional diagnosis pair. B: Scatter plot illustrating the mean age at diagnoses D1, D2, and D3 for the 25 length three trajectories followed by most patients with D1 between 65 and 70 years. X-axis: Age in years (continuous). Y-axis: Length two (A) or three (B) trajectories. ICD-10: International Statistical Classification of Disease and Health Related Problems 10th Revision. Color key according to ICD-10 chapter.

Supplementary figure 1: Distribution of P-values for covariates in the linear regressions.

Trends in the P-value for the covariates that were to select diagnosis pair (i.e., diagnostic co-occurrence) and diagnosis type (i.e., primary, or non-primary code) as the covariates that were used in the regressions that estimated age at diagnoses.

Figure 1

Figure 2

A

B

International Statistical Classification of Disease and Health Related Problems 10th Revision chapter I through XIV

- I Certain infectious and parasitic diseases
- II Neoplasms
- III Diseases of the blood and blood-forming organs and certain disorders involving the immune mechanism
- IV Endocrine, nutritional and metabolic diseases
- V Mental and behavioural disorders
- VI Diseases of the nervous system
- VII Diseases of the eye and adnexa
- VIII Diseases of the ear and mastoid process
- IX Diseases of the circulatory system
- X Diseases of the respiratory system
- XI Diseases of the digestive system
- XII Diseases of the skin and subcutaneous tissue
- XIII Diseases of the musculoskeletal system and connective tissue
- XIV Diseases of the genitourinary system

Supplementary figure 1

8 | Risk stratification of 72,249 patients with ischemic heart disease: a retrospective study linking prior multimorbidity, biochemical data, and genetics

Risk stratification of 72,249 patients with ischemic heart disease: a retrospective study linking prior multi-morbidity, biochemical data, and genetics

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Key points

Question: How can data on prior multi-morbidities be used for risk stratification and subgrouping of patients with ischemic heart disease (IHD)?

Findings: Unsupervised clustering identified IHD patient subgroups defined by the entire multi-morbidity spectrum could be stratified according to different risks of secondary ischemic events and death from non-IHD causes. Subgrouping was supported biologically by biochemical and genetic data.

Meaning: Unsupervised clustering discriminated between patients at high- and low risk of secondary ischemic events paving the way for differentiated management of patients with IHD, i.e., development of precision medicine in this domain.

Abstract

Importance: The clinical use in risk stratification of prior multi-morbidity data spanning decades; and biochemical data and genetics needs to be realized.

Objective: Explore how unsupervised clustering of multi-morbidity from electronic health records (EHRs) can be used to risk stratify patients with ischemic heart disease (IHD).

Design: Retrospective study that used data from the Danish National Patient Registry, EHRs from Eastern Denmark and genetic data from Copenhagen Hospital Biobank. Unsupervised clustering for identification of IHD subgroups based on multi-morbidities in male and female patients was performed separately. Cox-proportional hazard models were used to compute hazard ratios (HRs) for primary and secondary outcomes in subgroups. For a subset of patients, subgroups were characterized by available biochemical data and polygenic scores (PGS) for 10 different traits associated with IHD. Discrimination by cluster-based risk stratification was tested against the Charlson and Elixhauser co-morbidity indices (CMIs) and evaluated using the C-index.

Setting: A population-based study using nation-wide healthcare data. Multi-morbidity was assessed using spectrum-wide ICD-10 codes assigned prior to IHD.

Participants: Patients diagnosed with IHD in the years 2004-2016.

Exposures: None.

Main Outcomes: Primary outcome was a composite outcome comprised of acute myocardial infarction, unstable angina pectoris, revascularization (not related to initial IHD diagnosis) and death caused by IHD. Secondary outcome was any death not caused by IHD.

Results: In a cohort of 72,249 patients, we identified 31 male and 25 female subgroups. In total, 11 clusters had $HR > 1$ for the primary outcome only, and two clusters in each sex had $HR > 1$ for both the primary and secondary outcome. We also identified two subgroups that had $HR < 1$ for the primary outcome. Differences in biochemical data largely reproduced the subgrouping. The PGS for total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, diabetes, atrial fibrillation had significant effect sizes in at least one subgroup. Cluster C-indices were generally higher for female than for male clusters and comparable to CMI C-indices.

Conclusions and Relevance: Unsupervised clustering can be used to discriminate between high- and low-risk subgroups based on prior multi-morbidities that are consistent with well-known phenotypes. Subgroup-specific biochemical and PGS characteristics were identified. Overall, the discrimination obtained by the clusters was comparable to CMIs. For patients who were not at increased risk it was better.

Introduction

Worldwide, ischemic heart disease (IHD) affects more than 125 million people. Over the last decades, there has been a decline in mortality rates^{1,2}. Yet, IHD patients remain at high risk of complications and have an age-adjusted mortality that is two to six times higher than in people without IHD³. Nearly 85% of IHD patients are multi-morbid making it a complex phenotype, with disease courses that vary between patients and between sexes⁴⁻⁶. Further, multi-morbidity is a crucial component for reliable outcome prediction, including susceptibility to disease progression^{4,7,8}. It is currently being assessed using only few diagnoses and consequently often disregard the true complexity⁹. As biomedical research is being transformed by an exponential growth in patient profiling data and analytical capabilities, conditions to conduct studies that address the complexity of multi-morbidity are now conceivable^{8,10}. Advanced analysis of routinely obtained biochemical data is expected to supplement data on multi-morbidities^{10,11}.

Polygenic scores (PGS) are becoming a means of patient-profiling although the true potential is still to be confirmed¹². To date PGS are not incorporated in clinical care systematically and more studies using genetic data that model the risk of secondary ischemic events among IHD patients are needed¹³⁻¹⁷. This includes explorative studies that test how data from nation-wide health registries, EHRs (i.e. routinely collected data that capture most aspects of health care) and genotypes can be combined¹⁸⁻²⁰. Aggregated and possibly weaker phenome-wide information that appear stronger in more homogenous subgroups may increase the statistical power of future trials^{21,22}. In turn, this may refine risk stratification of IHD patients, allowing differentiation of treatment between patients¹⁰.

Here, we present a study of 72,249 IHD patients demonstrating how unsupervised clustering based on multi-morbidities can discriminate between patients at high- and low-risk of secondary ischemic events and death of non-IHD causes (i.e., high- and low-risk patients). Among low-risk patients, the performance of our model is better than that of other existing co-morbidity indices. By integrating biochemical and genetic data, we assessed if the unsupervised clustering correlate with biology. In sum, the study presents a strategy for defining and using multi-morbidity, that advances precision medicine to practice.

Methods

Data sources and study population

Data from the Danish National Patient Registry (NPR) and the Danish Registry for Causes of Death were linked to data from the Copenhagen Hospital Biobank Cardiovascular Disease Cohort (CHB-CVDC) and an EHR database, that covers the two Danish health care regions in Eastern Denmark (~2.9 million inhabitants)^{23–26}. Linkage of different health care data sources was obtained via the patient citizen number²⁷. We identified all patients in NPR who were assigned an ICD-10 code for IHD and had been subjected to coronary arteriography (CAG) or coronary computed tomography angiography (CCTA) and had been admitted to a hospital in Eastern Denmark in the years 2004–2016 (eTable 1 in the Supplement)^{28,29}. To qualify that the CAG/CCTA findings supported the IHD diagnosis, patients were only included if the CAG/CCTA was performed during a contact where patients were assigned an ICD-10 code for IHD. We set the earliest CAG/CCTA fulfilling this criterium as the index date and excluded patients with an index date before year 2004 or after 2016 (Figure 1).

Outcomes

Primary outcome was secondary ischemic events, and secondary outcome was death from other causes than IHD. The former was defined as a composite of hospitalization for myocardial infarction or unstable angina pectoris (i.e., hospitalization with myocardial infarction or unstable angina pectoris as the primary diagnosis), revascularization not related to the first IHD diagnosis and any death where IHD was listed as the primary or secondary cause. Eligible codes for inclusion and primary outcome and specific cutoffs are available in eTable 1 and eFigure 1 in the Supplement.

Data preprocessing and application of the Markov cluster algorithm

Male and female patients were clustered separately based on assigned ICD-10 codes prior to or at index using the Markov cluster (MCL) algorithm³⁰. For each subset (male and female), patient specific vectors representing the ICD-10 codes were used as input by the MCL algorithm to create a patient similarity network with patients as vertices and the cosine similarity between the embedded disease history vectors as edges³⁰. After initial testing of the algorithm, we selected six inflation parameters (i.e., granularity levels 1 through 6) for further exploration. Clusters would generally decrease in size at increasing granularity. Three patients did not cluster and were excluded from the

remaining analysis. A detailed description of the MCL algorithm application is available in eMethods. Clusters were labelled independently at different granularity levels (decreasing cluster size at increasing granularity) with an M (male clusters), or F (female clusters) followed by a numeral determined by cluster size. Numerical prefixes indicate the granularity level; 1.M01/1.F01 being the two largest clusters at the lowest level of granularity, while clusters 6.M01/6.F01 would be smaller than clusters 1.M01/1.F01.

Preprocessing of biochemical and genetic data

Clusters were characterized by biochemical and genetic data based on the subset of patients where these data were available (biochemical data: n=20,788 for males; n=12,343 for females; genetic data n=12,271 for males; n=5,920 for females). A panel of 25 different lab parameters was included in the analyses. Only tests taken up to 90 days before index or at the day of index were included. Included lab tests were plasma levels of potassium, sodium, hemoglobin, estimated glomerular filtration (eGFR), creatinine, carbamide, glucose, troponin (I/T), HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, total cholesterol, leukocytes, C-reactive protein, lymphocytes, monocytes, neutrophils, basofilocytes, platelets, INR, alanine transaminase, albumin, alkaline phosphatase, bilirubin, and triglyceride. For every cluster, a score was computed based on the number of patients with a lab test below, within or above reference value, indicated by -1, 0 and 1, respectively. The score was defined as the mean of the summarized values per cluster (eMethods in the Supplement).

Autosomal genotype data were obtained by identifying included patients who were also among the study participants in CHB-CVDC²³. PGS for six disease traits (immune-mediated inflammatory diseases, chronic kidney disease, stroke, atrial fibrillation, coronary artery disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus) and four biochemical traits (total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, and triglycerides) from seven GWAS meta-analyses were calculated³¹⁻³⁷. Traits were selected based on availability in CHB-CVDC. The PGS for coronary artery disease was denoted chronic IHD, corresponding to I25 (ICD-10 code), that defines the PGS (eMethods in the Supplement).

Statistical analyses of clusters identified by the MCL algorithm

To investigate the association between patient cluster membership and the competing risks of secondary ischemic events (primary outcome) and death from non-IHD causes (secondary outcome), we used Cox proportional-hazards models (Cox models). Patients were followed from

index until occurrence of the primary outcome, secondary outcome, or end of follow-up (year 2018), which ever came first. To age-adjust the models, analyses were performed using restricted cubic spline with three knots for age at index. Follow-up time was truncated to a maximum of five years. For each cluster hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were estimated for both sexes separately by comparing HRs for the members of the cluster with the HRs of non-members (eTable 5 in the Supplement). P-values were adjusted using the Bonferroni method assuming number of tests was equal to the number of clusters at the granularity level at which HRs were computed³⁸. Significance level was set to 0.05. In assessment of cluster robustness, we used the term diverging risk to denote the phenomenon where HRs for the primary outcome were not constant across granularity levels. For example, if cluster 1.M01 did not associate with HR for the primary outcome, but cluster 1.M06 did, then this would be an example of diverging risk.

Discrimination of the cluster-based risk stratification was compared to that of the Charlson and Elixhauser indices (CMIs), by first computing the two scores for all patients. Next, the cohort was randomly split into a training (75% of patients) and a test set and Cox models were fitted on the training set using age at index, one of the CMIs or cluster membership as covariates. The overall concordance (C-index) of the four Cox models were estimated by application of the fitted models to the test set. Similarly, C-indices were computed for all clusters separately to assess if they varied between subgroups.

For all clusters, ratios between observed and expected term (referring to ICD-10 codes representations, described in the section Data preprocessing and implementation of the MCL algorithm) frequencies were calculated and expressed as ratios between observed and expected frequencies (O/E-ratios)³⁹ (O/E-ratios for all terms in all clusters are available in the Supplement). Term frequencies in the entire male and female population were used to compute expected term frequencies. O/E-ratios > 2 were defined as enrichment and O/E-ratios > 10 as extreme enrichment (eFigure 4 in the Supplement).

Hierarchical clustering was applied to estimate the cluster similarity with respect to the biochemical tests using the Euclidean distance. For each trait (mentioned above), Wilcoxon rank sum tests were used to compare the PGS for a specific cluster to a combined PGS calculated across all other clusters. Resulting P-values were adjusted for multiple testing by the Bonferroni procedure

assuming 31 and 25 tests for males and females, respectively. Statistically significant results were reported by means of the effect direction, where a positive effect for a cluster indicated a higher PGS burden compared to all other clusters (i.e. “+” and “-“). The pipeline was written in R 3.6.2 and Python and integrated using snakemake^{40,41}. Further details are available in eMethods in the Supplement.

Authority approvals

This work was approved by National Committee on Health Research Ethics [project ID 60833] and the Danish Patient Safety Authority [project number 3-3031-1731/1]. CHB use was approved by the Danish Data Protection Agency [file number 2007-580015; institutional file number RH2007-30-4129/I-suite 00678] and National Committee on Health Research Ethics [approval number 1708829]. Study design, method and results were reported according to the STROBE statement⁴².

Code availability

The code used in this study to generate the results is available upon reasonable request to the authors.

Results

Unsupervised clustering to identify distinct patient subgroups

A total of 72,249 patients (63.1% males) were included. During follow-up, the primary outcome occurred in 11,476 patients, 6,177 died from other causes than IHD and 54,596 were censored (Table 1). Using the entire set of ICD-10 codes assigned prior to or at index as input for the MCL algorithm smaller clusters, as expected, segregated from larger clusters at increasing granularity. Across the six different granularity levels, the number of male clusters ranged from 24 to 35 and from 16 to 31 for females (Figure 2). To assess the physiological relevance of the subgrouping captured by the MCL algorithm, we used cluster-membership as a covariate in Cox models (eTable 5 in the Supplement). Results from the Cox model showed that the algorithm stratified the patients according to risk of the primary and secondary outcome. For both sexes, there were clusters with increased risk of the primary and secondary outcome, i.e., clusters 4.M02, 4.M20, 4.F02 and 4.F16 as well as clusters with significantly reduced risks, e.g., cluster 4.M01 and 4.F01 (Figure 3).

Cluster robustness assessment using the Cox model

The Cox models also served as an indicator for cluster robustness. For males, there was one cluster that segregated into two clusters with diverging risks of the primary outcome. Across all granularity levels two clusters segregated from cluster 1.M04 (Figure 2). HR for the primary outcome in cluster 1.M04 was 1.06 (95% CI: 0.97 to 1.17, adj. P: 0.18). At the fourth granularity level, the cluster originating from 1.M04 (no significant HR) segregated into clusters 4.M05 and 4.M25. In these clusters HRs for risk of the primary outcome were 0.99 (95% CI: 0.97 to 1.17, adj. P: 0.18) and 1.38 (95% CI: 1.15;1.65, adj. P: 0.03), respectively. For the remaining male clusters, the level of granularity did not affect HR for the primary outcome. Among female clusters, there was also a case where one cluster segregated into clusters with diverging risk of the primary outcome. Across all granularity levels, five smaller clusters branched off from cluster 1.F01 (Figure 2). By comparing the results of the Cox models at granularity level one and level four, we observed that HR for the primary outcome in cluster 1.F01 was 0.86 (95% CI: 0.78 to 0.95, adj. P: 0.075) whereas it was 0.74 (95% CI: 0.66 to 0.84, adj. P: <0.001) in cluster 4.F01. For the primary outcome, C-indexes of the clusters were comparable to that of the CMI with C-indexes in range 0.55 to 0.57 for males and 0.59 to 0.61 for females (eTable 6 in the Supplement).

Biochemical and genetic data add information to the patient subgroups

To investigate if the multi-morbidity patterns captured by the MCL algorithm correlated with the pathogenesis or biology, clusters at granularity level four were characterized with respect to the available biochemical and genetic data. Hierarchical clustering was applied to 25 biochemical test parameters to investigate biochemical similarities for different groups of clusters. For males, clusters 4.M02 and 4.M20 grouped together based on their biochemical data. This biochemical group was characterized by negative scores for hemoglobin and eGFR. For LDL and total cholesterol, the scores were positive, yet closer to 0 than that of the other clusters. For females, the two main biochemical groups had nearly the same number of clusters. One group was characterized by higher scores for troponin, CRP, neutrophils and eGFR. This agreed with the fact that all clusters with increased risk of the secondary outcome were in this biochemical group, e.g., clusters 4.F02, 4.F06, 4.F10, 4.F11, 4.F.12, 4.F16 and 4.F19 (eFigure 6 in the Supplement and Figure 3).

PGS for 10 different traits were also compared between clusters using Wilcoxon rank sum tests (eTable 4 in the Supplement). At granularity level four, the PGS distribution for eight of the 10 traits was significantly different in at least one cluster compared to the distributions of the other clusters. There were nine (out of 35) male clusters and six (out of 31) female clusters with significant PGS distribution for at least one trait (eTable 7 in the Supplement). In both sexes, the PGS for diabetes was increased in one of the high-risk clusters, i.e., cluster 4.M02 (HR: 1.51, 95% CI: 1.40 to 1.62, adj. P: <0.001) and in cluster 4.F02 (HR: 1.73, 95% CI: 1.57 to 1.91, adj. P: <0.001). Moreover, there were positive effect sizes for the PGS for atrial fibrillation in clusters with increased risk of the secondary outcome, e.g., 4.M04 (HR: 1.51, 95% CI: 1.35 to 1.70, adj. P: <0.001) and 4.F11 (HR: 1.42, 95% CI: 1.19 to 1.62, adj. P: <0.001). The risk of the primary outcome was reduced in cluster 4.M01 (HR: 0.74, 95% CI: 0.66 to 0.84, adj. P: $1.6e^{-4}$) where the PGS effect sizes were positive for LDL and total cholesterol and negative for chronic IHD (Table 2).

Phenotypes in subgroups with altered risk of the primary or secondary outcome

To investigate associations to phenotypes across subgroups, we next performed an enrichment analysis of selected clusters at granularity level four. Enrichment was quantified in the form of O/E-ratios. Cluster 4.M25 (HR, primary outcome: 1.38, 95% CI: 1.15;1.65, adj. P: 0.03), that was identified in assessment of cluster robustness (Figure 2), was extremely enriched for ICD-10 codes describing conditions in the musculoskeletal system (e.g., O/E-ratio for the ICD-10 code M62.6, muscle strain: 26.4). The cluster was also enriched for pericarditis (I30.1). In contrast to cluster 4.M25, cluster 4.M01 had reduced risk of the primary outcome (HR: 0.93, 95% CI: 0.87 to 0.99, adj. P: 0.027). In both clusters, patients were relatively young (Table 2).

Similarly, severe clusters were analyzed for phenotypic enrichment (eTable 6 in the Supplement). In both sexes, high-risk clusters where the PGS for diabetes was significant were extremely enriched (i.e., O/E-ratio > 10) for ICD-10 codes describing diabetes (i.e., 4.M02 and 4.F02). Moreover, diabetic retinopathy (H36.0) was among the ICD-codes with the largest O/E-ratio and reached 74.8 and 95.0 in 4.M02 and 4.F02, respectively (Table 2). In clusters enriched for diabetes, HRs for the primary outcome were 1.51 for males and 1.73 for females, respectively (4.M02 95% CI: 1.40 to 1.62, adj. P<0.001; 4.F02 95% CI: 1.57 to 1.91, adj. P: <0.001). In both sexes, abnormal glucose levels were frequent in the clusters enriched for diabetes (eFigure 6 in the Supplement).

Finally, the MCL algorithm also identified clusters where the secondary outcome was increased, while risks of the primary outcome were not significant. These included 4.M04, 4.M06, 4.M07, 4.M08, 4.M10, 4.M13, 4.M29, 4.F06, 4.F11, 4.F12 and 4.F21 (Figures 2 and 3); encompassing distinct clusters characterized by cancer (e.g. C44.3/C50.9), disorders due to the use of alcohol (e.g. F10.2), atrial fibrillation/heart failure (e.g. I48.9/I50.9) and chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPD) (e.g. J44.9) (Table 2). In both sexes, the PGS for atrial fibrillation was significant in clusters enriched for atrial fibrillation/heart failure (4.M04 and 4.F11) (Table 2). In these clusters, C-indices for the CMI were higher than the cluster C-indices. However, in some clusters without significantly altered risk for the primary or secondary outcome, a cluster-based risk stratification performed better than CMIs, e.g., 0.76, 0.73 and 0.72 for the secondary outcome for cluster 4.M14 (eTable 6 in the Supplement).

Discussion

The complexity and scale of multi-morbidity calls for development of risk stratification methods that acknowledge patient heterogeneity⁹. By application of the MCL algorithm to spectrum-wide multi-morbidities from 72,249 IHD patients, we identified patient subgroups at different risk of secondary ischemic events as well as death from non-IHD causes. For clusters at increased risk of secondary ischemic events, HRs ranged from 0.73 to 1.65 for males and 0.64 to 1.76 for females (Table 2). The study demonstrated that the MCL algorithm captured biologically relevant patterns within the ICD-10 terminology, which had support in biochemical and genetic data.

The fact that only modest effects on HRs were observed when changing the inflation parameter suggests overall cluster stability (Figure 2). Importantly, discrimination of survival models fitted using clusters as co-variables was comparable the CMIs. In some subgroups a cluster-based estimation even outperformed CMIs (eTable 6 in the Supplement). In our analyses only one cluster (4.M01) at decreased risk of secondary ischemic events, associated with PGS distributions in comparison to that of the other clusters (Table 2). This adds to the growing body of literature regarding sex-specific manifestations of IHD⁵. In comparison to other clustering strategies, our model succeeded in including rarer phenotypes by application of a flexible algorithm that only depends on a limited set of a priori assumptions regarding explanatory variables^{6,43}. Explicitly, we applied a data-driven strategy that discriminated between phenotypes that are at risk of both secondary ischemic events and death from non-IHD causes. For example, in both sexes, clusters

enriched for atrial fibrillation only associated with increased risk of death from non-IHD causes and correlated with the PGS for atrial fibrillation. The observation is consistent with a previous finding that anti-coagulative therapy should not be intensified in patients with atrial fibrillation and a recent percutaneous coronary intervention⁷. In addition we show that the association between IHD subgroups and PGS allows for adding genetics and possibly thereby enhancing the clinical utility of genetic data^{14,15}.

The study has several strengths, but also limitations. By performing an enrichment analysis based on past multi-morbidities and support it with biochemical and genetic data, we showcase how integration of complementary datatypes may lead to a more robust analysis. The study confirmed prior findings, while it potentially also leads to new discoveries. By studying patients aligned temporally according to IHD onset and their past spectrum-wide multi-morbidities, our work underscores the complexity of multi-morbidity in a model that in principle can be applied to any disease of interest. The complementary analysis of biochemical data and genetics provide evidence that this is indeed feasible.

As our modelling strategy allows for analysis of cluster granularity (as a function of the inflation parameter), the complexity of multi-morbidity is an integral part of the model. Evidently, this is also a limitation. However, we argue that the framework adds value as this limitation is not unique to our model and often pre-fixed^{6,19}. Yet, multi-morbidity is often studied binarily where neither the severity nor the order with which they were diagnosed is taken into account⁹. We assert that models allowing for such complexity will increase the likelihood of identifying relevant, yet weaker phenotypic and genetic information in subgroups. Information that potentially has the capacity to account for differences in disease risk and burden that are currently unknown. Further, the model requires data that are available in most health-care systems (i.e., ICD-10 codes). For successful translation of our findings into actionable risk stratification principles of value in clinical decisions making, further studies that apply the method at the $N = 1$ level are needed.

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Tables

Table 1: Cohort demographics, outcomes, and most prevalent non-IHD ICD-10 codes.

Cohort demographics		Total	Males	Females	P-value ¹
Number of patients (%)		72,249	45,576 (63.1)	26,673 (36.1)	
Mean age at index (SD)		63.9 (11.9)	62.9 (11.6)	65.6 (12.1)	< 0.001
Outcomes, number of cases		Total	Males	Females	P-value ²
Secondary ischemic events (%)		11,476 (15.9)	7,891 (17.3)	3,585 (13.4)	< 0.001
■ Myocardial infarction		4,522	2,851	1,671	
■ Revascularization		4,910	3,660	1,250	
■ Death caused by IHD		1,943	1,379	664	
Death from non-IHD causes (%)		6,177 (8.5)	3,902 (8.6)	2,275 (8.5)	
Censored (%)		54,596 (75.6)	33,783 (74.1)	20,813 (78.0)	
Outcomes, time to event		Mean time to event in years (SD)			P-value ¹
		Count	Males	Females	
Secondary ischemic events		2.25 (1.91)	2.27 (1.92)	2.21 (1.89)	0.82
■ Myocardial infarction		1.65 (1.41)	1.63 (1.42)	1.67 (1.40)	0.31
■ Revascularization		1.48 (1.34)	1.49 (1.36)	1.45 (1.31)	0.33
■ Death caused by IHD		1.14 (1.46)	1.18 (1.47)	1.05 (1.44)	0.060
Death from non-IHD causes		3.36 (1.80)	3.34 (1.81)	3.39 (1.80)	0.19
Censored		4.27 (1.13)	4.25 (1.15)	4.30 (1.11)	0.002
Total		3.72 (1.65)	3.67 (1.67)	3.81 (1.60)	< 0.001
ICD-10	Description	Males	Females	Total	
I10	Primary (essential) hypertension	14,519	10,316	24,835	
E78.0	Hypercholesterolemia	7,843	4,939	12,782	
E11.9	Type 2 diabetes mellitus: Without complications	4,895	2,667	7,562	
I48.9	Atrial fibrillation and atrial flutter, unspecified	4,509	2,567	7,076	
I50.9	Heart failure, unspecified	4,061	2,101	6,162	
R07.9	Chest pain	3,450	2,423	5,873	
H25.9	Senile cataract, unspecified	2,795	2,969	5,764	
J18.9	Pneumonia, unspecified	3,329	2,265	5,504	
E78.5	Hyperlipidaemia, unspecified	3,306	1,696	5,002	
J44.9	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, unspecified	2,452	2,174	4,626	

¹ Students T-test, two-sided

² χ^2 -test testing distribution of outcomes among males vs. females. Italics not included.

Table 2: Demographics of selected clusters. List of ICD-10 code descriptions in eTable 8.

ID	Mean age at index		HR, <u>primary outcome</u> (95% CI)	Adj. P-value	Main enrichment		Significant PGS. Trait (effect) ⁵
	Years (SD)	P-value ⁴			ICD-10	O/E-ratio	
4.M01	58.5 (10.8)	< 0.001	0.93 (0.87 to 0.99)	0.030	I21.3	2.46	TC (+) I25 (-) LDL (+)
4.M02	62.4 (10.8)	0.20	1.51 (1.40 to 1.62)	< 0.001	E10.9	28.8	E11 (+)
					E11.9	11,7	
					H36.0	74.8	
4.M19	67.1 (10.4)	< 0.001	1.28 (1.11 to 1.48)	0.04	I69.4	33.7	None
4.M20	67.6 (9.3)	< 0.001	1.65 (2.22 to 2.69)	< 0.001	I70.8	58.4	I48 (+)
4.M25	54.9 (10.9)	< 0.001	1.38 (1.15 to 1.65)	0.030	I30.9	2.6	None
					I73.0	4.4	
					M62.6	26.4	
4.F01	62.7 (11.0)	< 0.001	0.74 (0.66 to 0.84)	< 0.001	M75.4	2.1	None
					I20.1	2.03	
4.F02	64.0 (12.5)	< 0.001	1.73 (1.57 to 1.91)	< 0.001	E10.9	34.3	E11 (+)
					E11.9	11.9	
					H36.0	95.0	
4.F04	63.7 (12.5)	< 0.001	1.23 (1.10 to 1.38)	0.013	I21	2.52	None
4.F13	64.6 (11.6)	0.33	1.13 (0.93 to 1.38)	> 0.99	I63.9	21.1	None
4.F16	70.0 (10.5)	< 0.001	1.76 (1.48 to 2.10)	< 0.001	I73.9	43.0	I25 (-)
ID	Mean age at index		HR, <u>secondary outcome</u> (95% CI)	Adj. P-value	Main enrichment		Significant PGS. Trait (effect)
	Years (SD)	P-value ⁴			ICD-10	O/E-ratio	
4.M04	65.8 (10.6)	< 0.001	1.51 (1.35 to 1.70)	< 0.001	I48.2	11.1	I48 (+) E11 (-)
					I50.1	7.1	
4.M08	66.2 (11.2)	< 0.001	3.10 (2.81 to 3.4)	< 0.001	J44.0	65.7	None
4.M10	57.9 (10.3)	< 0.001	3.14 (2.72 to 3.62)	< 0.001	F10.2	196.2	None
4.M23	71.4 (9.5)	< 0.001	1.86 (1.57 to 2.20)	< 0.001	C61	80.9	None
4.F06	67.4 (11.3)	< 0.001	3.93 (2.93 to 3.69)	< 0.001	J44.9	16.7	None
4.F11	70.1 (11.4)	< 0.001	1.42 (1.19 to 1.70)	< 0.001	I34.0	7.3	I48 (+)
					I48.9	12.7	
					I50.0	4.0	
4.F12	69.9 (9.7)	< 0.001	1.75 (1.47 to 2.08)	< 0.001	C50.9	291.7	E11 (-)
4.F21	59.0 (11.2)	< 0.001	3.13 (2.38 to 4.12)	< 0.001	F10.2	104.7	None

⁴Two-sided Wilcoxon test for difference in mean age of patients in cluster against mean age of the other clusters. P-value Bonferroni adjusted.

⁵ICD-10 code except for LDL = LDL cholesterol and TC = total cholesterol. O/E ratio = Ratio of observed and expected term frequencies.

Figure captions

Figure 1: Flowchart: Data sources, study population and outcomes. Gray: Identification. Blue: Screening. Red: Eligibility. Green: Inclusion and outcomes. NPR = The Danish National Patient Registry. IHD: ischemic heart disease (ICD-10 codes I20-I25 or block R94). CAG = coronary arteriography. CCTA: coronary computed tomography angiography. ICD-10: International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th Revision. SKS: Sundhedsvæsenets Klassifikationssystem (The Danish Health Authority Classification System).

Figure 2: Clusters as a function of inflation parameter. Clusters plotted vertically at six different granularity levels displaying their branching in response to increased inflation going left to right. Number of male clusters (A) ranged from 24 to 35 and number of female clusters (B) ranged from 16 to 31 clusters across the six levels. Each black vertical bar corresponds to one granularity level (level 1 through 6 going left to right). Length of the bars is proportional to the number of patients in each cluster. Annotations inside black vertical bars denote a single, sex-specific cluster uniquely per granularity level. Granularity level indicated above black vertical bars. Color key according to the HR of a cluster. If a cluster is partly colored (i.e., different from grey) the entire cluster has the HR indicated by the color.

Figure 3: Risk of secondary ischemic events and risk of death from non-IHD causes stratified by cluster. Forest plots where clusters at granularity level four are shown against HR for risk primary (left) and secondary (right) for males (A) and females (B), respectively. Table on the left with cluster, number of patients (size) mean age at index (age) and cluster characteristics based on O/E-ratios. “*”: No extreme enrichment in cluster, i.e., no terms in cluster with O/E-ratio > 10. Boxes correspond to HR and bars indicate 95% CI. A: Male clusters at granularity level four. B: Female clusters at granularity level four. X-axis: HR for a cluster relative to average HR of all other clusters. Y-axis: Clusters arranged by risk of secondary ischemic events, increasing from top to bottom. IHD: Ischemic heart disease. GERD: Gastroesophageal reflux disease. GI-tract: Gastro-intestinal tract. HR: Hazard ratio. CI: Confidence interval. For a tabulated version of the results, see eTable 5 (survival analyses) and the Supplement with O/E-ratios.

Figure 1

Figure 2

A

B

- HR=1 for secondary ischemic events
- HR≠1 for secondary ischemic events
- Alternating HR for secondary ischemic events
- HR≠1 for death from non-IHD causes

Figure 3

A

B

9 | PMHnet-alpha: a neural network-based discrete-time survival model for mortality prediction in ischemic heart disease

PMHnet-alpha: a neural network-based discrete-time survival model for mortality prediction in ischemic heart disease

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Abstract

Background: Current risk prediction models in ischemic heart disease (IHD) use a small number of well-known risk factors that all need to be available and are largely the same as they were twenty years ago. To expand to a data-driven approach with a much broader set of input features, we developed PMHnet-alpha, a neural network-based survival model for prediction of all-cause mortality in IHD.

Methods: In this retrospective cohort study, 39746 IHD patients from the Eastern Danish Heart Registry were included. All patients had been subjected to a coronary angiography. Data sources included the Danish National Patient Registry, East Danish electronic health records and genotyping data from Copenhagen Hospital Biobank. Features were linked via the Danish personal identification number. A total of 595 different features (diagnosis codes, procedure codes, biochemical test results, clinical measurements, and polygenic scores) were extracted from these data sources and used for model development by gradually increasing the number of input features. Prior to model development, patients were randomly divided into a training set (n = 34746) and a validation set (n = 5000). Survival model performance was evaluated at six months, one year, three-, and five years of follow-up using time-dependent ROC curve analysis, Harrell's C-index and a variety calibration analyses. Feature explainability analysis was performed using SHAP values on the trained models. PMHnet-alpha was benchmarked against the GRACE Risk Score 2.0 (GRACE2.0).

Findings: PMHnet-alpha had excellent discrimination in the validation data with time-dependent AUCs of 0.883 (95% CI 0.862-0.898) at six months, 0.877 (95% CI 0.858-0.895) at one year, 0.839 (95% CI 0.821-0.861) at three years, and 0.818 (95% CI 0.800-0.836) at five years. The discrimination of the benchmark model GRACE2.0 on the same data was 0.768 at six months, 0.768 at one year, and 0.729 at three years. The explainability analysis showed that globally age, coronary pathology and smoking status were the most predictive input features.

Interpretation: We demonstrated that a neural network-based survival model for the prediction of all-cause mortality in IHD outperformed GRACE2.0. PMHnet-alpha supports better and optimized use of available healthcare data by including hundreds of input features and allowing for missing data. We argue that data-driven strategies are necessary to transform the increasing amount of data generated in the modern healthcare system into evidence-based clinical decision making.

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Introduction

Ischemic heart disease (IHD) is one of the leading causes of death world-wide and among the most studied diseases in medicine.^{1,2} Although IHD is a highly multi-factorial disease, risk assessment is typically performed with reference to age and gender and absence or presence of a few conditions such as hypertension, diabetes, and smoking.^{3,4} In the clinical management of patients with IHD, current risk scoring algorithms based on classical regressions such as Framingham, GRACE, and TIMI risk scores include only a limited set of well-characterized risk factors.⁵⁻⁸

In contrast to traditional regression models, most machine learning (ML) models such as neural networks, can process combinations of features non-linearly.⁹ Capture of non-linear relationships without the need of expert feature engineering is of major importance. In contrast to the traditional scores, strict data completeness is less of a concern since many ML models handle missing values by design.¹⁰ Thus, ML modeling is a potential solution to the fact that the increasingly complex healthcare data require advanced computational strategies as the capabilities of humans alone have been exceeded.¹⁰ In the case of IHD risk prediction, ML models have shown promising results but many have been limited to prediction of dichotomous outcomes, such as one-year survival or two-year major adverse cardiac events, while others have undergone limited or no external validation.¹¹⁻¹⁵

Here we present PMHnet-alpha, a neural network developed to predict all-cause mortality in IHD patients based on deep phenotyping, built on regionwide healthcare registries, complete electronic health records (EHRs), and polygenic scores (PGSs) obtained from genotyping data. To handle time-to-event data and censoring, we used a discrete-time survival ML model, which both increased power and allowed for generating predictions at different timepoints with a single model.

Methods

Data foundation, inclusion criteria, and outcomes

PMHnet-alpha was developed in a derivation cohort constructed from the Danish National Patient Registry (NPR) and the Eastern Danish Heart Registry (EDHR).¹⁶ Additional input features were obtained from an EHR database that covers Eastern Denmark in the years 2006-2016 (BTH), and the Copenhagen Hospital Biobank (CHB).¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Outcomes were defined using The Central Person Registry and The Danish Register for Causes of Death.^{20,21} Data sources were linked using the Danish personal identification number that since 1968 has identified all Danish citizens uniquely.¹⁷

The derivation cohort was defined by application of several inclusion and exclusion criteria to NPR and EDHR data (Figure 1). First we identified all patients with a WHO ICD-10 code for IHD (I20-I25) who had been subjected to a coronary angiography (CAG) between 2006 and 2016. Coronary pathology was defined as diffuse atheromatosis or one-, two-, or three- vessel disease (DA, 1VD, 2VD, 3VD) as classified by coronary angiography. Second, patients previously diagnosed with IHD, patients younger than 18 years at the time of the CAG, and emigrants were excluded. For patients fulfilling these criteria, we used the date of the earliest CAG as time zero (i.e. the index date) and included five years of follow-up. Patients were followed until either death or censoring, whichever came first. Using the holdout method, the derivation cohort was divided into a training set and a test set that were used for model development and independent assessment of performance, respectively.²²

Feature selection and pre-processing

Using exclusively data registered up until, and including, the index date, we extracted a total of 595 features from NPR, EDHR, BTH and CHB. Features included diagnosis codes, procedure codes (e.g. imaging examinations and surgical procedures), results from biochemical tests, clinical features such as blood pressure, height, weight, and smoking status, and coronary pathology at time zero. Moreover, a panel of ten different PGSs obtained from CHB were included and computed following a protocol described in previous work¹⁹. An overview of the features can be found in table 1.

Diagnosis codes (ICD-10) and procedure codes (SKS/NOMESCO) were extracted from NPR and included in the model as one-hot encoded features.¹⁷ Diagnosis codes assigned more than 20 years prior to the index date and codes assigned to less than 1% of patients in the cohort were excluded.

Biochemical test results and their reference ranges were originally stored in the databases Labka and BCC and in this study obtained from BTH.²³ Tests were either annotated in accordance with the Nomenclature, Properties and Units (NPU) or various local coding systems.²⁴ Biochemical tests drawn more than five years prior to the index date and tests performed on less than 5% of the cohort were excluded. Results of biochemical tests were included in the model as categorical variables. Each test could either take the value -1, 0, or 1 indicating if the value was below, within, or above the normal reference range. In cases where one patient had more than one value available the most recent was used.

A total of 23 clinical features were included of which 8 were the same as those used in the GRACE Risk Score 2.0 (GRACE2.0) input features (“*Clinical characteristics 1*”, Table 1). Blood pressure and heart rate were obtained from the unstructured part of the EHRs using an in-house developed information extraction tool that recognizes features from Danish clinical text. The remaining clinical features were extracted from the structured data. Available continuous features were Z-score normalized prior to model development and missing values were then encoded with a value of zero. For the categorical features we used one-hot encoding with an additional category to designate when variables were missing.

Model architecture and development

To model time-to-event data and allow for censoring, we used the generic discrete-time survival model for neural networks described in Gensheimer 2019.²⁵ In this model, follow-up time is divided into a fixed number of intervals and the model estimates a conditional hazard for each interval, i.e., the probability of failure given that no event has occurred before that particular interval. PMHnet-alpha uses 30 intervals separated in time such that event times in the training data were evenly distributed across all intervals. The implementation applied the PyTorch machine learning framework using the authors’ Keras implementation (Nnet-survival) as a reference.²⁶ For benchmarking against GRACE2.0, the clinical features were divided into the two categories “clinical characteristics 1” that was comprised of the eight GRACE2.0 input features and “clinical characteristics 2” that contained the other 15 clinical features.

We used a simple multilayer perceptron architecture with one to three hidden layers and 10-200 ReLU-activated neurons in each of the hidden layers. The final output layer was a fully connected sigmoid activated layer that outputs conditional hazards for each of the 30 different time points. We added dropout to each of the hidden layers to regularize the network and prevent over-fitting. Number of layers, number of neurons, and dropout rate for each layer were fine-tuned through hyperparameter optimization. In hyperparameter-optimization, we used five-fold cross-validation to obtain an optimism-corrected estimate of model performance on the training set. Networks were trained by application of stochastic gradient descent, with the negative log-likelihood as the loss function. Prior to modelling input features were grouped in the categories “*diagnosis codes*”, “*procedure codes*”, “*clinical characteristics 1*”, “*clinical*

characteristics 2”, “*clinical laboratory tests*”, and “*polygenic scores*” (Table 1). PMHnet-alpha was developed by sequentially combining these six data type categories.

Model performance

PMHnet-alpha was used to predict survival curves on all individuals in the validation cohort. Model performance was evaluated through careful assessment of model discrimination and calibration based on these predictions.

To assess calibration and discrimination graphically, the distribution of predicted survival probabilities at five years was used to construct five different risk strata. For each of the risk groups, the mean predicted survival curve was plotted together with a Kaplan-Meier estimate of the observed survival.²⁷ For model calibration, patient outcomes were plotted against five-year mortality predictions and a locally estimated scatterplot smoother was used to obtain a non-parametric estimate of the calibration curve.²⁸ The smoother was estimated using the `loess` function in R with the default bandwidth and the area a between the regression line and the ideal line $x = y$ was used as a measure of model calibration.¹⁵ Using bootstrap resampling, confidence intervals of the calibration score could be obtained.²⁹

To complement the graphical methods, we also calculated time-dependent AUC scores as well as Harrel’s C-index. Time-dependent AUC (tdAUC) scores were calculated using the `tdROC` R-package.³⁰ Harrel’s C-index was calculated using the `rcorr.cens` function from the `Hmisc` R-package.³¹ Time-dependent AUC scores were evaluated at six months, one year, three years, and five years after time zero.

To further benchmark PMHnet-alpha we calculated the GRACE2.0 for all patients in the validation cohort.⁶ We extracted the javascript source code for the GRACE2.0 webtool using Google Chrome’s Developer Tools. The javascript code was then manually converted to an R-package to enable automatised computation of GRACE2.0 on the entire cohort. Since GRACE2.0 does not allow for missing features, we imputed missing variables using the `missForest` R-package.³² Imputation was only performed to acquire a GRACE2.0 score for all patients; missing values were left missing in PMHnet-alpha. Explainability analysis was performed using SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) values. The relative feature importance of the different input feature categories was computed by summarizing the absolute SHAP values for each feature category³³.

Ethics declaration

Study design, methods, and results were reported in agreement with the TRIPOD statement.^{34,35} The scripts and source code are available upon reasonable request to the authors. The study was approved by The Danish National Committee on Health Research Ethics project IDs 60833 and 1708829.

Results

Baseline characteristics of derivation cohort

A total of 39 746 patients (67.3% males) were included in the derivation cohort. It was randomly split into a training (n = 34 746) and a testing set (n = 5000) used for model development and validation, respectively (Figure 1). Table 2 summarizes the patient baseline characteristics and the data composition of the training set, testing set, and the derivation cohort as a whole. Mean age at index date was 66.1

years and 19.5% of the cohort presented with a STEMI. The restricted mean follow up time was 1651 days (SE: 2.58) and the primary outcome (all-cause mortality) was observed in 21.3% of the subjects in the training set and 22.2% of those in the testing set (Figure S1).

Performance and benchmarking of PMHnet-alpha

PMHnet-alpha was developed by sequentially adding and combining the six different input feature types listed in Table 2, which led to six different intermediate models labelled 1 through 6. Through hyperparameter optimization, the best performing combination of hyperparameters were identified and then trained on the entire training data ($n = 34746$). The various PMHnet models then underwent validation using the unseen testing data ($n = 5000$). Figure 2 displays the tAUC at six-months, one-year, and three-years evaluation time points for the different versions of PMHnet-alpha defined by their respective input feature combinations. The preliminary results have shown that the performance of PMHnet-alpha remains unchanged by simply adding the PGSs to model 6, indicating that the information from the PGSs may be included in the other data types.

Serving as a reference for the observed performances, the GRACE2.0 score for six-months, one-year, and three-years was calculated on the entire training set. The eight variables used in GRACE2.0 were available for 51.4% of the cohort. Imputation was performed for patients with missing values (see Methods). The tAUC of GRACE2.0 was 0.768, 0.768, and 0.729 at six-month, one-year, and three-year timepoints, respectively (figure S2). Thus, except for *model 1*, PMHnet-alpha outperformed GRACE2.0 in prediction all-cause mortality at all the evaluated timepoints (Figure 2).

Generally, the performance of PMHnet-alpha improved as more feature categories were added. The version of PMHnet-alpha with diagnosis codes only, outperformed GRACE2.0 in prediction of three-year all-cause mortality but had poorer discrimination at six months and one year. Interestingly, the version of PMHnet-alpha trained using the feature category “*clinical characteristics 1*” (corresponding to the GRACE2.0 input features) outperformed GRACE2.0 at the six-months and three-years timepoints, likely because non-linear correlations are considered by PMHnet-alpha. At the one-year evaluation timepoint the performance of this version of PMHnet-alpha was almost identical to that of GRACE2.0 for the patients with missing values. However, the performance of GRACE2.0 on the patients without any missing values was better than that of PMHnet-alpha (Figure 2). In contrast to GRACE2.0, the predictive performance of PMHnet-alpha was the same for patients with and without missing values (Table 4). The best performing version of PMHnet-alpha was *model 6* that based its predictions on all feature categories (Figure 2). The model has excellent model discrimination (Table 3) and a good calibration with a score, $1 - \alpha$, of 0.944 (CI: [0.925;0.964]) (Figure 3). In terms of calibration, the model provided too pessimistic predictions for patients in the 50% risk range but otherwise looked good (Figure S3).

Explainability analysis of PMHnet-alpha

Next, the predictive values (i.e., feature importance) of the different features was quantified using SHAP values for PMHnet-alpha *model 6* (in the following referred to as the final version). Globally, age was the most predictive feature and its feature importance increased at increasing timepoints. That is, age contributed more to the prediction at the three-years than at the six-months evaluation timepoint. The sequential addition of input features types showed that diagnosis codes were an important addition to the model that only used GRACE2.0 features. However, in the final version of PMHnet-alpha, no diagnosis codes were among the top ranking features. This indicates that the performance of a model with many

features with relatively little predictive value can be better than one with few highly predictive ones (Figure 4).

In the final version of PMHnet-alpha, clinical features used to compute the GRACE2.0, e.g. Killip class, presentation with STEMI (yes/no), and SBP were among the most predictive ones. Aside from age, the two most predictive features (largest SHAP values) were coronary pathology and smoking status, which are not included in the GRACE2.0 score. Like age, coronary pathology was consistently important across the three evaluation timepoints. Yet, the importance decreased slightly over time suggesting that most patients with severe coronary pathology died relatively soon after index (i.e., earlier time points). The opposite was true for age, where the feature importance increased at increasing time points (Figure 4). For the feature coronary pathology, DA and IVD were predictive features driving towards death whereas 2VD and 3VD were predictive features driving towards survival. Of the four possible categories for coronary pathology, 3VD had the largest impact on the prediction. The impact on model output for DA and IVD was about the same. Unlike age and coronary pathology, the feature importance of smoking was relatively constant over the three different timepoints. SHAP values for smoking were negative, meaning that they contributed negatively to the outcome (Figure 4). The predictive importance of the feature categories was also assessed collectively. Although the biochemical tests were generally not among the highest ranked features, the input feature category “*clinical laboratory tests*” had the highest overall feature importance (Table 5)

Explainability analysis of PMHnet-alpha for one patient, N = 1

Finally, the feature importance was evaluated for four individual cases with a predicted three-years survival chance between 0.75-1.00, 0.50-0.75, 0.25-0.50, and 0.00-0.25, respectively. Each case was represented by the linear sum of the SHAP values for the predictions at the three evaluation timepoints. Predictive features with the largest absolute SHAP values were annotated on figure 5. No SHAP values below 0.02 were annotated (Figure 5).

Case 1 was characterized by very few SHAP values above the threshold for annotation indicating that the patient had few hospitalizations prior to index date. The ICD-10 code N81 (female genital prolapse) was one of few annotated values and contributed positively to the estimated chance of survival. In contrast, *cases 2, 3, and 4* had overlapping top-ranked features. For example, the ICD-10 code J44 (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) was among the top-ranked predictive features with the largest absolute SHAP value. In all three cases it contributed negatively to predictions (Figure 5). In contrast, IVD contributed negatively to the prediction for *case 3* and positively to the prediction for *case 4*. Similarly, age contributed negatively to the prediction for *case 3* (82.7 years) and positively to the prediction for *case 4* (57.9 years). Age was not among the top-scoring predictive features with the largest absolute SHAP value for *case 2*. For *case 2* the most predictive features were comprised of diagnosis codes, procedures codes, and two biochemical tests that were below reference range, where low arterial partial pressure of oxygen and low plasma glucose were among the most predictive biochemical features. In contrast, low plasma lactate was among the positive predictive features for *case 3*. Interestingly, missing information regarding familial IHD was among the most predictive features for *case 4* (Figure 5).

Generally, the feature attributions of PMHnet-alpha was consistent with physiological response mechanisms, e.g. low oxygen saturation and low plasma glucose vs. plasma lactate and the chances of survival (Figure 5). Thus, the SHAP analysis serves as a proof-of-principle of model development. In addition, the observations derived from the SHAP analysis demonstrate that the feature importance in PMHnet-alpha is context-dependent. For example, the analysis showed that in *case 1* the age of 75.2 years contributed

negatively, whereas the age of 82.7 contributed positively to the prediction for *case 3*; but that the overall survival probability was higher for *case 1* than for *case 3*. Lastly, the SHAP analysis illustrates that PMHnet-alpha can integrate information of an administrative nature as well as information reflecting physiology, i.e., missing information regarding familiar IHD as well as biochemical test results.

Discussion

In this study we have developed PMNnet-alpha, a neural network-based model for prediction of all-cause mortality in IHD patients. PMHnet-alpha outperformed GRACE2.0 when the predictions were based on same eight input features as those used in GRACE2.0. By extending the volume and variety of input features using six different feature categories amounting to a total of 595 distinct input features, the tdAUC of PMHnet-alpha improved from 0.75 to 0.876 (Figure 2).

It is a defining attribute of PMHnet-alpha that features were included with practically no a priori assumptions regarding potential predictive importance. Similarly, no assumptions regarding linear dependency between variables were made, which allowed us to include input features based on availability. This contrasts with most previously published prediction models in this domain, where model features are often limited to the few most predictive ones^{8,36}. PMHnet-alpha is evidence that it is indeed an advantage to include more than the most predictive features in a risk scoring model by outperforming GRACE2.0.

Using SHAP values, we were able to rank the level of information of the different input features and characterize the model systematically.³³ Overall, the SHAP analysis served as a proof-of-principle and also exemplified yet another advantage with PMHnet-alpha over traditional risk scoring algorithms as PMHnet-alpha was able to estimate the survival rate for all patients in the cohort irrespective of data availability (Figure 5). Explicitly, GRACE2.0 could not provide a risk estimate of *case 1* without feature imputation, whereas PMHnet-alpha successfully established a survival curve for this patient. Based on the results from the SHAP analysis, we could assess that the estimate seemed reasonable based on the predictive attribution to the available features (Figure 2). Further, PMHnet-alpha enabled us to identify predictive features that are not included in conventional models and the SHAP analysis allowed us to quantify their importance. For example, smoking, which is not included in GRACE2.0, was among the most informative features at all three evaluation timepoints. It was among the most predictive features at all three time-points with a nearly constant SHAP value (Figure 4). This adds to the literature regarding lack of improved survival in IHD patients, with a history of smoking.⁴ Taken together, the flexibility of PMHnet-alpha with regards to input features is highly valuable in modern medicine, where data availability and access vary between countries. Thus, PMHnet-alpha can in principle be trained on a data set based on feature availability in another country or healthcare system, independent of the features that were available at the time and place of development. Ongoing work is centered on external validation and interpretation of the performance when PGSs are added. The actual realized disease history may contain the same information as the current PGSs could contribute. However, the lack of improvement could also be due to the current architecture of the neural network. As we are still setting up experiments targeting the analyses of the predictive performance of the PGSs, these results are not discussed thoroughly in this version of the manuscript.

This study has several strengths but also some limitations. First, in this study PMHnet-alpha was only benchmarked against one of the extensively validated risk scores in this domain. However, generally other risk scores, e.g. TIMI, are not superior to GRACE2.0 and there is even evidence that GRACE2.0 has the best discrimination in some populations³⁷. Further, PMHnet-alpha was developed in a secondary prevention setting and thus, the Framingham risk score is unsuitable for benchmarking.⁵ However, the derivation cohort was different from that of GRACE2.0 as it included patients with acute manifestations

of IHD as well as chronic IHD (Table 2). In contrast to the Framingham, TIMI and GRACE2.0 scores, PMHnet-alpha is not only based a limited set of risk factors only⁵. Overall we take our prediction model several steps further than conventional risk scores, by developing a model that is flexible with respect to volumes and variety of input data. We show that the performance of PMHnet-alpha is superior to conventional survival models based on the same features and that the performance of PMHnet-alpha increases gradually when the number of features is increased (Figure 2).

Having developed and tested PMHnet-alpha, we argue that there is a need to rethink the usage of clinical data within medical research for modern medicine to take full advantage of the increase in data volumes, variety, and analytical capabilities. Another advantage of the strategy that we applied to risk assessment is that it may overcome the existing barrier between risk scoring algorithms and clinical practice.³⁸ Explicitly, PMHnet-alpha could potentially be included as an application in EHRs for real-time risk assessment of IHD patients, as it computes a risk for all individual patients based on the available data (Figure 5). We have however not tested systematically at what point the missingness becomes a problem. Finally, PMHnet-alpha includes framework for model explainability, which is a common concern against the usage of ML models within the medicine⁹. In this study, we showcase that an explainable model is a crucial component of successful survival modeling based on ML, such as neural networks. We showcase that explainability analysis may both provide grounds for model confidence as well as discovery of important predictive features that have not been included in traditional survival models.

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Tables

Table 1

Table 1: Overview of the different input feature categories.

Category	Features	Hyperparameters
Clinical characteristics 1	Age, pulse, systolic blood pressure, cardiac arrest at index, abnormal cardiac enzymes, killip class, creatinine, st-segment deviation	
Clinical characteristics 2	Abnormal ECG, CCS class, diastolic blood pressure, coronary artery dominance, familiar IHD, patient height, icd-device or pm, ischemia test, LVEF, NYHA class, sex, smoking status, coronary pathology, patient weight	
Diagnosis codes	422 different level-4 ICD-10 diagnosis codes. Kept as-is or converted to level-3, block, or chapter during model development.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • icd10 level • time cutoff
Procedure codes	154 different NOMESCO procedure codes corresponding to various radiological examinations and surgical procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • time cutoff
Clinical laboratory tests	85 different lab tests with results categorised as <i>below</i> , <i>within</i> , or <i>above</i> the reference range	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • time cutoff
Polygenic scores	10 different traits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • winsorization

Table 2

Table 2: Cohort characteristics. Numbers are n (%) or mean (SD). For features with missingness, the amount of missingness is indicated as “NA: %”. IHD=Ischemic heart disease. STEMI=ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction.

	Training (n = 34746)	Validation (n = 5000)
Mean age, years	66.0 (11.4)	66.2 (11.5)
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	23413 (67.3%)	3410 (68.2%)
Female	11333 (32.6%)	1590 (31.8%)
<i>Type of IHD</i>		
STEMI	6796	972
UAP or non-STEMI	???	???
Mean height, cm	173.0 (9.32, NA: 6.4%)	173.0 (9.14, 6.3%)
Mean weight, kg	81.3 (17.0, NA: 4.3%)	81.7 (16.9, NA: 4.1%)
Elevated enzymes	15531	2158
Cardiac arrest	513	69
<i>Blood pressure</i>		
Systolic, mmHg	139.0 (24.3, NA: 17.6%)	139.0 (23.8, NA: 17.9%)
Diastolic, mmHg	77.9 (13.9, NA: 33.5%)	139.0 (13.7, NA: 34.0%)
Elevated enzymes	15531	2158
<i>Outcomes</i>		
Mean time to event, years	3.42 (2.9)	3.53 (2.88)
5-year all-cause mortality	7726	1064
<i>NYHA class</i>		
NYHA I	3839	264
NYHA II	4429	598
NYHA III	1851	266
NYHA IV	174	33
<i>Comorbidities</i>		
Diabetes	???	???
<i>Smoking at index date</i>		
Active smoker	10237	1497
Former smoker	11961	1758
Never smoked	9347	1296

Table 3

Table 3: Time-dependent AUC values for the best performing PMHnet-alpha model for predictions at different time points. Confidence intervals were obtained using bootstrap resampling (see methods).

Time point	tdAUC	Confidence interval
Six months	0.883	[0.862;0.898]
One year	0.877	[0.858;0.895]
Three years	0.8	39 [0.821;0.861]
Five years	0.81	8 [0.800;0.836]

Table 4

Table 4: Performance measures with (left) and without (right) imputation.

Outcome	pmhnet-alpha	GRACE2.0	pmhnet-alpha	GRACE2.0
Six-months all-cause mortality	0.883	0.764	0.876	0.770
One-year all-cause mortality	0.872	0.756	0.869	0.783
Three-years all-cause mortality	0.831	0.724	0.843	0.738

Table 5

Table 5: Relative importance of the different feature categories in the final version of PMHnet-alpha.

Input feature category	Relative importance
Diagnoses	27.2%
ClinicalOne	12.0%
ClinicalTwo	15.6%
Biochemical	34.4%
Procedures	10.8%

Figures

Figure 1: **Study flowchart of inclusion criteria and outcomes.** Flowchart showing how the derivation cohort was identified based on data from NPR and EDHR. CAG: Coronary arteriography. CCTA: Coronary computed tomography arteriography. EHRs: Electronic health records. EDHR: Eastern Danish Heart Registry. ICD-10: International classification of diseases, 10th revision. IHD: Ischemic heart disease. NPR: Danish National patient registry.

Figure 2: **Discrimination of PMHnet-alpha at six-months, one-year and three-years evaluation timepoints.** Model performance on validation set for the six versions of the PMHnet-alpha evaluated at six months (*6m*), one year (*1y*), and three years (*3y*) from date of index. Horizontal lines indicate the performance of GRACE2.0. Colored boxes represent the different feature categories that were used as model input in the different versions of PMHnet-alpha. X-axis: The feature categories used to train the different models. Y-axis: Performance of the models. One dot per model. Total of X models. Horizontal, solid line: Performance of GRACE2.0 on the subset of patients where all input features were available, i.e. no imputation. Horizontal, dotted line: Performance of GRACE2.0 on all patients. Diagnoses: Diagnosis codes assigned up to 20 years before index date. ClinicalOne: same input features as used in GRACE2.0. ClinicalTwo: other clinical features not included in GRACE2.0. Biochemical: Biochemical tests measured up to five years before index date. Procedure codes: Procedure codes assigned up to 10 years before index date. Polygenic scores: Polygenic risk scores for XX different traits. GRACE2.0: GRACE 2.0 Risk score.

Figure 3: **Model performance of PMHnet-alpha model 6** *A*: Average predicted survival across 5 different risk-groups overlaid with observed Kaplan-Meier estimates. Colors according to risk stratum. X-axis: Time from date of index in years. Y-axis: Survival percent. *B*: Distribution of predicted survival scores to create risk strata in *A* as indicated by the vertical lines. X-axis: Five-years survival prediction in percent. Binsize: 2%. Y-axis: Proportion of patients in the four different risk strata.

Figure 4: Overview of results from global SHAP analysis. Summary of results from the global SHAP analysis at the six-months (6m), one-year (1y), three-year (3y), and five-year (5y) timepoints. **A:** The then largest SHAP values at the four evaluation timepoints. NPU04998: Creatinine. NPU01349: Basophilocytes. NPU27783: Alkaline phosphatase. NPU01459: Carbamide. Sysbp: Systolic blood pressure. Vessels: Coronary pathology. **B:** The predictive value of age against the min-max normalized age at the four difference evaluation timepoints. **C:** The predictive values for the type of coronary pathology at the four different evaluation timepoints. DA: diffuse atheromatosis. 1VD: One-vessel disease. 2VD: Two-vessel disease. 3VD: Three-vessel disease. SHAP: SHapley Additive exPlanations.

Figure 5: **Specific model evaluation for N = 1 of four distinct patients.** Prediction survival rate represented as SHAP values for four distinct patients in the cohort represented as *case 1*, *case 2*, *case 3*, and *case 4* reading left to right, top to bottom. Cases are from four different risk strata with a predicted risk of 15.1 (*case 1*), 34.6 (*case 2*), 72.8 (*case 3*), and 95.6 (*case 4*) at the three-years evaluation timepoint. X-axis: The three evaluation timepoints, i.e. six-months, one-year, and three-years. Y-axis: Predicted survival rate for the four different cases at the intersection of the two colors blue and red. Blue represents features that contribute positively to the prediction. Red represents features that contribute negatively to the prediction. Highest ranked features were annotated above a SHAP value of 0.02 were annotated. SHAP: SHapley Additive exPlanations.

Figure S1: **Kaplan-Meier estimates for the PMHnet derivation cohort.** Kaplan-Meier estimates for the training (blue) and testing (red) set of 34749 and 5000 patients, respectively. X-axis: Follow-up time in years. Y-axis: Survival percentage.

Figure S2: **Time-dependent receiver operating characteristics for the GRACE2.0 on the PMHnet test set.** Three tdROCs corresponding to the three evaluation six-months, one-years and three-years evaluation timepoints go left to right. Red: Patients in the test set where all GRACE2.0 input features were available. Blue: Patients where imputation was performed prior to computation of the GRACE2.0 due to missing features.

Figure S3: **Calibration curve of PMHnet-alpha model 6** Calibration curve showing the observed vs. predicted all-cause mortality at 5 years. The dotted line represents the ideal calibration line. The area between the non-parametric loess curve and the ideal line can be used as a measure for calibration.

10 | Polypharmacy and drug dosage modifications: a longitudinal analysis of 3.5 million electronic health records

1 Polypharmacy and drug dosage modifications:
2 A longitudinal analysis of 3.5 million electronic
3 health records

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16 Abstract

17 Polypharmacy continues to grow in importance because of multimorbid, aging populations.
18 However, a comprehensive, drug-specific analysis of concomitant therapies and response by
19 means of dosage adjustments has not been performed. In this longitudinal population-wide
20 study of dosage adjustments, we used electronic health records from 3.5 million inpatient
21 admissions at Danish hospitals spanning the years 2008-2016 and identified associations
22 between concomitant drug pairs and dosages in close to 185 million treatment episodes. The
23 study suggests that dosage modifications are proxies of drug-drug interactions (DDIs) in 83%
24 of the cases. We found that drug pairs with no evidence of DDIs often had shared
25 metabolizing cytochrome enzyme and cellular transporters, and on average had a
26 significantly higher odds ratio of dosage modifications than drug pairs with established DDIs
27 (p -value < 0.001). Typically, these high odds ratio pairs were prescribed to significantly
28 fewer patients and described significantly less together in the literature. This may rationalize
29 the absence of evidence of DDIs among high odds ratio pairs as they have been harder to
30 identify in smaller-scale studies.

31 Introduction

32 In most studies, polypharmacy has been investigated using the number of drugs as a burden
33 indicator rather than the burden reflecting the actual combination of specific drugs.

34 Polypharmacy, broadly defined as the concomitant use of multiple medications by a patient,
35 makes prescription a non-trivial task as polypharmacy increases the risk of compromising
36 drug response through drug-drug interactions (DDIs) and by adverse drug reactions (ADRs)¹⁻
37 ⁵. DDIs may influence the efficacy or the risk of toxicity of a drug^{6, 7}, while the risk of ADRs
38 has been shown to increase by the number of medications⁶. The right drug at the right dose is
39 key in precision medicine to achieve optimal therapeutic effect. Although drugs are being
40 tested repeatedly in clinical trials, pre- and post-marketing, knowledge of the mechanisms
41 explaining the great variability in patients' treatment response is limited⁸. Pharmacogenomics
42 is an emerging and cutting-edge field aiming to understand drug response variability⁹. The
43 polypharmacy-related dosage changes observed in real world settings are highly relevant in
44 this context as well¹⁰.

45 As life expectancy and prescription volumes are increasing, balancing patient safety among
46 the numerous treatment options is becoming a major challenge of modern medicine¹¹⁻¹⁷.

47 Multiple, simultaneous treatments are potentially harmful and difficult to manage and have
48 been associated with in-hospital mortality and readmissions independently of age¹⁸⁻²⁰. DDIs
49 are often studied in small cohorts and typically consist of standard evaluation of potential
50 pharmacokinetic inhibitors and inductors. Frequently, only major CYP450s and drug
51 transporters are tested in relation to likely interacting drugs that are known to be prescribed
52 concomitantly in selected target populations²¹⁻²³. This is a problem particularly in the in-
53 hospital setting where the extent of polypharmacy is higher than in the general population²⁴.
54 Large-scale clinical trials of polypharmacy characterising drug response are difficult to carry
55 out. In randomized controlled setups, the volume of data required to reproduce the full
56 spectrum of treatment regimens is often not considered and concomitant treatments are
57 typically addressed in the elderly or in selected phenotypes only^{25, 26}.

58 As electronic health records (EHRs) are broadened into a research resource, studies
59 modelling prescription patterns, including identification of dose dependent ADRs, have been
60 conducted for entire populations and for selected patient groups²⁷⁻³⁵. However, the focus of
61 these studies has primarily been inappropriate prescription, improvement of patient
62 adherence, reduction of readmissions, ADR detection, and examination of the potential for

63 deprescription³⁶⁻³⁸. Yet, evidence for the relationship between polypharmacy and drug
64 response by means of dosage adjustments is sparse, and studies modelling polypharmacy are
65 typically limited to a smaller number of drugs³⁰. Surrogate measures of polypharmacy like
66 the medication burden index³⁹⁻⁴¹ and the comorbidity-polypharmacy score^{42, 43} are useful, but
67 still ignore many aspects of drug treatment contexts³⁹.

68 In this study, we characterized the complexity of polypharmacy in an in-hospital setting by
69 investigating concomitant drug pairs subject to more frequent dosage adjustments. We
70 analysed in the order of 185 million concomitant treatment episodes derived from more than
71 24 million drug prescriptions. We aimed to provide insight into polypharmacy in a real-world
72 setting and decide whether identification of co-medication pairs subject to dosage
73 adjustments may improve the understanding of drug efficacy, toxicity, and known and
74 possibly unknown DDIs. Finally, we argue that this study can complement
75 pharmacogenomics studies for addressing response variability in patients subject to
76 polypharmacy.

77 Results

78 In-hospital drug use and polypharmacy

79 In this observational study, we used prescription and admission data from 1,069,873
80 inpatients covering approximately 50% of the Danish population in an eight-year period
81 (2008-2016). **Table 1** presents a quantitative summary of the data. The median number of
82 uniquely prescribed drugs per patient was higher among hospitalized patients compared to
83 the general population³⁸. Polypharmacy was prevalent in all age groups and the number of
84 different drugs correlated positively with age (Pearson $p:0.40$, 95% confidence interval
85 CI:0.39-0.40, $p\text{-value} < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$, **Supplementary figure 1**). The degree of polypharmacy
86 varied across different admission reasons (primary diagnoses) with a median of drugs ranging
87 from three to eight (**Supplementary table 1**). Drugs were classified according to the
88 Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System and we used the first and
89 second levels to refer to anatomical and therapeutic drug classes, respectively. Among the
90 24,379,285 inpatient drug prescriptions, 902 distinct drugs were prescribed to at least 50
91 patients; and these drugs were concomitantly administered with up to 857 other drugs. The
92 therapeutic classes that were prescribed to most patients were analgesics (N02), antibiotics
93 (J01), and antithrombotic agents (B01). These were also the ones with the highest number of
94 concomitant medications ($p:0.93$, 95% CI: 0.91-0.96, $p\text{-value} = 1.70 \times 10^{-37}$) (**Fig. 1**).

95 Condensation of millions of prescriptions into drug dosage patterns

96 In order to study drug dosage alterations comprehensively and provide a framework for the
97 discovery of potentially unknown DDIs, we characterized the 24 million drug prescriptions in
98 terms of treatment episodes, which then comprised the data foundation for a Bayesian
99 hierarchical logistic regression. For each patient, we identified both concomitant treatment
100 episodes (where two or more drugs were administered simultaneously) and monotherapy
101 episodes (where only one drug was administered). Concomitant treatment episodes were
102 structured as pairs of an index drug and a co-medication containing information regarding
103 drug addition, prescribed dosage, and discontinuation (**Fig. 2**). Only drugs with monotherapy
104 episodes, and drugs that appeared in concomitant treatment episodes of at least 50 patients,
105 were included in the Bayesian hierarchical logistic regression (**Supplementary figure 2**).
106 From the set of 902 unique drugs, 413 drugs were included in the regression model that
107 estimated likelihoods for dosage adjustments during concomitant treatment episodes. In total,

108 184,026,179 concomitant treatment episodes were identified among the 413 drugs that
109 combined into 77,494 different co-medication pairs (i.e. an index drug and a co-medication).
110 Each co-medication pair was then characterized by the likelihood of dosage adjustment for
111 the index drug using odd ratios (ORs) and the monotherapy episode of the corresponding
112 index drug as reference. For 309 index drugs. the dosage was more likely to be adjusted with
113 co-medications than during the monotherapy episodes. Among the 77,494 co-medication
114 pairs, 3,993 co-medication pairs had an OR >1 (**Supplementary table 2**).

115 Among the co-medication pairs, 59 ATC therapeutic subgroups were represented and 56 had
116 at least one drug with ORs >1. All index drugs belonging to antithrombotic agents (B01, e.g.
117 dalteparin, enoxaparin, aspirin, clopidogrel), drugs acting on the renin-angiotensin system
118 (C09, e.g. ramipril, losartan, enalapril, tandolapril), and lipid modifying agents (C10, e.g.
119 atorvastatin, simvastatin, rosuvastatin and ezetimibe) were subject to dosage adjustments
120 during concomitant treatment episodes. Yet, there was no clear pattern in classes generally
121 widely co-administered (e.g. N02, A02, J01, C03, N05) and the proportion of index drugs
122 subject to adjustments with co-medications. Three drug classes with low co-medication
123 burden had no adjustments with OR >1, i.e. vasoprotectives (C05), antibiotics and
124 chemotherapeutics for dermatological use (D06), and nasal preparations (R01)
125 (**Supplementary figure 3**).

126 The complexity of drug dosage adjustments in a real-world setting

127 Next, we characterized the co-medication pairs in relation to the therapeutic class of the index
128 drug and the anatomical class of the co-medications. While co-medications appeared
129 homogeneously distributed across therapeutic classes (**Fig. 3a, left**), co-medication pairs with
130 ORs >1 were dominated by nervous system (N), cardiovascular system (C), and alimentary
131 tract and metabolism system (A) co-medications (>60%) (**Fig 3a, right**).

132 Co-medication pairs where index drugs were classified in the therapeutic subgroups
133 psycholeptics (N05); psychoanaleptics (N06); antiepileptics (N03); other nervous system
134 drugs (N07); drugs for obstructive airway diseases (R03); corticosteroids, dermatological
135 preparations (D07); and antihypertensives (C02) had co-medications of the same anatomical
136 main group in >40% of the co-medication pairs with ORs >1. For the co-medications with
137 ORs >1 and an index drug classified as antiemetics and anti-nauseants (A04), the associated
138 co-medication classes were more evenly distributed. Dosages of immunosuppressant (L04)

139 and antimycotic (J02) index drugs were often adjusted when co-medicated with anti-infective
140 drugs (J) (**Fig 3a**).

141 Co-medication pairs where index drugs were classified as antithrombotic agents (B01),
142 agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system (C09), antibiotics (J01), analgesics (N02), and
143 anti-inflammatory and antirheumatic agents (M01) had the highest ORs (ORs >3) (**Fig. 3b**,
144 **Supplementary figure 4**).

145 Co-medication pairs and evidence of drug-drug interactions

146 To test the hypothesis that dosage adjustments during concomitant treatment episodes were
147 associated with altered drug response due to DDIs, the 3,993 co-medication pairs with ORs
148 >1 were cross-referenced with known DDIs collected and curated from 15 publicly available
149 databases (**Fig. 4**; see Methods). DDIs were found for 3,297 of the co-medication pairs (83%;
150 **Supplementary table 3**). About half of the co-medication pairs with known DDIs involved
151 drugs from the classes antithrombotic agents (B01), diuretics (C03), beta blockers (C07),
152 psycholeptics (N05), and psychoanaleptics (N06), while systemic antibacterials (J01)
153 accounted for a minuscule part of the co-medication pairs with DDI evidence. For the co-
154 medication pairs with no DDI evidence the systemic antibacterials increased by a factor of
155 two, and particularly involved co-medications with antidiabetics (A10; e.g. cefuroxime with
156 insulin aspart, OR:1.3, 89% HDI:1.1-1.4), psychoanaleptics (N06;
157 e.g. dicloxacillin with citalopram, OR:1.2, 89% HDI:1.1-1.4), drugs for obstructive airway
158 diseases (R03; metronidazole with tiotropium bromide, OR:1.4, 89% HDI:1.2-1.6), and
159 agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system (C09, e.g. gentamicin with enalapril, OR:1.3,
160 89% HDI:1.1-1.5). Another extreme with a high level of unknown DDIs did involve drugs
161 for treatment of bone diseases (M05) as co-medications (increase by a factor of four). In this
162 case M05 co-medications involved index drugs belonging to J01 (e.g. metronidazole with
163 alendronic acid, OR:1.4, 89% HDI:1.2-1.7), B01 (e.g. dalteparin with alendronic acid,
164 OR:1.4, 89% HDI:1.2-1.8), N06 (e.g. mirtazapine with alendronic acid, OR:1.3, 89%
165 HDI:1.1-1.4) and N02 (e.g. paracetamol with alendronic acid, OR:1.3, 89% HDI:1.1-1.5).

166 Dosage adjustments, pharmacokinetics and common P450 enzyme and 167 transporters

168 We investigated whether the portion of co-medication pairs with ORs >1 had shared
169 metabolic or transporter activity. In total, there were 1,243 co-medication pairs (31%) that

170 were inducers, inhibitors or substrates of overlapping CYP isozymes, 754 pairs (19%) with
171 overlapping drug transporter and 948 (24%) with genetic variants having an effect on each
172 other's metabolism/transport activity (**Supplementary table 4**). On average, 7,097 patients
173 were prescribed these co-medication pairs (mean for all co-medication pairs with ORs >1 was
174 6,285). **Fig. 5** presents the 58 co-medication pairs with no DDI evidence that were inducers,
175 inhibitors or substrates of overlapping CYP isoenzymes, transporters or annotated in
176 PharmGKB⁴⁴ with genetic variants having an effect on each other's metabolism/transport
177 activity. They primarily involved index drugs from systemic antibacterials (J01), analgesics
178 (N02) and anaesthetics (N01) and co-medications from thyroid therapy (H03), analgesics
179 (N02) and obstructive airway disease drugs (R03). Among these are, for example, the index
180 drug ropivacaine, a local anaesthetic metabolized by CYP3A4, with the antibiotic co-
181 medication dicloxacillin, an inducer of CYP3A4 (OR:1.2, 89% HDI:1.1-1.3); similarly, the
182 index drug clopidogrel, an antiplatelet drug substrate of ABCB1 transporter, with the co-
183 medication levothyroxine sodium, an inducer of ABCB1 (OR:1.4, 89% HDI:1.2-1.6).

184 Comparison between patient volume, DDI evidence and dosage adjustments

185 Co-medication pairs (ORs >1) with no DDI evidence were prescribed to significantly fewer
186 patients compared to the DDI evidence group (two sided Mann-Whitney U-test, p-value
187 6.28×10^{-18}). We searched the literature for publications mentioning the index drug and the co-
188 medication (see Methods, **Supplementary table 5**). ORs for dosage adjustment were, indeed,
189 significantly higher in the less prescribed and the less researched group of co-medication
190 pairs (p-value = 2.44×10^{-19}) (**Supplementary figure 5**). The correlation between co-
191 mentioning and DDI evidence supports the argument that co-medication pairs with no DDI
192 evidence are less studied (Mann-Whitney U-test, p-value = 1.5×10^{-14}). In particular, co-
193 medication pairs involving index drugs from the therapeutic subgroups antithrombotic agents
194 (B01), antibiotics (J01) and several nervous system drug classes (N) were significantly less
195 prescribed and with higher ORs for adjustment among the co-medication pairs with unknown
196 DDIs compared to their corresponding pairs with DDI evidence (**Supplementary figures 6-**
197 **8**). Some examples include the antiplatelet rivaroxaban (B01AF01) with the co-medication
198 levothyroxine sodium (H03AA01), and the antibiotic cefuroxime (J01DC02) with the
199 benzodiazepine derivative nitrazepam (N05CD02). Rivaroxaban-levothyroxine sodium was
200 administered to 1,179 patients, had an OR:1.4 and was co-mentioned in 4 publications (mean
201 for B01 pairs with DDI evidence was 9,547 patients, OR:1.4 and 28 co-mentioned
202 publications). The second pair, cefuroxime-nitrazepam, was administered to 1,341 patients

203 (OR:1.4 and co-mentioned in 4 publications) versus 9,220 patients in J01 pairs with DDI
204 evidence (OR:1.3 and 12 co-mentioned publications). This may suggest that drug pairs with
205 no evidence of DDIs are often not captured in classical testing of drugs in clinical trials.

206 Dosage adjustments when treating multi-morbidities

207 To further characterize the most prevalent co-medication pairs in relation to DDIs, we
208 focused on four therapeutic classes generally prescribed to patients with a wide range of
209 morbidities and co-medications: antidiabetics (A10), antineoplastic drugs (L01),
210 antithrombotic agents (B01), and lipid modifying agents (C10) (**Fig. 6**). Alterations in
211 antidiabetics dosages were commonly observed when co-administered with analgesics (e.g.
212 paracetamol, morphine), other antidiabetics (e.g. glimepiride, metformin, different types of
213 insulins), diuretics (e.g. furosemide) and antithrombotic agents (e.g. dalteparin,
214 acetylsalicylic acid). The highest ORs appeared with co-medications of the same class.
215 Insulin aspart was likely to be adjusted with prevalent co-medications like morphine,
216 metronidazole and dalteparin for which there is no DDI evidence. Among antineoplastic
217 agents, methotrexate was the index drug subject to adjustments with the greatest number of
218 co-medications, many recognized as DDIs with shared pharmacokinetics, e.g. pantoprazole,
219 furosemide, ciclosporin, and ceftazidime, but also with no DDI evidence such as electrolytes
220 and carbohydrates. In the case of antithrombotic agents, co-medication pairs were all
221 characterized by DDIs, and co-medication with other antithrombotic agents presented the
222 highest ORs (e.g. acetylsalicylic acid, fondaparinux, clopidogrel). Last, among lipid
223 modifying agents, atorvastatin was frequently adjusted with antithrombotic co-medications
224 (e.g. acetylsalicylic acid, clopidogrel and ticagrelor), while simvastatin was commonly
225 adjusted with antidiabetic co-medications (e.g. metformin and insulin aspart).

226 Discussion

227 Here, we present the first comprehensive, large-scale study addressing the complexity of
228 polypharmacy at the individual drug level. The study integrated drug prescription and
229 administrative data from Danish EHRs and was designed to identify significant dosage
230 adjustments between specific index drugs and co-medications.

231 Dosage variability in relation to patient genotypes has been recently studied using the UK
232 Biobank cohort³¹, showing that maintenance dose correlates with patient genotypes even if
233 the prescribing doctors in most cases have not been aware of it. However, neither
234 longitudinal dosage changes nor patient polypharmacy was considered in this work. Another
235 earlier study of the UK Biobank characterized the genetic variants associated to the use of
236 different classes of drugs²⁹. This study did not investigate dosage changes either. Although
237 genetic variation is an important aspect to be considered in drug response, the genotype of a
238 patient provides only a portion of the information required to guide the choice of the right
239 drug at the right dose. Drug-drug-gene interactions (DDGI) and clinically relevant
240 phenoconversion induced by co-medication medications where a genotypic extensive
241 metabolizer is converted into a phenotypically poor metabolizer are now emerging as other
242 important factors^{45, 46}. Our analysis includes 1.1 million inpatients and close to 185 million
243 treatment episodes and does, in contrast, to the studies above focus on the identification of
244 polypharmacy-related dosage changes.

245 We found that dosage adjustments correlated with co-medications across nearly all
246 therapeutic classes, representing up to 5% of all co-medication pairs. By merging data from
247 15 publicly available DDI databases we found a strong correlation between DDI evidence
248 and index drugs presenting altered dosage when co-administered with other drugs, especially
249 among systemic antibiotics, antithrombotic agents and psycholeptics. Many involved co-
250 medications belonging to the same anatomical or therapeutic class, and probably representing
251 adjunct therapies, like in the case of antidepressants and psycholeptics for treatment-resistant
252 depression, the adjunct use of beta-adrenergic agonists and anticholinergics in the treatment
253 of acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, or adjunct treatment with
254 different antithrombotic agents, which could be explained by their additive effects^{47, 48}.

255 This study also substantiates the impact that cytochromes and drug transport proteins have in
256 drug dosage adjustments. A total of 193 index drugs were found to have shared
257 pharmacokinetic activities with some of their co-medications and constituted about 40% of

258 the co-medication pairs with ORs >1. Dosage adjustments with a pharmacokinetic character
259 primarily involved CYP3A4, CYP2A6 isozymes, and the ABCB1 transporter. We were able
260 to identify 58 co-medication pairs that were largely undescribed in the context of DDIs, yet
261 with shared metabolism, transport and pharmacogenomics. Among these, nine pairs shared
262 CYPs and genetic variants (e.g. tacrolimus with ketobemidone, and cholecalciferol with
263 valproic acid); six presented shared CYPs and transporters (e.g. clopidogrel with
264 levothyroxine sodium); and six presented shared transporters and genetic variants (e.g.
265 risperidone with levothyroxine, venlafaxine with levothyroxine, and levothyroxine with
266 quetiapine).

267 Our method may complement clinical guidelines⁴⁹ and drug interaction studies to help
268 addressing polypharmacy and provide directions for future studies in discovering new
269 mechanistic responses of drugs and new DDIs, which are likely numerous. However, this
270 study has several limitations. While we adjusted for sex, age, diagnosis at admission,
271 hospital, and yearly influence, factors such as patient weight, kidney and liver function were
272 not considered. Nonetheless, we did adjust for patient heterogeneity by adding a random
273 parameter in the model. Also, only the window when the patient is admitted to the hospital
274 was taken into account. We cannot exclude that other co-medications prescribed before
275 admission have an effect. We did not reproduce all dosage changes known to be associated
276 with known DDIs either. For example, we observed no dosage changes in the treatment of 76
277 index drugs for co-medications with known DDIs. We did not find an association between
278 warfarin and ibuprofen or between the macrolide erythromycin and the CYP3A4-inhibitor
279 verapamil, although DDIs are well-characterized between these drugs. In the study we used
280 the DDI information in a binary form, present or non-present, and this is obviously a
281 simplification. The two examples above represent well known DDIs with expected major
282 adverse outcomes (e.g. bleeding and cardiac toxicity). Thus, we should probably not expect
283 to observe many dosage adjustments in these cases, as the co-administration may be
284 discontinued immediately. Last, DDIs may not result only in adverse events but may have an
285 intentional purpose for an enhanced efficacy of the drug. However, we did not evaluate the
286 clinical consequences (i.e. adverse effects or efficacy) resulting from altered dosage patterns.

287 As dosage variation associated with co-medications was not fully described in the context of
288 DDIs and pharmacokinetics, we suggest that these pairs provide a basis for developing a
289 strategy to identify potentially novel DDIs. For example, methotrexate has previously been
290 linked to alterations on electrolyte handling and increased glucose uptake^{50, 51}, which is well

291 reflected in our findings where methotrexate is more likely adjusted with electrolyte and
292 carbohydrate co-mediations. Similarly, many antibiotics (i.e. flucloxacillin, gentamicin,
293 erythromycin, cefuroxime, dicloxacillin, meropenem and piperacillin) were adjusted with the
294 co-medication insulin aspart, which may reflect the altered metabolic control during infection
295 in patients with diabetes⁵².

296 Overall, this study contributes to a refined understanding of the importance of polypharmacy
297 derived from real-world data. Improved understanding of all sources of drug response
298 variability, independently and systematically, will allow for better possibilities to assess drug
299 efficacy and designing new methods to discover DDIs and DDGI as well as ADRs.

300 Online methods

301 Study design

302 The data used in this study was obtained from EHRs of 12 public hospitals in the Capital
303 Region and Region Zealand of Denmark covering the period January 2008 to June 2016. We
304 only considered inpatient hospital admissions, which included 3,161,647 million records for
305 1,069,873 million individuals. Admissions covering two or more discharges between wards
306 were combined into a single one. Similarly, in cases of re-admission within 24 hours of
307 discharge, records were also combined. The primary diagnosis of each admission recorded at
308 discharge was coded according to the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and
309 Related Health problems 10th Revision (ICD-10). From the EHRs, two different medication
310 modules were used to retrieve in-hospital drug prescription data: Electronic Patient
311 Medication (EPM) and OPUS-medication (OpusMed). The former has been previously
312 validated as a useful tool for pharmacoepidemiologic research⁵³, and the latter has been used
313 in a similar manner making it a credible source, too. The modules contain time-stamped data
314 on prescribed drugs and instructions in regard to the dosing regimen. All drugs were coded
315 according to the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification.

316 Calculation of prescribed dosage

317 For all drug prescriptions, average daily doses (ADDs) were computed. ADD was calculated
318 according to the dosage regimen indicated in the drug prescription. ADD represents the
319 clinical decision of the treatment plan regarding the prescribed dose, frequency and interval
320 (Equation 1). Drug dose (d) refers to the dose for each single administration; dose frequency
321 (f) represents the number of times the dose needs to be taken in the dose interval. Dose
322 interval (t) refers to the time interval in hours to which the dose frequency applies
323 (**Supplementary figure 9**).

$$ADD = \frac{1}{t} \sum_{i=1}^n d_i \cdot f_i \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

324 ADD was calculated for all prescriptions containing information for the prescribed dose,
325 frequency and interval of administrations. ADD of medications to be taken as needed and
326 with variable dose were coded as categorical ADD. In cases where prescribed dose was not
327 specified, the ADD was calculated given the strength indicated in the drug package label
328 information and the prescribed volume. If the prescribed volume was not specified, we

329 assumed 1 unit of volume. If the dose interval was not indicated, but the frequency was
330 specified, the interval was derived from it. If the interval and frequency were not specified,
331 we assumed a daily interval. Finally, if frequency was not defined, we assumed 1
332 administration per interval. Prescriptions for whose ADD could not be calculated represented
333 less than 10% of the total prescriptions analysed (n=1,790,106) and were removed.

334 Construction of concomitant treatment episodes

335 Treatment episodes (events from the start to the end of the administration of a medication)⁵⁴⁻
336 ⁵⁹. We constructed concomitant treatment episodes as the intervals of time when two different
337 drug prescriptions were contemporaneously active. We also constructed a reference treatment
338 episode as the intervals of time when a drug was not concomitantly given with any other drug
339 ('monotherapy episode') (**Supplementary figure 10**). Concomitant treatment episodes were
340 constructed in a temporal manner accounting for all the modifications in the prescribed
341 regimen of a medication in each individuals' drug profile, for both concomitant and
342 monotherapy episodes. Treatment adjustments were defined as the modification on the
343 prescribed dosage (ADD) during different episodes. Treatment episodes for which complete
344 sequence of prescribed ADD could not be calculated were excluded from the analysis.

345 Bayesian inference

346 The objective of the analysis was to estimate the probability of adjusting the dosage of a
347 treatment associated to the simultaneous exposure with other co-medications. We examined
348 all drug pairs present in 50 patients or more and all drugs that had a monotherapy episode in
349 at least 50 patients. We also excluded 77 drugs that were prescribed as one-time drugs in
350 more than 70% of their prescriptions (**Supplementary table 6**).

351 Dosage adjustments were modelled using a hierarchical Bayesian logistic regression model.
352 For each individual episode, the total number of modifications y was calculated as the
353 number of times there was a lagged change in the prescribed dosage:

354

$$y = \sum_{i=1}^n (ADD_{i+1} - ADD_i) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

355 The total number of trials T was defined by the total number of prescriptions during a
356 concomitant treatment episode. We then defined the probability mass function of the
357 binomial distribution as:

$$P(y|T, p) = \binom{T}{y} p^y (1 - p)^{T-y} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

358 where p is the event probability. In the binomial model, we directly predict p at the logit-
 359 scale, which means that for each observation i we compute the success probability of a
 360 dosage change p_i as:

$$\text{logit}(p_i) = \log\left(\frac{p_i}{1 - p_i}\right) = \frac{\exp(\eta_i)}{1 + \exp(\eta_i)} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

361 where η_i is the linear combination of the subset of concomitant and monotherapy episodes for
 362 every drug formally expressed by:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_i = & \beta_{i,0} + \beta_{i,\text{Concomitant drug}} + \beta_{i,\text{Age}} + \beta_{i,\text{Sex}} + \beta_{i,\text{Hospital}} \\ & + \beta_{i,\text{diagnosis}} + \beta_{i,\text{Year}} + \gamma_{i,\text{patient}} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

363 We included age, sex, hospital, year, primary admission diagnosis at the chapter level and a
 364 term for each co-medication as fixed effects in the model. We corrected for the main
 365 admission diagnosis as different admission reasons presented significantly different
 366 medication burdens that had to be taken into consideration. The criteria for including
 367 hospitalisation year accounted for changes in the market due to drug approvals, withdrawals
 368 and modification of guidelines that may influence the analysis^{60, 61}, such as with the
 369 decreasing trends of prescription in the case of opioids and antibiotics^{62, 63}. To account for
 370 unmeasured heterogeneity correlated with individuals and multiple visits, a patient random
 371 effect was included in the model.

372 To complete the model, we specified a set of priors on the coefficients:

$$\beta_{i,0} \sim N(0, \sigma_0) \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

$$\beta_{i,d2} \sim N(0, \sigma_{d2}) \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

$$\beta_{i,\text{Age}} \sim N(0, \sigma_{age}) \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

$$\beta_{i,\text{Age}} \sim N(0, \sigma_{age}) \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

$$\beta_{i,\text{Hospital}} \sim N(0, \sigma_{hospital}) \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

$$\beta_{i,\text{Diagnosis}} \sim N(0, \sigma_{diagnosis}) \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

$$\beta_{i,\text{year}} \sim N(0, \sigma_{year}) \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

$$\gamma_{i,\text{patient}} \sim N(0, \sigma_{patient}) \quad \text{Equation 13}$$

373 We assigned weakly informative priors to all coefficients, i.e. a normal distribution with zero
 374 mean and a variance of 1. Note that, the adjective "weakly informative" prior used in this

375 study is the classical wording but does not necessarily mean that the prior is truly non-
 376 informative. The random effect was also assumed to follow a normal distribution and the
 377 standard deviation of the random effects is given a normal prior distribution between 0 and
 378 1. We defined the prior on the scales of the coefficients as shown in equations (14-20).

$$\sigma_{d2} \sim N(0,1) \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

$$\sigma_{age} \sim N(0,1) \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

$$\sigma_{sex} \sim N(0,0.5) \quad \text{Equation 16}$$

$$\sigma_{hospital} \sim N(0,1) \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

$$\sigma_{diagnosis} \sim N(0,1) \quad \text{Equation 18}$$

$$\sigma_{year} \sim N(0,1) \quad \text{Equation 19}$$

$$\sigma_{patient} \sim N(0,1) \quad \text{Equation 20}$$

379 The models were fitted and posterior distributions were estimated using the R package *brms*
 380 (v2.8.0)⁶⁴. A total of four chains for 2,000 iterations each were run, with a burn-in period of
 381 1,000 iterations per chain. Model convergence was assessed by inspecting divergences, tree
 382 depth and R-hat values, which indicate if the four chains arrived at approximately the same
 383 posterior distribution for the parameters⁶⁵. We concluded that models converged with R-hat
 384 values below or equal to 1.1, tree depths not at maximal in any of the chains after warm-up,
 385 and zero divergences. For computational modelling reasons, drugs with more than 500,000
 386 concomitant episode observations (n=88) were down sampled following a stratified approach
 387 retaining the distribution of the original set of observations. Down-sampling was done by
 388 first selecting the most frequent 300 co-medications, and then reducing the number of
 389 observations to 500,000 episodes randomly selected based on the frequency distribution of
 390 six variables: age, sex, years, hospitals, admission reason and co-medication. The stratified
 391 sampling was performed by computing probability intervals for all six variables iteratively on
 392 the filtered data set. Probability intervals for categorical variables were based on the
 393 frequency of their values in the population, and age was discretized based on Rice's rule
 394 criterion (equation 21)⁶⁶. Co-medications that after down-sampling were prescribed to less
 395 than 50 patients were excluded from the subsequent analysis.

$$k = \lceil 2n^{1/3} \rceil + 1 \quad \text{Equation 21}$$

396 Adjusted odds ratio of dosage modifications

397 Adjusted odds ratios (ORs) for each co-medication pair were reported, using treatment
398 episodes without any concomitant drugs ('monotherapy') as a reference. Posterior
399 distributions were summarized with 89% High Density Interval (HDI)⁶⁷ of the OR. HDI is
400 the portion of the posterior distribution containing the percentage of probable values. HDI
401 with 89% intervals were used as these are considered to be more stable than 95% intervals⁶⁷
402 as several effective sample sizes (ESS) from the posterior distribution were not always >200
403 or >1000. An ESS of 10,000 is recommended for choosing the 95% interval⁶⁸. ORs can be
404 interpreted as the likelihood the administration with a co-medication was observed with a
405 change in the dosage in the following prescription of the index drug. The reported OR is the
406 median of the posterior distribution. In order to assume clinically meaningful associations,
407 we defined a Region Of Equivalent Practice (ROPE) in the interval (-0.05, 0.05) equivalent to
408 a null region. If the HDI is completely outside the ROPE, the null hypothesis was rejected;
409 whereas if all most values of HDI covers the ROPE the null hypothesis was accepted⁶⁹.

410 Drug-drug interaction data

411 To analyse the overlap between co-medication pairs associated with dosage changes and
412 DDIs, drug interaction data from the 15 most widespread DDI databases were collected
413 following a similar approach to Ayvaz et al.⁷⁰. These were DrugBank⁷¹, Danish Medicines
414 Agency database for drug interactions⁷², NLM CV DDI Corpus⁷⁰, ONC-HP⁷³, ONC-NI⁷⁴,
415 Corpus PK⁷⁵, Corpus 2013⁷⁶, Corpus 2011⁷⁷, Twosides⁷⁸, CredibleMeds⁷⁹, KEGG Medicus⁸⁰,
416 VA NDF-RT, HEP Drug Interactions database (www.hep-druginteractions.org), HIV Drug
417 Interactions database (www.hiv-druginteractions.org) and Cancer Drug Interactions database
418 (www.cancer-druginteractions.org). The low consistency and overlapping can be explained
419 by data different sources among database and because some are focused on specific disease
420 (i.e. HIV, HEP, Cancer) or complication areas (CredibleMeds and QT intervals).

421 Drug metabolism and transport data

422 Enzyme metabolism and protein transport data was retrieved from DrugBank⁷¹.

423 We limited the investigation to a common set of cytochromes and drug transporters
424 recommended to be evaluated by regulatory agencies: CYP1A2, CYP2B6, CYP2C8,
425 CYP2C9, CYP2C19, CYP2D6, CYP2E1, CYP3A4, CYP3A5, CYP3A7, ABCB1, BCRP,
426 MATE1, Mate-2k, OAT1, OAT3, OCT1, OCT2, OATP1B1, OATP1B3 and P-SP^{21, 22}.

427 We assumed a common metabolism or transport activity if drug and co-medications were
428 inducers, inhibitors or substrates for the same CYP enzyme or transport protein.

429 Information regarding variant annotations of associated genes with drugs was retrieved from
430 PharmGKB⁴⁴. We assumed a drug and its co-medication as potential DDGI when an
431 associated gene variant could interfere with each other's metabolic or transport activity,
432 either by induction, inhibition or substrate, or with an associated gene variant associated to a
433 CYP or a transport protein.

434 Literature data

435 Literature search and statistics about co-mentioned concomitant drugs were extracted using a
436 previously described full-text article corpus comprising up to 15 million full text articles as
437 well as 16.5 million additional abstracts in PubMed and MEDLINE⁸¹. This corpus was
438 reduced to only include articles indexed in MEDLINE, as these are the ones including
439 journals related to Health Sciences, Chemistry and Life Sciences, and therefore the ones most
440 likely covering DDIs. We used the following rules to decide which texts to include: (1) Use
441 the full text for an abstract if available from PubMed Central; (2) use the full text for an
442 abstract if available from the full text corpus; (3) otherwise, use the abstract (Supplementary
443 figure 11). In total we analysed 3.8 million articles of which the full text was available (1.1
444 million non-PubMed Central and 2.7 million from PubMed Central) as well as 27.7 million
445 MEDLINE abstracts.

446 Comparison between patient volume, DDI evidence and dosage adjustments

447 The two-sided Mann–Whitney U-test was used to test whether number of patients, number of
448 co-mentions and ORs were significantly higher in co-medication pairs with known DDI
449 evidence compared to co-medication pairs with unknown DDI evidence.

450 Ethics declarations

451 Competing interests' statement

452 S.B. reports ownerships in Intomics A/S, Hoba Therapeutics Aps, Novo Nordisk A/S,
453 Lundbeck A/S and managing board membership in Intomics A/S outside the submitted work.
454 The other authors declare no competing interests.

455 Data sharing

456 Permission to access and analyse the underlying person-sensitive data can be obtained
457 following approval from the Danish Data Protection Agency and the appropriate Danish
458 Region (regional office for registry research in patient journals). Stan (v2.21)⁸², Python
459 (v3.5.4), and R (v.3.4.0) were used for statistical analysis. Due to privacy concerns, the
460 provided Supplementary Data only contain estimates for dosage adjustments and concomitant
461 treatments when it has been assigned to at least 50 patients. All data made available are non-
462 person-sensitive summary level data. The code used in the study is available upon request to
463 the authors.

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469 manuscript; or the decision to submit the manuscript for publication.

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471 Contributions

472 C.L.R. and S.B. designed the study. S.B. supervised the study and obtained funding.
473 C.L.R. performed the pre-processing of the data. C.L.R. and G.M. performed computational
474 analysis. C.L.R., G.M., A.D.H. and S.B. contributed to data interpretation. C.L.R, A.D.H. and
475 S.B. performed the literature search. C.L.R., G.M., A.D.H., J.H.S., L.C., R.E., D.W. and
476 K.G.B. provided technical and material support. C.L.R., A.D.H., and S.B. wrote the initial

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Tables

Table 1

Hospital admission characteristics (n=3,161,647).

Number of patients	1,069,873
Admissions/patient, median [IQR]	5 [2-10]
Age, median [IQR]	59 [36-73]
Women (%)	1,702,030 (54)
Number of admissions with status death (%)	63,609 (2.0)
Length of stay (days), median [IQR]	2 [1-5]
Number of drug prescriptions	24,379,285
Number of drug prescriptions/admission, median [IQR]	8 [3-14]
Number of unique prescribed drugs, median [IQR]	6 [3-11]
Most frequent drug classes, number patients (%)	
Analgesics, anilides (N02BE)	774,305 (72)
Analgesics, natural opium alkaloids (N02AA)	462,535 (43)
Anti-inflammatory/antirheumatic, propionic acid derivatives (M01AE)	371,309 (35)
Antithrombotic agents, heparin group (B01AB)	352,758 (33)
Antibacterials, second-generation cephalosporins (J01DC)	322,073 (30)
Drugs for acid related disorders, proton pump inhibitors (A02BC)	262,051 (24)
Corticosteroids, glucocorticoids (H02AB)	252,544 (24)
Antiemetics, serotonin antagonists (A04AA)	237,001 (22)
Antithrombotic agents, platelet aggregation inhibitors (B01AC)	224,017 (21)
Analgesics, other opioids (N02AX)	218,377 (20)

Figures

Figure 1

Prevalence and number of co-medications across therapeutic classes (circles). Circles are coloured based on the drugs’ ATC anatomical class and sized proportional to the number of index drugs within each ATC therapeutic class. Therapeutic classes with one index drug were not included (n=10). ATC: Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification system.

Figure 2

Conceptual overview for drug co-administration and dosage patterns. **a** example of an inpatient admission where three index drugs (drug A, drug B and drug C) were administered. Timestamped prescriptions (Rx n) are shown for each drug (four for drug A, three for drug B and one for drug C), the colour grading indicates a prescribed dosage calculated from the prescribed average daily dose (ADD). **b** For each index drug, concomitant treatment episodes were defined as the co-medication overlap between a pair of drugs. The dotted area exemplifies the concomitant episode for the index drug A with co-medication drug B, A(B). During A(B), the index drug A is added, followed by three consecutive prescriptions (Rx1, Rx2, Rx3) and then discontinued (D/C).

Figure 3

Representation of co-mediations and co-mediations with ORs >1 for dosage adjustments across therapeutic classes. **a** Distribution of all co-mediations (left) and co-mediations with ORs >1 (right). Therapeutic classes of index drugs (vertical axis) were ordered by the proportion of co-mediations with ORs >1, lowest in the bottom. **b** OR distribution where each point represents a co-mediation pair. ORs >3 were observed for index drugs in the therapeutic classes A07, B01, B02, C09, J01, N02 and M01. Vertical axis and colour legend shared for **a** and **b**. Colour according to therapeutic class of the co-medication. ATC: Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification system. OR: odds ratio.

Figure 4

Circosplot of co-medication pairs with ORs >1 with known (left) or unknown (right) DDIs. Relations between an index drug and its co-medication are marked by connecting bands, with the width of each band proportional to the number of pairs found between two therapeutic classes (the thinnest ribbon represents one pair, e.g. C07-P01 in the group known DDIs and A10-N04 in the group of unknown DDIs). The outer ring corresponds to the anatomical main classes, and the inner ring corresponds to the therapeutic classes. Colour of connecting bands corresponds to the anatomical class of the co-medication. The most abundant known DDI relations were observed between N05-N06, N05-N05 and B01-J01. Unknown DDIs mostly involved the therapeutic classes J01 (e.g. J01-A10), B05 (e.g. B05-N02), A12 (e.g. A12-R03), A10 (e.g. B01-A10), R03 (e.g. J01-R03) and M05 (e.g. B01-M05). DDI: drug-drug interactions. OR: odds ratio.

Figure 5

Shared cytochrome isozyme and transport protein activities in co-medication pairs with no DDI evidence. Among the 696 co-medication pairs with ORs >1, 46 shared cytochromes, 17 shared transporters and 13 were annotated with genetic variants having an effect on each other's metabolism/transport. For each co-medication pair (index drug + co-medication) shown vertically the OR of dosage adjustments based on shared metabolism, transport or variants is displayed. The horizontal line indicates the Bayesian 89% high density interval (HDI). For each anatomical class of the index drug, pairs were ordered according to their prevalence (top, highest).

Figure 6

Co-medication pairs associated with dosage adjustments for drugs from selected therapeutic classes used in treatment and prophylaxis of diabetes, cancer and cardiovascular diseases. For each therapeutic class, the 20 most prevalent co-medication pairs (index drug + co-medication) with ORs >1 are displayed (top, highest number of patients). Colour indicates the anatomical class of the co-medication, shape whether the pair is a known or unknown DDI with shared pharmacokinetic activities. OR: odds ratio. DDI: drug-drug interaction. PK: pharmacokinetics.

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11 | Optimizing drug selection from a prescription trajectory of one patient

1 **Optimizing drug selection from a prescription trajectory of one patient**

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18

19 **Abstract**

20 It is unknown how sequential drug patterns convey information on a patient's health status and
21 treatment guidelines rarely account for this. Drug-agnostic longitudinal analyses of
22 prescription trajectories in a population-wide setting are needed. In this cohort study, we used
23 24 years of data (1.1 billion prescriptions) from the Danish prescription registry to model the
24 risk of sequentially redeeming a drug after another. Drug pairs were used to build multi-step
25 longitudinal prescription trajectories. These were subsequently used to stratify patients and
26 calculate survival hazard ratio between the stratified groups. The similarity between
27 prescription histories was used to determine individuals' best treatment option. Over the course
28 of 122 million person-years of observation, we identified 9 million common prescription
29 trajectories and demonstrated their predictive power using hypertension as a case. Among
30 patients treated with agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system we identified four groups:
31 patients prescribed angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor without change,
32 angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) without change, ACE with posterior change to ARB,
33 and ARB posteriorly changed to ACE. In an adjusted time-to-event analysis, individuals treated
34 with ACE compared to those treated with ARB had lower survival probability (hazard ratio,
35 0.73 [95% CI, 0.64-0.82]; $P < 1 \times 10^{-16}$). Replication in UK Biobank data showed the same
36 trends. Prescription trajectories can provide novel insights into how individuals' drug use
37 change over time, identify suboptimal or futile prescriptions and suggest initial treatments
38 different from first line therapies. Observations of this kind may also be important when
39 updating treatment guidelines.

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45 **Introduction**

46 High cost of prescription drugs has become a problem in most Western societies, where the
47 expenditure of prescription is ever increasing and consume a growing share of the total
48 healthcare outlay^{1,2}. A better understanding of variation in treatment response and tolerance,
49 would increase quality of life and improve treatment guidelines while also reducing costs of
50 maintaining a healthy ageing population partly via prescribed treatment³. During the past 40
51 years, handwritten prescriptions have largely been replaced by electronic versions, and in most
52 Western countries e-health infrastructures have been designed to manage them⁴. This
53 transformation has facilitated secondary use of healthcare data, including studies of
54 prescription databases. Since 1995, all prescriptions redeemed at a pharmacy in Denmark have
55 been registered in the Danish National Prescription Registry (DNPR), now holding data on 7.2
56 million people⁵. DNPR is among the oldest and largest prescription registries in the world.
57 Examples of other prescription data resources include the Finnish database on drug utilisation
58 that was established in 1994⁶, and the UK Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD), which
59 also holds prescription data⁷.

60 Research using these resources has been performed mostly in a hypothesis driven manner and
61 highly targeted, either in terms of diseases (e.g., myocardial infarction)⁸ or drugs (e.g.,
62 antibiotics and gastric acid inhibitors)⁹⁻¹¹. In a large longitudinal study, prescriptions from a
63 cohort of over 9 million people were used to conclude that 26% of all prescribed drugs
64 influence cancer risk¹². Other studies have addressed opioid use and the rapid increase in
65 opioid prescription over the last decades¹³. Prescription studies have also been designed to
66 predict prescriptions based on previous, redeemed prescriptions. Data-mining prescriptions of
67 anti-diabetic drugs have, for example, been used to predict future anti-diabetic prescription¹⁴.
68 These studies involve less than one million people and focus on a subset of all drugs only^{15,16}.

69 Numerous guidelines derived from randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and meta-analyses –
70 for specific diseases and complications – have been published, e.g., hypertension, diabetes and
71 cardiovascular complications¹⁷. However, such guidelines rarely consider the full spectrum of
72 diseases that are often being treated simultaneously; and typically, guidelines present an
73 overview of state-of-the-art literature and evidence levels rather than answers to conflicting
74 clinical considerations. This traditional limitation may, in turn, result in inadequate or
75 unnecessary treatment for some patients¹⁸. Yet, the digital transformation, where entire health
76 registries are being studied in a data-driven manner, can potentially compliment results from
77 classical RCTs and meta-analyses in understanding the variation in treatment responses and
78 tolerance¹⁹.

79 Previous longitudinal analyses of sequential drug prescriptions have been performed in a
80 targeted fashion based on selected diseases or groups of drugs. However, it is unknown how
81 sequential drugs patterns convey information about an individual's health status and treatment
82 guidelines rarely account for this. This study is the first to perform a drug-agnostic longitudinal
83 analysis of prescription trajectories in a population-wide setting.

84 The objective of this cohort study was to identify and characterize the most prevalent
85 prescription trajectories in the Danish population, hence providing a model to help fill gaps
86 between disease registry data from hospitals, indications from general practitioners and
87 dispensed prescriptions.

88 Mapping population-wide prescription trajectories can provide novel insight into how
89 individuals' drug use change over time. This method can – at the level of individuals – identify
90 potentially suboptimal prescription sequences, as well as futile prescriptions.

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97 **Results**

98 **Condensing prescription data into trajectories**

99 We performed a comprehensive cohort analysis of the DNPR covering prescription patterns
100 across all drugs dispensed at all pharmacies in a nation-wide, universal healthcare setting. We
101 condensed the longitudinal prescription redemption data on each individual into prescription
102 trajectories then characterized over 9 million prescription trajectories of varying lengths among
103 7 255 919 individuals, 49.3% male and 50.7% female, (Supplementary Table 1 and
104 Supplementary table 2). For 48% of the population (3.5 million people) their presence in the
105 registry start in 1995 and end in 2019 (Supplementary Figs. 1-3).

106 In figure 1A females display an increase in the proportion of anatomical group G (genitourinary
107 system and sex hormones) during the teenage period. Furthermore, for both sexes in the age
108 interval 5-15 years there is an increase in the proportion of anatomical groups H and P (systemic
109 hormonal preparations, excluding sex hormones and insulins; and antiparasitic products,
110 insecticides and repellents), possibly related to growth and the infections of childhood. At older
111 ages, the proportions of drugs related to anatomical group B and C (blood forming organs and
112 cardiovascular system) increase, representing medication for the most common diseases of the
113 age group such as hypertension and atherosclerosis (Fig. 1A). Figure 1B shows a spike at
114 young age for both sexes, primarily related to anatomical groups J, R and S (anti-infectives for
115 systemic use, respiratory system and sensory organs). There is also a continuous increase from
116 young adults with a peak value at the age of 65-70 years for males and 75 years in females,
117 reflecting that the prevalence of polypharmacy increases with age and that life expectancy is
118 higher for females than for males (Supplementary Fig. 4).

119

120 **Temporal drug prescription association analysis**

121 From the full data set, 229 803 sequential prescription pairs (P1 → P2) were identified, where
122 all chemical subgroups of each anatomical group were represented. We then excluded all
123 prescription pairs that were redeemed by less than 100 patients, those with Q -value above 10^{-3}
124 and those with $RR < 1$ (Supplementary Fig. 4a).

125 Figure 2A (Supplementary Table 3) presents the most frequent statistically significant
126 directional prescription pairs (classified by chemical ATC class). All pairs were prescribed to
127 more than 100 000 people and interestingly all had an $RR > 2$. The pair with shortest average
128 intermediate time is formed by two drugs that belong to the nervous system group
129 $N02AA \rightarrow N02AB$, natural opium alkaloids and phenylpiperidine derivatives, respectively (RR
130 $= 2.76$, 95% confidence interval (95% CI): 2.74-4.13, $P = 2.70 \times 10^{-8}$), with an average time of
131 two years. Beta blocking agents redemption increases the risk for subsequent redemption of
132 digitalis glycoside ($C07AB \rightarrow C01AA$; $RR = 3.55$, 95% CI: 2.30-5.47, $P = 9.07 \times 10^{-9}$). Both
133 chemical subgroups are used as cardiac antiarrhythmic drugs. The pair with the highest RR
134 (~ 4) is $G03AA \rightarrow G01AF$, progestogens and estrogens, which include hormonal contraceptives,
135 to imidazole derivatives, respectively ($RR = 3.98$, 95% CI: 2.42-6.55, $P = 5.27 \times 10^{-8}$), while
136 the pair with the highest number of patients is $G03AA \rightarrow J02AC$, triazole derivatives ($RR =$
137 2.82 , 95% CI: 1.76-4.53, $P = 1.66 \times 10^{-5}$). Both imidazole and triazole derivatives are used to
138 treat fungal infections²⁰.

139 The directional prescription pair of drugs from different anatomical groups having the lowest
140 RR is $D07BB \rightarrow AB10K$, corticosteroids, moderately potent, combination with antiseptics, and
141 sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, respectively ($RR = 0.002$, 95% CI: 0.001-
142 0.003, $P = 4.44 \times 10^{-142}$). An increased risk of redemption of opioids (N02) is observed after
143 prescription of diabetic treatment, particularly blood glucose lowering drugs (A10B). Diabetic
144 patients often use opioids to treat neuropathic pain derived from diabetes²¹. The use of direct
145 factor Xa inhibitors (B01AF), which is a group of antithrombotic agents associated with a lower

146 risk of subsequent redemption of other anti-dementia drugs (N06DX) (RR = 0.41, 95% CI:
147 0.37-0.46, $P = 1.38 \times 10^{-62}$) (Fig. 2B). In Figure 2C pairs that belong to the same anatomical
148 group show that there is a high risk of taking vitamin B12 (B03BA) after redemption of iron
149 (B03AE) (RR = 9.87, 95% CI: 6.78-14.37, $P = 6.95 \times 10^{-33}$). Patients redeeming GLP-1
150 prescriptions (A10BH) are at lower risk of redeeming SGLT-2 (A10BJ) prescriptions
151 subsequently (RR = 0.45, 95% CI: 0.37-0.55, $P = 1.34 \times 10^{-14}$). Both types of medication are
152 effective antihyperglycemics and have also been associated with cardiovascular protection²².

153

154 **Prescription trajectories across chemical subgroups**

155 The directional prescription pairs were then combined into prescription trajectories defined by
156 recurrent prescriptions of three or more chemical subgroups, which were followed by a
157 minimum of 1 000 patients (Table 1). Trajectories containing prescriptions of four different
158 chemical subgroups exceeded 3.2 million. All trajectories form a heterogeneous network with
159 intertwined connections across anatomical subgroups (Fig. 3A), attesting to the complexity of
160 prescription patterns, as well as the fine-grained level of patient stratification these analyses
161 can support. Supplementary Fig. 4a displays trajectories where all prescriptions are classified
162 in the same anatomical subgroup. The largest number of trajectories is formed by ATC groups
163 J, D and N (antiinfectives, dermatologicals and nervous system, respectively).

164 We found that shifts between different cardiovascular drugs are heterogeneous and complex
165 (Fig. 3B). Patients starting with low-ceiling diuretics (C03AB) continue to another prescription
166 within this ATC group in 77% of the cases, whereas 26% of patients starting with high-ceiling
167 diuretics (C03CA) continue to another prescription in this ATC group (Supplementary Fig.
168 4b). The use of sulphonamides significantly increases the risk that the patient with this
169 prescription later will be prescribed potassium-sparing agents (C03CA → C03DB; RR = 6.43,

170 95% 95% CI: 4.16-9.93, $P = 5.40 \times 10^{-17}$). The use of thiazides and potassium in combination
171 (C03AB) increases the risk of retrieving a prescription subsequently that comprises several
172 other drug subgroups, such as beta-blocking agents (C07), dihydropyridine derivatives
173 (C08CA), angiotensin II antagonists (C09C and C09D), among others.

174

175 **Using prescription trajectories in risk stratification**

176 In Figure 3B, the chemical subgroup agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system (C09) show
177 a large number of trajectories interconnected across all chemical subgroups, following
178 prescriptions within the same group subsequently. More than 50% of those who ever redeemed
179 C09A (ACE inhibitors, plain) (n=1 074 196) also eventually redeemed a second drug from the
180 chemical subgroup C09 (n=569 212). More than six thousand individuals (n=6 379) follow a
181 trajectory that starts with C09A, followed by C09B (ACE inhibitors, combinations), C09C
182 (angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs), plain) and finally C09D (angiotensin II receptor
183 blockers (ARBs), combinations) in a short span of time (average 7 years between first and last
184 redemption).

185 Next, we tested if the differences in proportion of patients starting with ACE inhibitors and
186 ARBs, and subsequently redeeming another cardiovascular drug or not, would correlate with
187 the survival probability of these patients. The demographics of patients treated with ACE
188 inhibitors (C09A and C09B) and having no earlier C09 redemptions, and patients who posterior
189 to ACE got prescribed ARBs (C09C and C09D) were similar (Supplementary Table 4).
190 However, we identified four groups of patients with different survival probabilities (Fig. 4A).
191 A Cox proportional hazard model showed that individuals treated solely with ACE are
192 associated with an increased hazard. Individuals treated with ARBs as first line treatment and
193 with no posterior change in prescription vs individuals treated only with ACE inhibitors have

194 an HR < 1 (HR = 0.73, 95% CI: 0.64-0.82, $P < 1 \times 10^{-16}$). Individuals treated with ACE
195 inhibitors as first line treatment with posterior change to ARBs vs individuals treated with ACE
196 inhibitors, and individuals treated with ARBs with posterior change to ACE vs individuals
197 treated with ACE and no change, also have HR < 1 (HR = 0.47, 95% CI: 0.41-0.54, $P < 1 \times 10^{-16}$;
198 and HR = 0.96, 95% CI: 0.77-1.19, $P < 1 \times 10^{-16}$, respectively).

199 We then used the UKB self-reported medication information to stratify patients according to
200 RAS treatment, as described above. Similarly to the results obtained using the stratification by
201 RAS of patients in DNPR, a Cox proportional hazard model showed that individuals treated
202 solely with ACE inhibitors had a higher HR compared with the other three groups of patients
203 (ARB vs ACE: HR = 0.90, 95% CI: 0.84-0.95, $P < 1 \times 10^{-3}$; ACE-ARB vs ACE: HR = 0.06,
204 95% CI: 0.03-0.11, $P < 1 \times 10^{-16}$; ARB-ACE vs ACE: HR = 0.02, 95% CI: 0.003-0.16, $P < 1$
205 $\times 10^{-4}$). Interestingly, these groups had different survival probabilities (Fig. 4B).

206 Next, we calculated the trajectory similarity of patients treated with ACE with no change
207 (ACE) to patients treated with ACE with posterior change to ARB (ACE-ARB), based on their
208 length 4 trajectories leading up to RAS. Using the adjusted Tanimoto similarity score we
209 ranked the patients treated with ACE based on similarity to each frequent trajectory (followed
210 by more than 1 000 patients) from ACE-ARB patients. The survival probability of those
211 individuals whose trajectory history leading to RAS was most similar to the trajectories of
212 ACE-ARB was significantly lower. The top 5% (95th percentile) most similar patients had a
213 survival probability loss of almost 15 years in comparison to the rest of the ACE patients; and
214 the top 30% (70th percentile) most similar patients to ACE-ARB had a survival probability of
215 approximately 10 years less compared to the rest of ACE patients (Fig. 4C and 4D).

216

217

218 **Discussion**

219 This study sheds light on the immense heterogeneity in the prescription trajectory space in a
220 population covered by a one-payer health model. As population-wide health research with
221 registries and EHRs evolves rapidly, it grows closer to account for patient dissimilarities, i.e.,
222 advance precision medicine initiatives²³⁻²⁷.

223 Treatment decisions can be supported by these longitudinal analyses, as, for instance, the
224 findings for increased risk after C03AB of different drug redemptions. Thus, prescribing both
225 drugs at the same time, or changing the first line treatment for some groups of patients might
226 improve the outcome and reduce the risk of multiple treatment shifts. This finding is of special
227 importance for anti-hypertensive drugs as more than 70% of the patients in this study that have
228 a prescription for an anti-hypertensive will be prescribed more than one^{28,29}.

229 Patients with hypertension are very heterogeneous and display different tolerance to drugs.
230 Prescription trajectories might in many cases represent the existing treatment guidelines, which
231 indicate the sequence of drugs to administer given specific diseases and symptoms, and only
232 in case of side effects or incapacity to tackle the diseases can the doctor prescribe the
233 subsequent drugs (primary, secondary and third prophylaxis)³⁰. As exemplified above, in more
234 than 50% of cases, the use of ACE inhibitors (C90A and C09B) as a first prescribed drug is
235 followed by a series of different drugs within the same therapeutic group (C09). Often, drugs
236 redeemed after ACE inhibitors include C09C and C09D. These trajectories suggest that the
237 treatment is more effective when reaching the level of ARB therapy in the guideline.
238 International guidelines advise to consider ARBs as first-line antihypertensive therapy only if
239 there is a compelling indication³¹; the present trajectory-based analysis offers an insight that
240 perhaps most patients receive no substantial benefits from the first line of treatment and only
241 when reaching later treatments such as C09C or C09D are they are treated effectively.

242 Individuals' trajectory similarity can be used to support decision treatment in patients that
243 require treatment with RAS drugs.

244 Our study had several strengths and limitations. Using registry data from the entire Danish
245 population ensured a large sample size preventing problems related to inclusion and exclusion,
246 as well as cohort grouping during the drug pair modelling. Furthermore, using a nation-wide
247 registry with structured information on prescription redemptions, where redemptions are
248 always registered, guaranteed that we did not miss many cases in our study. Nevertheless, codes
249 will be missing in the cases where drugs are sold over the counter or dispensed directly by
250 health care providers. Second, the prescription of drugs will be limited to the decision made by
251 the physician, making observations confounded by indication. Third, with respect to the
252 number of people that follow a trajectory, those formed by drugs commonly prescribed will be
253 over-represented.

254 Some unaddressed challenges remain. For example, neither treatment compliance nor
255 treatment duration is considered in the current version of the model. However, we argue that
256 prevalent diseases like hypertension are ripe for analysis using this strategy given the large size
257 of the data set and plethora of treatment options. We exemplify this using the prescription
258 trajectories for ACE inhibitors and ARBs (Fig. 3). This model was developed based on the
259 Danish population and thus a population with a homogenous demography and generally a low
260 level of emigration, with 92.5% being European and the next most prevalent region of origin
261 being Asia (2.9%) (Supplementary Table 5)³². The prescription trajectories might be
262 confounded by patient characteristics. In order to reduce bias due to sex, age at redemption, or
263 year of prescription, these were introduced as covariates in the model. For specific cases other
264 covariates, such as specific diseases or other prescriptions, could be used. However, we did not
265 include it in the general analysis as these are case-dependent, and we aimed for presenting a

266 generic approach. Future work will be focused on integration of additional data sources, e.g.,
267 data regarding socio-economic status.

268 We identified the most prevalent prescription patterns in the Danish population, hence
269 providing a model to help fill gaps between disease registry data from hospitals, indications
270 from general practitioners and the dispensed prescription. Ultimately, the implementation of
271 prescription trajectories in clinical decision support may aid in better patient stratification,
272 further advancing modern healthcare towards personalised medicine.

273

274 **Methods**

275 **Study design**

276 Using the Danish Central Person Registry (CPR) number, a unique identifier to each individual
277 implemented in 1968, all residents of Denmark can be tracked and followed over time³².

278 We identified a cohort of all individuals in the Danish population recorded in CPR between
279 January 1st, 1995 and June 30th, 2019 (n = 7 873 901), who were at risk of redeeming one or
280 more prescriptions. Prescription redemption is recorded in the population-based Danish
281 National Prescription Registry (DNPR), and we found that 91% (n = 7 255 919) of the
282 population at risk redeemed at least one prescription in the study period.

283 From the DNPR, we extracted features from the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC)
284 Classification System at the chemical subgroup level (i.e., the 4th ATC level). For each
285 individual and each ATC chemical subgroup (e.g., A10BA, biguanides), only the first
286 redemption was included in the analysis.

287 Information regarding diseases was obtained from the Danish National Patient Registry, which
288 contains administrative information related to hospital admissions such as primary and

289 secondary diagnoses, which uses the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and
290 Related Health Problems 10th revision (ICD-10) during the period 1994 to December 2017.

291 The UK Biobank (UKB) self-reported medication data were used to replicate patient
292 stratification and survival analysis results.

293

294 **Statistical analysis**

295 We examined all sequential prescriptions redemption, i.e. two prescriptions redeemed at two
296 different times by the same individual, for all patients across a 24-year period. The relative risk
297 ratio of redeeming P2 after P1 relative to those who did not redeem P1 was modelled using a
298 Poisson regression model, where the patients' counts were treated as the dependent variable.
299 The analyses were adjusted for sex, age, calendar year and time at risk as offset parameter. As
300 patients are often observed over time, a single patient can contribute to multiple redemption,
301 age and calendar year categories. Consequently, prescription redemption, age and calendar year
302 were treated as time-varying factors in the analysis (see Supplementary Fig. 5 for an
303 illustration).

304 To establish whether the parameters in the model are significant, a Wald Chi-Squared Test was
305 used to obtain associated p-values. The counts may have a variation greater than that predicted
306 by a Poisson distribution, thus leading to overdispersion. Consequently, this may bias the p-
307 values downwards, leading to too small p-values. Q-values were calculated from the p-values
308 using the Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure to adjust for multiple testing.

309 To determine directionality of the pairs (P1 → P2 or P2 → P1) we compare the p-values for each
310 RR. We then selected the lowest q-value of the two as the two as the significant direction. To
311 corroborate the selection, we directly compared the two associations using a binomial test to
312 validate them.

313 To establish whether the parameters in the model are significant, a Wald Chi-Squared Test was
314 used for each Poisson model to obtain associated p-values. Q-values were calculated from the
315 p-values using the Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure. Moreover, the event counts may have
316 a variation greater than that predicted by a Poisson distribution, thus leading to overdispersion.
317 Hence, some pairs will have too small p-values.

318 To determine directionality of the pairs ($P1 \rightarrow P2$ or $P2 \rightarrow P1$) we compare the RR derived from
319 the model for each prescription co-occurrence. We used the p-value of both to select the more
320 significant direction and we posteriorly run a binomial test to validate them.

321 Pairs with a significant directionality ($P1 \rightarrow P2$ or $P2 \rightarrow P1$) were iteratively joined in
322 prescription trajectories to identify longitudinal trajectories containing three or more
323 prescriptions. These were obtained by combining pairs with overlapping prescriptions ($P1 \rightarrow P2$
324 and $P2 \rightarrow P3$ combined to $P1 \rightarrow P2 \rightarrow P3$). They were subsequently extended with more
325 overlapping prescription pairs to obtain longer trajectories. In order to add robustness to the
326 trajectories, we selected only those followed by 1,000 or more patients. The average time
327 difference between each prescription pair in the trajectory was computed.

328

329 **Survival analysis**

330 We evaluated the association between prescriptions pairs with a significant directionality and
331 death for the individuals who had been exposed to renin-angiotensin agents (C09). Patients
332 were included if they had been prescribed any C09 twice or more, at any point in their recorded
333 history. Patients were followed up until death or end of data period, which was up to 24 years.
334 This was modelled using a left-truncated right-censored multivariable Cox regression model
335 with individuals contributing to the risk group from the time they redeem the first prescription
336 of interest. The risk group was compared to the individuals who did not redeem any

337 prescription in the C09 subgroup twice or more. The model included age, sex and Comorbidity
338 Index (CCI)³³ as covariates (Supplementary Fig. 6).

339

340

341 **Trajectory similarity analysis**

342 The similarity between redeemed, individual prescription histories was calculated using length
343 4 trajectories (followed by more than 1 000 patients and up to 5 years before the first redeemed
344 RAS drug). Patients treated with ACE inhibitors and no posterior change to ARB, where the
345 last prescription was the RAS drug, were compared at the trajectory level to patients treated
346 with ACE with posterior change to ARB (ACE-ARB). To quantify the similarity, we used an
347 adjusted Tanimoto similarity score³⁴. Each patient's prescription history in terms of statistically
348 significant drug pairs in their length 4 trajectories leading to the first RAS treatment were
349 compared against each frequent trajectory followed by ACE-ARB patients. The intersection of
350 prescriptions was divided by the total number, PP , of elements in the ACE-ARB trajectory,

351

$$352 \quad sim(patient, ACE - ARB) = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{|PP \text{ in patient history} \cap PP \text{ in ACE} - ARB_{trajectory,k}|}{|PP \text{ in ACE} - ARB_{trajectory,k}|}}{n}$$

353 (1)

354

355 Similarity analysis was performed across all ACE-ARB trajectories for each patient treated
356 with ACE and no switching to other RAS drugs. The closer to 1 the more similar the patient is
357 to the frequent trajectories followed by ACE-ARB patients. To quantify the overall similarity,
358 we calculated the mean similarity for each patient across the set of trajectories.

359 **Data availability**

360 Permission to access and analyse the underlying person-sensitive data can be obtained
361 following approval from the Danish Data Protection Agency and the Danish Health Authority.
362 Due to privacy concerns the data has to be analysed in closed analysis environments. This study
363 has been approved by the Danish Data Protection Agency (ref: SUND-2016-83) and the Danish
364 Health Authority (refs: FSEID-00001627, FSEID-00003092, and FSEID-00003096).

365 **Code availability**

366 In order to analyse the data, the following software tool was used: R v. 3.6.1.

367 **Contributors**

368 A.A.O. and S.B. conceived the idea and wrote the first draft. A.D.H. and I.F.J. reviewed early
369 drafts L.V.M. had oversight of the data analysis, which was carried out by A.A.O. L.V.M.,
370 P.M., and D.W. contributed to later drafts. All authors approved the final submission.

371 **Competing interests**

372 S.B. reports ownerships in Intomics A/S, Hoba Therapeutics Aps, Novo Nordisk A/S,
373 Lundbeck A/S, and managing board memberships in Proscion A/S and Intomics A/S outside
374 the submitted work. A.A.O., A.D.H., I.F.J., D.W., P.M. and L.V.M. declare no competing
375 interests.

376

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381 (refs: FSEID-00001627, FSEID-00003092, and FSEID-00003096).

382

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465

Tables

Table 1: Quantitative summary of the number of prescription trajectories

Trajectory length	Number of combinatorial possibilities (x10 ⁹)	Number of trajectories (followed by > 1000 patients)	RR > 1*	Number of patients	Avg. time of trajectories (days)
2	0.00016	38,607	26,018	6,971,152	2,903
3	0.031	86,715	570,374	6,092,274	4,436
4	4.52	4,595,060	3,267,979	5,970,284	5,327
5	519.24	4,314,951	3,186,683	4,547,832	5,880
6	49,414.73	3,779,496	2,411,796	3,593,486	7,708
7	4,023,771.39	183,213	81,417	1,475,953	8,594
8	286,190,740.36	203	62	53,512	9,060

Figures

Figure 1

Fig. 1: Prescriptions redeemed at all Danish pharmacies in the period 1995-2019 stratified by the 14 anatomical ATC groups for males (left) and females (right). (A)

Proportion of different ATC groups against age at redemption. **(B)** Total counts of prescriptions against age at redemption. Color key according to anatomical ATC group.

Figure 2

Fig. 2: Selected directional prescription pairs. (A) Attrition of prescription pairs following temporal statistical modelling. This includes the drug pair steps (P1 → P2) that were taken sequentially by over 100,000 individuals, had a relative risk ratio (RR) > 2 and a Q-value < 10⁻⁰³. Drug pairs were ordered vertically by time between P1 and P2 from shortest to longest time (top to bottom). Sizes of bars for each prescription (P1 and P2) are equal and correspond to the absolute number of the logarithm of its RR. The pair with the largest RR is G03AA→G01AF. The unannotated bars to the right indicate the number of individuals following each of the directional prescription pairs. (B) Drug pairs (P1→P2) with the lowest and highest RR where

P1 and P2 belong different ATC classes. (C) Drug pairs (P1→P2) with the lowest and highest RR where P1 and P2 belong to the same ATC class. Pairs are ordered by RR, lowest to highest (top to bottom). *Refer to Figure 1 for ATC group legend.

Figure 3

A Trajectory network

B Antihypertensives trajectory network

Fig. 3: Prescription trajectory space. (A) All statistically significant prescription trajectories followed by more than 1,000 patients are represented in this interconnected network. The order

of the trajectories and the organisation of the network is arbitrary. The length of the trajectory is depicted by the number of nodes it contains (from left to right, ranging from 2 to 8). The heterogeneity of prescription trajectories is depicted here. **(B)** Alluvial plot of the chemical subgroups used in treatment for hypertension, including C02, C03, C07, C08, C09 (antihypertensives, diuretics, beta blocking agents, calcium channel blockers, and agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system, respectively). The plot is ordered by length from left to right, and arbitrarily by chemical subgroup from top to bottom. The edge height represents the number of people that move from one node to the next (going left to right). Note that patients can follow more than one trajectory at the same time. *Refer to Figure 1 for ATC group legend in figure 3A.

Figure 4

Fig. 4: Survival curves for the survival of patients treated with different RAS drugs as different lines of treatment. (A) Survival curves for different risk groups stratified by prescription trajectories. Age, Sex and CCI adjusted Cox proportional hazard survival probability by groups of RAS treatment: i) redeeming solely ACE inhibitors with no change to ARB; ii) redeeming ACE inhibitors with posterior change to ARB; iii) redeeming uniquely ARB(s) with no change to ACE; and iv) redeeming ARB(s) with posterior change to ACE. The hazard ratio (HR) is lower for all individuals treated solely with ARB or treated with ARB before or after ACE when compared to individuals treated with ACE with no change to second line treatment. (B) Survival curves for the same groups of patients in the UKBB (C) 95th

percentile most similar ACE patients to ACE-ARB trajectories survival vs ACE patients less similar to ACE-ARB. **(D)** 70th percentile most similar ACE patients to ACE-ARB trajectories survival vs ACE patients less similar to ACE-ARB.

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Disease trajectory browser for exploring temporal, population-wide disease progression patterns in 7.2 million Danish patients

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We present the Danish Disease Trajectory Browser (DTB), a tool for exploring almost 25 years of data from the Danish National Patient Register. In the dataset comprising 7.2 million patients and 122 million admissions, users can identify diagnosis pairs with statistically significant directionality and combine them to linear disease trajectories. Users can search for one or more disease codes (ICD-10 classification) and explore disease progression patterns via an array of functionalities. For example, a set of linear trajectories can be merged into a disease trajectory network displaying the entire multimorbidity spectrum of a disease in a single connected graph. Using data from the Danish Register for Causes of Death mortality is also included. The tool is disease-agnostic across both rare and common diseases and is showcased by exploring multimorbidity in Down syndrome (ICD-10 code Q90) and hypertension (ICD-10 code I10). Finally, we show how search results can be customized and exported from the browser in a format of choice (i.e. JSON, PNG, JPEG and CSV).

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Large-scale, population-wide studies of health and disease are increasingly gaining attention, as they complement conventional clinical studies focusing on a limited set of hypothesised disease associations to predefined outcomes^{1–4}. However, most population-wide disease registries are made available for research as large databases that require custom-made software to be analysed^{5–7}. While some disease registries provide interfaces that can extract summary statistics for patients with a given diagnosis, more advanced queries on disease progression patterns are generally not supported⁸. Multimorbidity—instances where one patient is diagnosed with more than one chronic morbidity—is, as life expectancy generally goes up, an increasing problem⁹. Therefore, the need to understand at the molecular level how etiological factors impact co-occurring and interacting diseases is also growing, where strategies typically benefit from the application of network biology concepts^{1,10,11}. However, these efforts should ultimately match disease progression observations made in large-scale, population-wide health data as already demonstrated in uncovering associations between complex disease and Mendelian loci² and estimates of heritability in the absence of genetic data⁴.

In clinical trials, the complexity of multimorbidity is being addressed by master protocols defined as an overarching model designed to answer multiple questions, for example, by studying multiple interventions in multiple diseases¹². Correspondingly, adaptive platform trials (APTs) facilitate the study of multiple interventions in a condition in a perpetual manner. In these trials, interventions may enter and leave an ongoing trial based on a predefined decision algorithm, e.g., response-adaptive randomisation (RAR)¹³. The shift towards more complex trial designs again emphasises the demand to monitor and study phenotypes as longitudinal disease progression patterns irrespective of predefined outcomes^{3,14}. At the molecular level, techniques like whole-genome sequencing and clinical proteomics produce data in a disease spectrum-wide manner enabling analysis of global interactions between disease pathways for subsequent linkage to actionable mechanisms^{15–17}. Finally, another contributing factor is the health economic incentive to study multimorbidity as medical management is complex and costly¹⁸.

The aim in numerous ongoing precision medicine efforts is to stratify seemingly similar patients into subgroups by identification of underlying differences in disease etiology^{1,19}. Ultimately, this will reduce the gap between geno- and phenotypes for optimised diagnostics and enhanced therapeutic responses²⁰. In line with the precision medicine discourse, disease trajectories, derived from population-wide registry data, were recently proposed as a novel robust way of studying disease progression over time; thereby creating a foundation for the discovery of causal relationships and the temporal modelling of multimorbidity^{3,21,22}. Trajectories illustrating frequent and recurrent patterns of disease progression can be constructed by identifying pairs of co-occurring sequential diseases with a statistically significant direction²³. Such work is likely to lead to revisions in the disease nomenclature; for example by redefining diseases based on disease history data and genetic risk profiles as opposed to the present paradigm where conclusions are derived from single encounters with the health care system^{24,25}.

In this context, we have constructed The Danish Disease Trajectory Browser (DTB) that lets users, e.g. researchers, trialists and clinicians explore longitudinal population-wide disease progression patterns from the entire population of Denmark. The browser is based on data spanning the period January 1994 to April 2018 and comprises electronic health data on 7.2 million Danes representing a total of 122 million admissions during the almost 25-year long period. Denmark implemented its unique person identification number in 1968 making it possible to track

disease development continuously across all hospitals at the level of individuals^{26,27}. DTB enables users to search, filter, analyse, and visualise disease trajectories derived from, statistically significant directional diagnosis pairs calculated from population-wide electronic health data^{3,21}. As the underlying data stem from a government-funded universal health care system, the data are likely less biased than many other large data sets that either focus on selected diseases, age groups, hospitals, or professions^{6,27}. DTB is made available at <http://dtb.cpr.ku.dk> and presents data as summary statistics. Therefore, it does not provide access to any person-sensitive data.

Results

Data foundation and disease trajectory approach. The data foundation for DTB is the Danish National Patient Register (NPR) covering 7.2 million patients from the 1994–2018 period. All entries in NPR are time stamped and linked to the national identification number that uniquely indexes every resident in Denmark. The sex is indexed in the final digit (i.e. unequal, male)²⁷. Events are therefore linked over time unproblematically, which this study benefitted from in computing mortality by linkage of patients from NPR to The Danish Register of Causes of Death²⁸. DTB uses a general approach to create disease trajectories that was originally developed to discover sequential disease progression patterns in a data-driven manner^{3,14}. Following a pre-filtering step and a matching procedure that corrects for age, sex, and period of year, all 1777 unique disease codes (International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD) version 10, level 3 indexed) resulted in 77,294 significant diagnosis pairs (Fig. 1). For subsequent analyses of disease progression patterns, the method requires that the direction of diagnoses D1 → D2, is statistically significant compared to the reverse order D2 → D1 with relative risk (RR) > 1 and *P*-value < 0.05 (Fig. 1). Disease trajectories must be followed by minimum 20 patients. The directional progression strength D1 → D2 can then be quantified by the RR and the associated *P*-value for any significant directional disease pair that results from a search query²¹ (see Methods). Furthermore, the DTB offers the option to analyse sex-specific disease trajectories, which are built from significant directional diagnosis pairs computed from male or female populations only. In effect, DTB users can also explore differences in disease progression patterns between men and women.

Disease progression patterns and disease heterogeneity. From the complete data set a total of 9608 statistically significant directional diagnosis pairs were identified (Table 1 and Fig. 1). These diagnosis pairs form the basis for the trajectory browser functionalities as they can be combined into linear trajectories and disease trajectory networks as shown in previous studies^{3,14}. The disease trajectory D1 → D3 cannot necessarily be deduced from the combination of D1 → D2 → D3. This highlights the complexity of disease heterogeneity and disease progression patterns. DTB queries for one or more ICD-10 codes return a number of trajectories with length ranging from 2 to 6 depending on the search base entry (ICD-10 codes) and search filter selection.

Below we exemplify the browser functionalities and potential for exploring population-wide disease progression patterns by characterising search results for patients diagnosed with Down syndrome (DS) and patients diagnosed with essential (primary) hypertension (HT; ICD-10 codes Q90 and I10, respectively), which represent two very different cohorts. We also exemplify how the combination of length 2 trajectories into longer trajectories further elucidates disease heterogeneity. The browser

Fig. 1 Register data processing. Disease trajectory algorithm flowchart (a) and schematic representation of the disease trajectory algorithm that is the foundation for Danish Disease Trajectory Browser functionality (b). **a** Pre-filtering and computation of statistically significant diagnosis pairs in The Danish National Patient Registry (NPR), containing data on 7,186,865 patients. **b** (1) Users select a ICD-10 indexed patient population by typing ICD-10 code(s) or disease(s) of interest (ICD-10 code, level 3). (2/3) The first step where the algorithm identifies statistically significant directional diagnosis pairs. (4/5) The second step where the algorithm builds linear trajectories by concatenating statistically significant diagnosis pairs, that can then be merged into a disease trajectory network, consequent to the fact that one disease may appear in more than one linear disease trajectory. ICD-10 International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision. Colours indicate disease category.

Table 1 The Danish Disease Trajectory Browser data foundation and examples.

The Danish National Patient Registry			
Years of data	24	Total number of hospital admissions	121,884,394
Total number of patients	7,186,865	Number of unique ICD-10 codes given ^a	1777
The Danish Disease Trajectory Browser			
Total number of directional diagnosis pairs	9608	Number of ICD codes included in the browser in directional pairs ^a	928
Down syndrome (ICD-10 code: Q90)			
Number of patients	3714		
Number of linear disease trajectories	117		
Essential (primary) hypertension (ICD-10 code: I10)			
Number of patients	807,234		
Number of linear disease trajectories	8359		

^aICD International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems.

displays search results either as linear disease trajectories or as a disease trajectory network (e.g. Figs. 2 and 3). For quick queries and overview, it is recommended that users turn on the network view, which will be fastest and also appropriate for subsequent adjustment of search filters. In DS ($n = 3714$ patients) and HT (n

$= 807,234$ patients), the number of resulting linear trajectories ranges from 117 to 8359 (Table 1). These disease codes relate to a chromosomal disorder and multifactorial disease, respectively, and hence, the two cohorts have vastly different frequencies and only limited shared etiology. Consequently, the number of

Fig. 2 Linear disease trajectories for Down syndrome (Q90). Upper bar with search field and switch to turn on Network view. Below the upper bar search results are displayed in the visualisation interface. Users can see the total number of linear trajectories (in this case 117). When a node is selected, search results are linked to the WHO ICD-10 browser in the side panel. The content of the link depends on the selected node (circles). When an edge is selected, search results also link to Google Scholar and Statistics Denmark. Width and shade of edges co-vary with the number of patients that follow the particular trajectory or as here the relative risk (depending on Settings selection, located in the side panel, Search tab). Users can navigate the search results, select the content of the links and change location of trajectories by clicking and dragging in the search result field. Search filter setting: no settings applied. WHO ICD-10 World Health Organization, International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision. Colours of nodes represent ICD-10 chapters.

resulting trajectories and degree of diversity may hint DTB users towards the underlying complexity of the true multimorbidity spectrum that necessitates protocols and strategies for studying multiple diseases and multiple therapies jointly (e.g. by master protocols as mentioned above)¹².

Exploring disease trajectories of chromosomal diseases. As expected, the linear disease trajectories for DS shown in Fig. 2 contain multiple diagnoses from chapter X (Diseases of the respiratory system) and chapter XVII (Congenital malformations, deformations, and chromosomal abnormalities), whereas the disease trajectories contain no diagnosis from chapter II (Neoplasms)^{29,30}. These findings may very well relate to the phenotypic effect of gene copy-number, which is rather profound in a trisomy like DS³¹. Moreover, the disease trajectory network topology shown in Fig. 3 reflects the fact that DS is diagnosed early in life (i.e. pre- or perinatally), as Q90 is the first code in all trajectories. It also demonstrates the complexity of disease progression patterns, as there is only a significant directional association among DS patients who are diagnosed with H65 (Nonsuppurative otitis media) and then F79 (Unspecified mental retardation) and no direct edge (i.e. length 2 trajectory) from Q90 to F79 (Fig. 3). Importantly, there is a considerable overlap between diagnoses that people with DS have a high risk for developing, e.g., Alzheimer's disease (ICD-10 code G30)³² and also diagnoses likely to be listed in the death certificate of people with DS, and the ICD-10 codes present in the trajectory network. These include Other hypothyroidism (ICD-10 code E03) and Congenital malformations of aortic and mitral valves (ICD-10

code Q23)^{33,34} (Fig. 2). Further, note the statistically significant pair from Dementia in Alzheimer's disease (ICD-10 code F00) to Death (introduced with code Y99, see Methods section).

Exploring disease trajectories of multifactorial diseases. Due to the marked demographic differences between phenotypes and degree of disease heterogeneity, appropriate search filters vary across DTB queries. For instance, proper use of the search filter functionalities is essential in collapsing the 8359 linear disease trajectories originating from an I10 search to a disease trajectory network. For demonstration purposes, we applied search filters for HT resulting in 2672 linear trajectories that were then collapsed into a disease trajectory network (Figs. 4 and 5).

In contrast to the network for DS, the network for HT mainly includes other, multifactorial, chronic diseases, e.g. heart failure (ICD-10 code I50), and other anaemias (ICD-10 code D64); chronic and unspecified kidney failure (ICD-10 codes N18 and N19; Fig. 6). The network topology also reflects this observation as I10 has both incoming and outgoing neighbourhood edges, collectively termed transition edges (Fig. 5). This finding is evidence that HT inherently is a heterogeneous phenotype that is associated with heterogeneous progression patterns^{35–37} agreeing with the fact that target pressure depends on comorbidities and that comorbidities may even be the treatment indication, per se^{38,39}. In addition, the relatively large proportion of linear trajectories length >3, indicates that the average age in this population is rather old and multimorbid. This is further evidence that the I10 population represents a health economic burden as there is a directional, statistically significant association

Fig. 3 Network view representation of the linear disease trajectories for Down Syndrome (Q90). Nodes represent ICD-10 codes and each colour corresponds to one of the 21 chapters in the ICD-10 index. Five chapters are excluded (for details, see Methods section). Arrows represent a statistically significant directionality between two diagnosis codes. Numbers describe how many patients follow the trajectories. If an edge is selected manually by clicking (red highlight) the statistical specifications will be displayed in the side panel. In the visualisation interface, selected nodes and edges may also be deleted (grouped or individually) by clicking on the icon “Delete edge”. A description of each variable can be retrieved by placing the cursor over the question marks. Search filter settings: all patients, length 3–5, relative risk (RR) 1.5–361, number of patients 21–114,099. ICD-10 International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision. Colours of nodes represent ICD-10 chapters.

between e.g. hypertension and heart failure, a rapidly growing public health issue^{18,40} (Fig. 6). Interestingly, no malignant disease (indexed in ICD-10 chapter II, Neoplasms) appear in the search on hypertension. This seems to agree with the conflicting literature on the association between cancer risk and hypertension⁴¹ but might as well relate back to a rather pragmatic index structure of the ICD-10 system⁴², as opposed to a network-based approach to human disease¹¹.

Browser search functionality and trajectory manipulation. DTB is disease-agnostic in the sense that any level 3 ICD-10 code or combination of ICD-10 codes (for details, see Methods section) can be selected as a search query and then interrogated for involvement in statistically significant disease trajectories.

DTB search results can be visualised in two formats depending on the Network view status (e.g. Figs. 2 and 3). When Network view is off, the browser will list the search result as linear disease trajectories and also report the total number of linear disease trajectories that matches the query (Figs. 2 and 4). When *Network view* is on, the search result will be displayed in a summarised, collapsed format. Every disease trajectory can be explored further by clicking on nodes (circles) or edges (arrows) that link to the WHO ICD-10 browser, Google Scholar and the Danish National Statistics Bureau in the browser side panel (Fig. 3). When a single node is selected the number of unique patients who are assigned the code within the registry period as well as the 5-year mortality are shown (Fig. 2). When an edge is selected, two different sets of summary statistics appear in the Information tab, depending on the network view selection (Figs. 3 and 4). If network view is on (e.g. Fig. 3), summary statistics for the length 2 disease trajectories, i.e., mean age at diagnosis of D1, time between

diagnoses and 5-year mortality are presented in the side panel. If network view is off users can also view summary statistics for length 2 disease trajectories and the entire disease trajectory of length up to 6 (Fig. 4).

Search-dependent data filtering and exploration. To focus search results, an array of search filters can be applied. Users can decide to search for disease trajectories that occur in the entire population or one of the two sexes, only. This can be selected in the side-panel drop-down menu, when the Information tab is selected. A more detailed search filtering is further obtained by adjusting three different parameters which are trajectory length, RR and number of patients. All search filters can be adjusted independently (Fig. 5). As mentioned above, DS (ICD-10 code Q90) is a rare condition typically diagnosed at birth. Consequently, the node for Q90 only has outgoing edges and relatively few people follow each trajectory (Fig. 3). Oppositely, a search for HT (ICD-10 code I10) that is often diagnosed in older, multi-morbid patients results in disease history reaching statistical significance (incoming edges) and many subsequent comorbidities (outgoing edges; Fig. 5).

Users can navigate the visualisation interface by applying tools from the toolbar to a specified part of the network or navigate manually with the cursor over the visualisation interface. Tools include selecting incoming or outgoing edges to a node of choice, Neighbourhood button (selecting all incoming and outgoing edges to a node of choice) and Select inverse button (selecting anything which is not selected at that moment). Users can also move and delete nodes as well as edges manually by clicking and dragging in the interface. Nodes and edges can be deleted either individually or grouped (Figs. 5 and 6). Multiple selection is

Fig. 4 Linear disease trajectories for essential (primary) hypertension (I10). When an edge is selected, users can explore characteristics for the entire trajectory and the individual trajectory edges separately. In this case, there are 56,251 patients who follow the trajectory I10 -> I50, 24,729 patients that follow the trajectory I10 -> N18 and 4241 patients who follow the trajectory I10 -> I50 -> N18 (visualisation interface). In the Information tab users can find information on the selected length 2 trajectory as well as the entire trajectory (side panel). If users select a different edge or search for I50 or N18, the browser allows to compare e.g. mean age at assignment of first trajectory across all statistically significant trajectories with $RR > 1$ in the entire population. Search filter settings: all patients, length 4–5, RR 1.15–361, number of patients 4000–114,099. I10: ICD-10 code for essential (primary) hypertension. I50: ICD-10 code for heart failure. N18: ICD-10 code for chronic kidney disease. ICD-10 International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision. Colours of nodes represent ICD-10 chapters.

obtained by dragging with the mouse cursor while holding down the control-key (Windows/Linux) or command-key (Mac). Undo and redo buttons are available in the toolbar for simple corrections. Users can zoom in and out; either via the toolbar zoom buttons or directly by scrolling with the mouse wheel or trackpad.

Disease trajectory analysis and data export. In addition to interactive data analyses and visualisations, DTB allows data exports and downloads via options in the side panel, Information tab (Fig. 3). If the Search tab is selected in the side panel, options for annotation of disease nodes and transition edges are available via the drop-down menus. Node annotation offers four options (ICD-10 code and description, ICD-10 code, Diagnosis code description and None), and Edge annotation offers three options (Number of patients, Relative risk, and No annotation; Fig. 5). Nodes remain constant irrespective of selection, whereas the edge will change thickness and shade of grey once an annotation is selected. The higher the annotation value (number of patients or relative risk) the thicker and darker the edge will be. Further exploration of disease trajectories is achieved by clicking on each transition edge in the network and selecting the Information tab in the browser side panel. The user will find the relative risk, P -values, number of patients, time between diagnoses, mean age at the trajectory inception, and 5-year mortality count at trajectory end. Moreover, users can also search for diagnosis pairs at Google Scholar via a direct link and choose to delete edges or nodes (Fig. 3).

To create an overview of the raw summary statistics data, data can be summarised in a tabular format by clicking View data table

in the side panel in the Information tab. All trajectories made with DTB can be downloaded in several formats for further data processing, analyses, and presentation of search results. Cytoscape JSON format exports are available for downloading⁴³. The Cytoscape files can be opened locally in the Cytoscape desktop application for rearranging or modifying the visualisation further. Export of search results as linear disease trajectories and disease trajectory networks is also possible in PNG format (with transparent background) or JPEG with white background. The raw comma-separated data values (CSV) are available for download for easy data import into Excel or data science programming applications.

Discussion

In a modern healthcare system, the value of examining disease associations at the population-level, in both chronic conditions (exemplified above) and acute, clinical conditions can only be underscored^{44,45}. Particularly, the development of computational methods for harmonising, analysing and visualising large, heterogeneous electronic health data sets is an integral part of modern medicine that is increasingly being shaped by precision medicine initiatives^{19,46–48}. To date the only large disease cohort visualisation tool made publicly available is the Comorbidity-viewer from Stockholm Electronic Patient Records (SEPR) originating from ~605,000 patients⁴⁹. However, the Comorbidity-viewer does only report disease co-occurrences, not progression patterns, and no disease trajectories or disease networks can be created. Researchers who have their own large patient registry cohorts can use existing software tools for computing comorbidity scores and analysing their own data. In contrast, DTB

Fig. 5 Disease trajectory network for essential (primary) hypertension (I10). When the search tab is selected in the side panel, users can perform advanced DTB queries by application of DTB functionality, comprised of a the drop-down menu (All patients, female patients only or male patients only), notches (trajectory length, relative risk and number of patients) or fields for typing the boundary values (relative risk and number of patients). Users can customise the layout of the search results by selecting annotation (type and font) and perform a local search by typing an ICD-10 code or a disease (bottom, left corner). Search filter setting: all patients, length 4-5, RR 1.15-361, number of patients 4000-114,099. DTB Danish Disease Trajectory Browser, ICD-10 International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision. Colours of nodes represent ICD-10 chapters.

provides useful clinical, temporal comorbidity analyses without requiring user-provided clinical data.

DTB aims to deliver easy access to a comprehensive population-wide data set of disease trajectories and comorbidities and is intended as a framework for studying disease progression patterns, where analyses with additional datatypes (e.g. socio-economic and molecular level data) can be incorporated. The browser can help researchers obtain an overview of the disease progression in a homogeneous, mostly Northern European population. Therefore, search results for diseases with a relatively low or high prevalence in Scandinavia will not necessarily replicate in other populations. Malaria represents one such example in effect of an endemic nature. Malaria is indeed included in the NPR registry, however with low incidence in Denmark. Our cut-offs have excluded malaria from the list of significant directional diagnosis pairs but DTB offers the possibility of inspecting the full list of pairs where malaria is included. The overview is summarised in statistical metrics, such as mean age at which the different trajectories started for the patients, the overall relative risk of getting one disease after the other and the 5-year mortality count for patients following specific trajectories. Such data can then be compared to statistics in other populations with akin gross domestic product (GDP), health care model, and geography or be used to characterise the degree of similarity between countries with different demographics⁵⁰. Importantly, search results from DTB can complement existing epidemiological methods by identifying sequential trends in disease progression patterns of up to six diseases.

It is evident, that diseases tend to display heterogeneity and manifest in different phenotypic contexts¹. The results from this study provide a framework for studying cases where the diagnosis pairs D1 -> D2 and D2 -> D3 are both statistically significant in terms of direction, even if quite few patients will follow both

pairs, but still share D2. A case like this highlights the heterogeneity within disease conditions, and points at D2 and its involvement in different disease courses. The browser functionality will allow users to identify such cases as counts are displayed for how many patients will follow D1 -> D2 -> D3, but also how many of the patients following D1 -> D2 would not follow D2 -> D3, in a longer trajectory (Fig. 4). This makes it possible to discover cases of intrinsic heterogeneity of diseases.

Many more generalised systems biology tools exist for visualising networks of biological data^{51,52}; however, these tools have a molecular focus and are not suited for large-scale disease trajectory analysis¹. Eventually, our tool can motivate data integration at the molecular and disease systems biology levels enabling researchers to further understand the underlying relationships between diseases⁵³. Researchers can use the browser to compare or verify trends in their own settings, make new discoveries and hypotheses on factors driving diseases, comorbidities, and their functional relationships.

The browser's disease database is coded in the ICD-10 system which is used by WHO and many healthcare systems world-wide. It therefore facilitates entry into the system for clinicians. In a clinical setting, disease trajectories may hint at a specific treatment strategy when a doctor cares for a patient, prescribes medicine or informs patients of possible future complications and diseases. DTB will allow anyone to do disease trajectory analyses in a real-world setting, without direct access to person-sensitive registry data and without requiring access to high performance computers.

Methods

Underlying comprehensive population-wide registry data. NPR contains data from all encounters at Danish hospitals, that be inpatient wards, outpatient clinics, and emergency room visits. As it has been mandatory for hospitals to report any

Fig. 6 Details relating to Fig. 5 where the Neighbourhood tool has been selected. When network view is on, users can customise the network display by applying different tools, e.g. Neighbourhood where all edges that link directly to a node are highlighted (red outline). In this case, I10 was selected and highlighted edges link to neighbour nodes. Other tools include Incoming edges, Outcoming edges and Select inverse. If the Select inverse functionality is activated after Neighbourhood, nodes and edges which are not neighbours will be highlighted. This is especially useful for deleting a section of the network, that users do not wish to export. Users can export the network that is displayed in the visualisation interface and may select parts manually by clicking on nodes and edges while holding down shift or dragging while holding down control (Windows/Linux) or command (Mac). I10 ICD-10 code for essential (primary) hypertension, ICD-10 International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision. Colours of nodes represent ICD-10 chapters.

type of contact (inpatient, outpatient, and emergency room visits) to the NPR for reimbursement purposes since 1994, the register is complete in nature and does not suffer from population bias²⁷, i.e., bias in terms of demography and areas of specialty is limited. NPR also holds data on place of residence (municipality), a patients' sex, hospital and ward, hospitalisation duration, date of death, etc.^{26,27}. The registry thus contains information at the level of individual patients that in relation to accuracy has been benchmarked extensively^{27,54}. For disease classification, NPR uses the WHO scheme ICD-10. The ICD-10 system has been used in Denmark since 1994, where it replaced the ICD-8 system (used in Denmark from 1977 to 1994). To incorporate death in the disease trajectory analysis we added the code, Y99, defined as death within 5 years of assignment of diagnosis D1 in the trajectory D1 → Y99. Data from The Danish Register of Causes of Death registry was used to compute the pairs needed to include mortality as a functionality in the browser²⁸. The temporal disease trajectories were then calculated from this data foundation following a two-step process.

Ethical approval. The study was approved by the Danish Data Protection Agency (ref: 2015-54-0939 and SUND-2017-57) and Danish Health Authority (ref: FSEID-00001627 and FSEID-00003092).

First step of the disease trajectory programme. The first step operates in a sequential manner by first identifying statistically significant diagnosis pairs (i.e. diseases that co-occur temporarily) and then selecting the diagnosis pairs with a significant directionality, which is defined as disease trajectories of length 2. The second step concatenates these pairs together to build disease trajectories of length >2 (Fig. 1). Computing all 3,155,952 possible disease pair permutations is too computationally demanding. Therefore, a pre-filtering step is applied. The pre-filtering step estimates the *P*-values for all possible diagnosis pairs within a 5-year time-window exploiting a single Bernoulli trial, that considers each sampling of a comparison discharge a Bernoulli trial. Using the probability distributions from these Bernoulli trials, 212,008 diagnosis pairs passed the pre-filtering step at level of significance $P < 1.21 \times 10^{-9}$ (Bonferroni corrected for multiple testing) ensuring model robustness³ (Fig. 1). For the diagnosis pairs (i.e. comprising diagnoses D1 and D2) that pass the pre-filtering step, patients are assigned diagnosis D1 are matched with $N = 10,000$ randomly selected individuals controlling for sex, age, discharge type and discharge week to limit any bias regarding seasonal disease trends. The RR is calculated as the ratio of D2 occurrences between the exposed population (C_{exposed}), patients who have been assigned diagnosis D1, and control

populations ($C_1 \dots C_N$) 10,000 random controls matched to each patient with diagnosis D1.

$$RR = \frac{C_{\text{exposed}}}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_i C_i} \quad (1)$$

P-values are estimated using a binomial distribution that models each single comparison of a disease pair with the cut-off threshold of 1.21×10^{-8} (Bonferroni corrected for multiple testing). For the diagnosis pairs that are statistically significant the directionality is computed. This procedure identifies the pairs, D1 → D2, where D1 occurs significantly more before D2 compared to the opposite direction using a binomial distribution. Only the diagnosis pairs with a significant directionality are retained for visualisation purposes (*P*-value < 0.05), whereas all significant diagnosis pairs with RR < 1 can be downloaded from the browser (Fig. 2 and Supplementary Data 1). To compute sex-specific disease trajectories, directional diagnosis pairs are also computed separately for male and female populations. Results from this analysis appears as a DTB functionality in the form of a search filter (Fig. 5).

Second step of the disease trajectory programme. In the second step, the algorithm builds the linear trajectories by concatenating statistically significant directional diagnosis pairs. For example, if D1 → D2 and D2 → D3 are significant directional diagnosis pairs, the pairs are fused into a disease trajectory of length three, i.e. D1 → D2 → D3. This principle can be re-applied to obtain longer trajectories. If the disease pair D3 → D4 also exists, the algorithm generates the trajectory D1 → D2 → D3 → D4. Patients follow the trajectories if the first occurrence of each of the diseases follows the specified trajectory. For example, one patient could be diagnosed with D1 → X → D2 → Y → D3 → Z and thereby follow the trajectory as all three diseases (D1, D2 and D3) are present in the specified order. A trajectory is included if a minimum of 20 patients follow D1 → D2 → D3 without skipping any of the diseases. This can be adjusted by application of the corresponding search filter.

Database creation. The DTB web application contains the resource of summarised trajectory data and is queried on the fly for making linear disease trajectories and disease trajectory networks. As of now, the database content is limited for use within the web application, but portions of the database can be exported for use locally in several different formats. Formats include CSV format, JSON either for importing visualisations into Cytoscape Desktop⁴³ or for use in scripts or

images files with white or transparent background (i.e. PNG or JPEG formats). Supplementary Data not used in the browser, with diagnosis pairs where $RR < 1$ can be downloaded from the side panel Information tab (Fig. 2).

The tool was developed with the use of the graph theory Javascript library called Cytoscape.js and implemented using the web development framework Angular v6 by Google, running on a Node.js backend server (see below).

DTB has information on all ICD-10 chapters but Certain conditions originating in the perinatal period (chapter XVI), Symptoms, signs & abnormal clinical & laboratory findings (chapter XVIII), Injury, poisoning & certain other consequences of external causes (chapter XIX), External causes of morbidity and mortality (chapter XX), and Factors influencing health status & contact with health services (chapter XXI). In the Information tab in the browser side panel, excluded chapters are grey (Fig. 6). The tool is released as a web application on the URL: <http://dtb.cpr.ku.dk> and gives access to an interactive interface for exploring, analysing and visualising the Danish National Patient Register cohort of 7.2 million patients recorded over almost 25 years.

Software: frameworks and libraries used. Cytoscape.js – graph frontend Javascript library.

Dagre.js – directed graph Javascript library.

Angular (frontend Javascript framework).

Node.js (Sails.js) – backend Javascript framework.

MongoDB (database software).

Data availability

Permission to access and analyse the underlying person-sensitive data can be obtained following approval from the Danish Data Protection Agency and the Danish Health Authority. A statistical summary for this article is available as a Supplementary Data 1. Due to privacy concerns, the browser and the provided Supplementary Data 1 only contain diagnosis and co-occurrence information when it has been assigned to at least five patients. All data made available are non-person-sensitive summary level data.

Code availability

To analyse the data the following software tools were used: R v. 3.4.0, Python v. 2.7, C++ v. 11 and Cytoscape Desktop v. 3.6.0. The key algorithm has been described in published literature (see refs. 3,14).

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Author contributions

T.S. and S.B. conceived the study. S.B. obtained the funding. T.S., R.R., I.F.J., A.D.H. and S.B. performed the literature search, figures, study design, programming and data analysis. T.S., R.R., I.F.J., A.D.H., M.L., A.A.-O., J.X.H., A.B.J., K.B. and S.B. contributed to

data interpretation. T.S., R.R., I.F.J., A.D.H. and S.B. wrote the initial draft, and M.L., A.A.-O., J.X.H., A.B.J., K.B. and S.B. contributed also to the final article.

Competing interests

S.B. reports ownerships in Intomics A/S, Hoba Therapeutics Aps, Novo Nordisk A/S, Lundbeck A/S and managing board memberships in Proscion A/S and Intomics A/S outside the submitted work.

Additional information

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Part III

APPENDICES

A | Appendix

Describing multi-morbidity using temporal disease trajectories

RR is a standard measure for the relationship between an exposure and an outcome happening at a later point in time[67]. RR expresses the strength of the association between an exposure and an outcome (Table 1).

Table A.1: 2x2-contingency tables: Risk (left) and classification performance (right)

		Outcome	
		+	-
Exposure	+	A	B
	-	C	D

		Condition	
		+	-
Prediction	+	True positive	False positive
	-	False negative	True negative

In the disease trajectory program RR measures the strength of the correlation between diagnoses D1 and D2. The RR is given by the number of patients who have been assigned diagnosis D1 and maximum five years after diagnosis D2 compared to the number matched controls with the diagnosis D2, who have not been assigned the diagnosis D1. To compute the RR the program first identifies all discharges in NPR with the diagnosis D1. This set was considered the exposure group. Next, a number of matched comparison groups are formed. The exposure and comparison group were matched by sex, age, type of contact and week of contact. RR is then calculated as the number of discharges where diagnosis D2 was assigned within five years in the exposed group relative to the that number in the comparison group.

Mathematically, RR for diagnostic co-occurrences is computed by the formula:

$$RR = \frac{C_{exposed}}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i C_i} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where RR is relative risk, $C_{exposed}$ is the exposed group, and C_i denotes one of the comparison groups. For each diagnosis pair (D1, D2) a total of 10 000 matched comparison groups were formed[71].

Figure A.1: Search specifications for a query performed at <http://dtb.cpr.ku.dk> that is included as figure 6 in section 3.2.

A model where multi-morbidity and text documents share properties

Computation of the maximum term frequency, inverse document frequency, and normalized term frequency introduced in section 3.3. The maximum term frequency (tf_{max}) is given by

$$tf_{max} = \max_{\tau \in d} tf_{\tau, d} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where τ ranges over all diagnoses assigned to the patient and d denotes the entire set of diagnoses codes assigned to the patient.

The inverse document frequency is then computed by

$$idf_t = \log \frac{N}{df_t} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where N is the number of documents (i.e. number of patients in the cohort) and df_t is the number

of patients with a the diagnosis for which the scaling factor is being calculated [78].

In addition, term frequencies were normalized to reduce the chances that diagnoses codes present many times simply because a certain patient has had many contacts would bias the result. Normalized term frequencies ($\text{ntf}_{t,d}$) were computed following the scheme

$$\text{ntf}_{t,d} = \alpha + (1 + \alpha) \frac{\text{tf}_{t,d}}{\text{tf}_{max}} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where α is a smoothing term between 0 and 1 which is generally set to 0.4, which it also was in the study presented in manuscript 2[78].

A temporal analysis of multi-morbidity in ischemic heart disease

Table A.2: Selected ICD-10 codes and their description

ICD-10 code	Description
E10	Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus
E11	Non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus
E66	Obesity and other hyperalimantation
E78	Disorders of lipoprotein metabolism and other lipidaemias
I10	Essential (primary) hypertension
I21	Acute myocardial infarction
I25	Chronic ischaemic heart disease

B | Appendix

Supplement: eAppendix

Manuscript title: Risk stratification of 72,249 patients with ischemic heart disease: a retrospective study linking prior multi-morbidity, biochemical data, and genetics

Authors: Haue AD, Holm PC, et al.

eMethods

Data preprocessing and application of the MCL algorithm

For the cluster analysis, only primary and secondary ICD-10-codes assigned before or at index were included; codes from chapters XV–XVII and XIX–XXII were removed (eTable 2). Prior to clustering, we sought to create a lower dimensional representation highlighting the distinct characteristics of the ICD-10 codes. In order to include information related to the hierarchical structure of the ICD-10 coding system in the vector representation, every code was split into four terms (a level 4 term, level 3 term, block, and chapter). For example, the ICD-10 code for acute myocardial infarction of anterior wall, I21.1 was split into I21.1 (level 4), I21 (level 3), R94 (block) and chapter IX (chapter). Lastly, after counting the different terms, any term present in less than 100 of the patients was removed and the remaining 5,764 terms were included in the analysis. Patients in the cohort were then represented as vectors comprised of integers indicating the number of times a patient had been assigned a particular term. For example, if a patient had been assigned the codes I21.0, E11.0 and I10.9 and been assigned all of them only once, then the patients will have a vector containing 1 in all the terms that these ICD-10 codes are split into except for chapter IX, as both I21.0 and I10.9 belongs to this chapter (eFigure 2).

By using a vector space approach that combines a term frequency-inverse document frequency (tf-idf) weighting scheme and the linear dimensionality reduction technique singular value decomposition, we condensed terms representing the 5,764 terms (derived from ICD-10 codes) to a vector representation with 50 topics^{1,2}.

For the tf-idf scaling, we used a maximum normalized term frequency weighting to dampen the effect of diagnosis codes that were often assigned to patients with long admission histories. Let the diagnostic admission history of each patient be denoted d and

$$tf_{\max} = \max_{\tau \in d} tf_{\tau,d}, \quad (1)$$

where τ ranges over all terms in d . Then, the normalized term frequency for each term t in the diagnostic admission history was computed as

$$ntf_{t,d} = \alpha + (1 - \alpha) \frac{tf_{t,d}}{tf_{\max}} \quad (2)$$

where α is a smoothing term in the range between 0 and 1 and is generally set to 0.4, which we also used in this study². Furthermore, a global weighting of the different terms was applied and given by the inverse diagnostic admission history frequency

$$\text{idf}_t = \log \frac{N}{\text{df}_t} \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of diagnostic admission histories (i.e., to the number of patients) and df_t is the number of diagnostic admission histories with a given term (e.g. number of patients with an ICD-10 code).

Combined, the final weighting is

$$\text{tf-idf}_{t,d} = \text{tf}_{t,d} \cdot \text{idf}_t \quad (4)$$

for the different terms in each diagnostic admission history.

After constructing the tf-idf matrix (containing one row per patient and one column per term), a lower rank approximation was created using the “truncatedSVD” implementation of SVD from the python package scikit-learn with 50 components, 10 iterations, and fixed random seed of 42 to ensure reproducible results³. After initial testing of the MCL algorithm, inflation parameters 1.3, 1.4, 1.5, 1.6, 1.7 and 1.8 were selected for further exploration corresponding to granularity level 1 through 6.

Sex-specific similarity networks were created using the “mxcarray” tool from the “mcl-edge” software collection⁴. To reduce the density of the networks, while still retaining an informative topology, all edges with an edge weight less than 0.3 were removed and the number of edges connected to each node were limited using the “#ceilnb” transformation from “mcl-edge”; a maximum of 9,000 was used for the male and 4,500 for the female network (eFigure 4). The weights of the remaining edges in the network were shifted such that the lowest weight was 0.0 as recommended in the mcl manual. The final pre-processed networks were then used as input for the “mcl” implementation of the MCL algorithm⁵. We used a pruning scheme of -P 10000 -S 1100 -R 1400 -pct 90 (default scheme 5), and a pre-inflation factor of 0.5 to make edge-weights more homogenous.

Preprocessing of biochemical and genetic data

The biochemical laboratory values from the EHR data were originally archived in the administrative biochemical databases Labka and BCC⁶. In relation to the EHR data used in this study, Labka covers the hospitals with SHAK codes 1301, 1309, 1330, 1351, 1401, 1501, 1516 and 4001 in the Capital Region of Denmark and BCC covers the hospitals with SHAK codes 2000 and 2501 in Region Zealand for the periods 2009-2016 and 2012-2016, respectively (eTable 1).

Biochemical laboratory tests were either classified in accordance with the Nomenclature, Properties and Units (NPU) or local systems⁷. Reference intervals were provided from the laboratories that analyzed the blood tests. Biochemical data was expected to be available for the patients where the index procedure was performed at a hospital located in either the Capital Region or Region Zealand at a time that was covered by the two databases.

A total of 48,957 patients (30,736 males and 18,221 females) were included from a hospital where biochemical data was available (67.8% of the entire cohort). As an indicator for data completeness and quality, the number of patients where available biochemical data at time of index agreed with the clinical standard of care was assessed. This implied that patients had sodium, potassium, hemoglobin and creatinine (or estimated glomerular filtration rate) measured maximum 90 days before or at the day of index. The 33,131 patients (20,788 males and 12,343 females) who fulfilled this requirement were included in the biochemical analysis (eTable 3). Finally, blood analytes that were measured for at least 50% of the 20,788 males and 12,343 females, respectively, were analyzed. In cases where patients had more than one test available in the period up from 90 days before to index, the test closest to index was available. As listed in the main text included samples were plasma levels of potassium, sodium, hemoglobin, estimated glomerular filtration (eGFR), creatinine, carbamide, glucose, troponin (I/T), HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, total cholesterol, leukocytes, C-reactive protein, lymphocytes, monocytes, neutrophils, basophilocytes, platelets, INR, alanine transaminase, albumin, alkaline phosphatase, bilirubin, and triglyceride. All analyses of biochemical data were performed in R 3.6.2 using the “ComplexHeatmap” and “circlize” packages.

Statistical analyses of clusters identified by the MCL algorithm

Autosomal genotype data from 188,462 individuals in the CHB-CVDC was filtered to only include variants present in the HapMap3 set of 1,120,696 reference variants¹¹. A total of 18,192 patients were included on the genetic analyses (eTable 4). In preparation for PGS calculations using the PGS

software LDpred2, genotype data were filtered to only include variants present in LDpred2's recommended set of 1,120,696 reference variants^{11,12}. The summary statistics were selected to only include European individuals and to have an adequately large sample size for the traits of interest. Variants present in both genotype and summary statistics data were then subjected to LDpred2's recommended standard deviation quality control. This recommended set is based on the reference set HapMap3 from the International HapMap project, which was established by genotyping 1.6 million single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in 1,184 individuals from 11 global populations¹³. Any missing genotype information was imputed to be the affected locus' reference allele. Any missing genotype information was conservatively imputed to be the affected locus' reference allele. We matched the remaining set of 978,246 genotyped variants with summary statistics data corresponding to six traits, obtained from five GWAS meta-analyses (immune-mediated inflammatory diseases, chronic kidney disease, stroke, atrial fibrillation, type 2 diabetes with and without adjustment for BMI)¹⁴⁻¹⁸. Variants present in both genotype and summary statistics data were then subject to LDpred2's recommended standard deviation quality control. After variant matching and quality control, a mean of 969,607 (S.D. 8,777) variants remained for subsequent per-chromosome risk score calculation for each of the six traits. We used the LDpred2-auto algorithm with 30 Gibbs sampling chains, 1,000 burn-in iterations and 500 iterations after burn-in. The initial values for the 30 sampling chains were a) the LDSC regression estimate for heritability h^2 (same for all chains); b) one of 30 initial values for the proportion of causal variants p , evenly spaced on a logarithmic scale from $10e^{-4}$ to 0.9.

Final per-chromosome effect sizes were calculated from each set of 30 sampling chains (per trait and chromosome) through a three-step process, which serves to ensure that the model (spanning 30 chains) converged: 1) computing the standard deviations of each chains' predicted scores, 2) keeping only the chains within three median absolute deviations from the median standard deviation, 3) averaging the effect sizes of the remaining chains. Across the 132 per-chromosome models (6 traits times 22 chromosomes), 26.89 chains were included in the final score on average. The lowest number of included chains was 18. Finally, the resulting per-chromosome risk scores were added together into genome-wide PGS. Survival analyses and phenotypic characterization were performed with R 3.6.2 using the "rms" package^{8,19}. The LDpred2 framework was implemented in R version 3.5.0 with the package bigsnpr (v1.5.2)^{8,20}.

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eTable 1: Eligible codes for inclusion and primary outcomes

ICD-10 ¹ chapter IX			Definition, level 3
Block	Level 3	Level 4	
R94	I20	I20.0*, I20.1, I20.8, I20.9	Angina pectoris
	I21*	I21.0, I21.1, I21.2, I21.3, I21.4, I21.9	Acute myocardial infarction
	I23	I25.0, I25.1, I25.2, I25.23, I25.4, I25.5, I25.6, I25.8, I25.9	Certain current complications following acute myocardial infarction
	I24	I24.0, I24.1, I24.8, I24.9	Certain current complications following acute myocardial infarction
	I25	I25.0, I25.1, I25.2, I25.23, I25.4, I25.5, I25.6, I25.8, I25.9	Chronic ischaemic heart disease
NomESCO² code		Procedure	
FNA*		Connection to coronary artery from internal mammary artery	
FNB*		Connection to coronary artery from gastroepiploic artery	
FNC*		Aorto-coronary venous bypass	
FND*		Aorto-coronary bypass using prosthetic graft	
FNE*		Coronary bypass using free arterial graft	
FNF*		Coronary thrombendarterectomy	
FNG*		Expansion and recanalisation of coronary artery	
SKS³ code		Procedure	
UXAC85[A-D]		Coronary arteriography	
UXCC00A		Coronary computed tomography angiography	
SHAK⁴ code		Hospital	
1301		Rigshospitalet	
1309		Bispebjerg og Frederiksberg Hospitaler	
1330		Amager og Hvidovre Hospital	
1351		Amager Hospital	
1401		Frederiksberg Hospital	
1501		Gentofte Hospital	
1502		Glostrup Hospital	
1516		Herlev og Gentofte Hospital	
2000		Hospitalerne i Nordsjælland	
2501		Amtssygehuset i Roskilde	
3800		Region Sjællands Sygehusvæsen	
4001		Bornholms Hospital	

¹ ICD-10 = WHO International classification of diseases and health related problems 10th edition. Danish version where code types A, B and G included in our definition of primary and secondary codes.

² NOMESCO = Nordic Medico-Statistical Committee

³ SKS = Sundhedsstyrelses klassifikationsystem [danish]

⁴ SHAK = Sygehus- og afdelingsklassifikation [danish]

* Included in primary outcome (secondary ischemic events). For ICD-10 codes only code types A (primary) and in-hospital patients.

eTable 2: ICD-10 chapters included in the cluster analysis

ICD-10 chapter	Definition	Number of patients with at least one code in chapter
I	Certain infectious and parasitic diseases	7,888
II	Neoplasms	14,481
III	Diseases of the blood and blood-forming organs and certain disorders involving the immune mechanism	3,566
IV	Endocrine, nutritional, and metabolic diseases	28,388
V	Mental and behavioural disorders	6,388
VI	Diseases of the nervous system	15,744
VII	Diseases of the eye and adnexa	15,744
VIII	Diseases of the ear and mastoid process	11,228
IX	Diseases of the circulatory system	72,211
X	Diseases of the respiratory system	17,273
XI	Diseases of the digestive system	24,958
XII	Diseases of the skin and subcutaneous tissue	9,591
XIII	Diseases of the musculoskeletal system and connective tissue	34,293
XIV	Diseases of the genitourinary system	20,303
XVIII	Symptoms, signs and abnormal clinical and laboratory findings, not elsewhere classified	36,102

eTable 3: Demographics for patients included in the biochemical analysis and NPU codes

Cohort demographics	Total	Males	Females	P-value⁵
Number of patients	33,131	20,788	12,343	
Mean age at index (SD)	64.4 (11.9)	63.4 (11.6)	66.2 (12.2)	2.2e ⁻¹⁶
Outcomes, number of cases	Total	Males	Females	P-value⁶
Secondary ischemic events	5,003	3,490	1,513	2.2e ⁻¹⁶
Death from non-IHD causes	3,518	2,194	1,324	
Censored	24,610	15,104	9,506	
Outcomes, time to event	Mean time to event in years (SD)			P-value¹
	Total	Males	Females	
Secondary ischemic events	2.25 (1.91)	2.27 (1.92)	2.21 (1.89)	0.096
Death from non-IHD causes	3.36 (1.80)	3.34 (1.81)	3.39 (1.80)	0.122
Censored	4.27 (1.12)	4.25 (1.15)	4.30 (1.11)	5.6e ⁻⁷
Total	3.72 (1.65)	3.67 (1.67)	3.81 (1.60)	2.2e ⁻¹⁶
Indicators for data quality and completeness				
Blood analyte	NPU codes and local systems			
Sodium	NPU03429, GEN00992, NPU03796, POC00022, 240, POC00021, POC00023, GEN00990			
Potassium	NPU03230, GEN00995, POC00019, POC00018, POC00020, GEN00993			
Hemoglobin	NPU02319, GEN00989, NPU02321, NPU02320, NPU02322, NPU17007, POC00013, NPU04208, NPU01393, POC00012, POC00014, NPU29057, GEN00987			
Creatinine / EGFR	NPU04998, NPU03918, NPU09102, NPU19661, NPU14048, NPU03800, HLL00037, DNK35131, POC00109, RHB00941, NPU28842			

⁵ Students T-test, two-sided

⁶ χ^2 -test, two-sided

eTable 4: Demographics for patients included in the genetic analyses

Cohort demographics	Total	Males	Females	P-value⁷
Number of patients	18,192	12,271	5,921	
Mean age at index (SD)	65.2 (11.6)	64,2 (11,2)	67,4 (11.9)	5.2e ⁻⁶⁶
Outcomes, number of cases	Count	Males	Females	P-value⁸
Secondary ischemic events	3,471	2,465	1,006	2.2e ⁻⁰⁶
Death from non-IHD causes	1,797	1,176	621	
Censored	12,924	8,630	4,294	
Outcomes, time to event	Mean time to event in years (SD)			P-value¹
	Total	Males	Females	
Secondary ischemic events	1.52 (1.43)	1.51 (1.43)	1.53 (1.43)	0.706
Death from non-IHD causes	2.28 (1.51)	2.26 (1.50)	2.34 (1.54)	0.289
Censored	4.47 (0.94)	4.45 (0.96)	4.50 (0.92)	3.9e ⁻⁰³
Total	3.69 (1.66)	3.65 (1.68)	3.77 (1.63)	4.7e ⁻⁰⁶

⁷ Students T-test, two-sided⁸ χ^2 -test, two-sided

eTable 5: Cox models using clusters as covariates for males and females at granularity level four.

cluster	event	HR	lower	upper	Pval	Pval_bonf	cluster	event	HR	lower	upper	Pval	Pval_bonf
4.M16	primary outcome	0.727	0.608	0.869	0.000	0.028	4.M28	secondary outcome	0.450	0.249	0.814	0.008	0.512
4.M09	primary outcome	0.753	0.659	0.861	0.000	0.002	4.M26	secondary outcome	0.534	0.340	0.839	0.007	0.403
4.M15	primary outcome	0.776	0.652	0.923	0.004	0.262	4.M15	secondary outcome	0.547	0.374	0.799	0.002	0.114
4.M18	primary outcome	0.794	0.664	0.950	0.012	0.731	4.M07	secondary outcome	0.587	0.484	0.712	0.000	0.000
4.M29	primary outcome	0.808	0.624	1.047	0.107	1.000	4.M09	secondary outcome	0.590	0.462	0.754	0.000	0.001
4.M23	primary outcome	0.809	0.667	0.982	0.032	1.000	4.M01	secondary outcome	0.627	0.555	0.709	0.000	0.000
4.M13	primary outcome	0.850	0.743	0.971	0.017	1.000	4.M13	secondary outcome	0.677	0.555	0.826	0.000	0.008
4.M21	primary outcome	0.885	0.741	1.057	0.179	1.000	4.M06	secondary outcome	0.685	0.555	0.845	0.000	0.026
4.M27	primary outcome	0.898	0.720	1.121	0.344	1.000	4.M18	secondary outcome	0.689	0.494	0.963	0.029	1.000
4.M12	primary outcome	0.899	0.788	1.026	0.114	1.000	4.M16	secondary outcome	0.704	0.530	0.937	0.016	1.000
4.M22	primary outcome	0.904	0.757	1.078	0.260	1.000	4.M24	secondary outcome	0.728	0.521	1.016	0.062	1.000
4.M24	primary outcome	0.921	0.753	1.126	0.421	1.000	4.M05	secondary outcome	0.742	0.607	0.906	0.003	0.212
4.M01	primary outcome	0.932	0.875	0.992	0.027	1.000	4.M14	secondary outcome	0.784	0.620	0.991	0.041	1.000
4.M07	primary outcome	0.938	0.841	1.045	0.245	1.000	4.M27	secondary outcome	0.810	0.558	1.176	0.268	1.000
4.M04	primary outcome	0.955	0.867	1.051	0.342	1.000	4.M25	secondary outcome	0.818	0.521	1.286	0.385	1.000
4.M11	primary outcome	0.968	0.856	1.094	0.600	1.000	4.M22	secondary outcome	0.890	0.705	1.124	0.327	1.000
4.M06	primary outcome	0.970	0.870	1.082	0.587	1.000	4.M11	secondary outcome	0.904	0.773	1.058	0.208	1.000
4.M30	primary outcome	0.991	0.762	1.290	0.949	1.000	4.M03	secondary outcome	0.933	0.829	1.049	0.245	1.000
4.M05	primary outcome	0.994	0.897	1.102	0.912	1.000	4.M21	secondary outcome	0.962	0.701	1.321	0.811	1.000
4.M28	primary outcome	1.008	0.811	1.254	0.940	1.000	4.M17	secondary outcome	0.976	0.767	1.242	0.846	1.000
4.M03	primary outcome	1.012	0.928	1.104	0.781	1.000	4.M30	secondary outcome	1.029	0.682	1.551	0.893	1.000
4.M14	primary outcome	1.058	0.930	1.204	0.390	1.000	4.M31	secondary outcome	1.162	0.642	2.100	0.620	1.000
4.M26	primary outcome	1.098	0.902	1.338	0.351	1.000	4.M12	secondary outcome	1.303	1.105	1.535	0.002	0.099
4.M31	primary outcome	1.101	0.769	1.576	0.600	1.000	4.M19	secondary outcome	1.331	1.092	1.623	0.005	0.288
4.M10	primary outcome	1.115	0.984	1.262	0.087	1.000	4.M29	secondary outcome	1.406	1.096	1.804	0.007	0.453
4.M08	primary outcome	1.124	1.011	1.250	0.031	1.000	4.M04	secondary outcome	1.512	1.348	1.695	0.000	0.000
4.M17	primary outcome	1.132	0.975	1.315	0.104	1.000	4.M23	secondary outcome	1.859	1.567	2.204	0.000	0.000
4.M19	primary outcome	1.281	1.111	1.476	0.001	0.039	4.M20	secondary outcome	2.403	2.048	2.819	0.000	0.000
4.M25	primary outcome	1.378	1.150	1.651	0.000	0.031	4.M02	secondary outcome	2.444	2.224	2.686	0.000	0.000
4.M02	primary outcome	1.507	1.404	1.618	0.000	0.000	4.M08	secondary outcome	3.102	2.806	3.429	0.000	0.000
4.M20	primary outcome	1.653	1.448	1.887	0.000	0.000	4.M10	secondary outcome	3.138	2.718	3.622	0.000	0.000

cluster	event	HR	lower	upper	Pval	Pval_bonf	cluster	event	HR	lower	upper	Pval	Pval_bonf
4.F20	primary outcome	0.635	0.450	0.895	0.010	0.496	4.F20	secondary outcome	0.402	0.209	0.775	0.006	0.337
4.F03	primary outcome	0.742	0.645	0.853	0.000	0.001	4.F03	secondary outcome	0.597	0.478	0.746	0.000	0.000
4.F01	primary outcome	0.744	0.657	0.843	0.000	0.000	4.F01	secondary outcome	0.459	0.370	0.568	0.000	0.000
4.F10	primary outcome	0.748	0.621	0.900	0.002	0.109	4.F10	secondary outcome	0.510	0.378	0.689	0.000	0.001
4.F18	primary outcome	0.761	0.575	1.006	0.055	1.000	4.F18	secondary outcome	0.915	0.645	1.299	0.619	1.000
4.F24	primary outcome	0.776	0.524	1.151	0.208	1.000	4.F24	secondary outcome	0.384	0.192	0.770	0.007	0.364
4.F15	primary outcome	0.816	0.654	1.019	0.073	1.000	4.F15	secondary outcome	0.947	0.738	1.215	0.666	1.000
4.F07	primary outcome	0.884	0.763	1.023	0.097	1.000	4.F07	secondary outcome	0.778	0.624	0.969	0.025	1.000
4.F08	primary outcome	0.910	0.785	1.055	0.210	1.000	4.F08	secondary outcome	1.015	0.858	1.201	0.861	1.000
4.F11	primary outcome	0.917	0.773	1.089	0.323	1.000	4.F11	secondary outcome	1.423	1.189	1.702	0.000	0.006
4.F09	primary outcome	0.948	0.802	1.120	0.531	1.000	4.F09	secondary outcome	0.793	0.615	1.023	0.074	1.000
4.F12	primary outcome	0.985	0.830	1.170	0.867	1.000	4.F12	secondary outcome	1.753	1.475	2.083	0.000	0.000
4.F17	primary outcome	0.994	0.789	1.251	0.957	1.000	4.F17	secondary outcome	0.591	0.392	0.893	0.012	0.646
4.F14	primary outcome	0.999	0.798	1.251	0.992	1.000	4.F14	secondary outcome	1.094	0.805	1.487	0.566	1.000
4.F23	primary outcome	1.004	0.687	1.468	0.982	1.000	4.F23	secondary outcome	0.714	0.356	1.430	0.342	1.000
4.F22	primary outcome	1.011	0.767	1.333	0.938	1.000	4.F22	secondary outcome	0.892	0.586	1.360	0.596	1.000
4.F05	primary outcome	1.078	0.956	1.215	0.223	1.000	4.F05	secondary outcome	0.897	0.766	1.051	0.179	1.000
4.F13	primary outcome	1.132	0.928	1.379	0.221	1.000	4.F13	secondary outcome	1.453	1.138	1.856	0.003	0.144
4.F25	primary outcome	1.185	0.786	1.785	0.418	1.000	4.F25	secondary outcome	0.740	0.352	1.555	0.427	1.000
4.F06	primary outcome	1.189	1.048	1.349	0.007	0.381	4.F06	secondary outcome	3.285	2.928	3.685	0.000	0.000
4.F04	primary outcome	1.232	1.102	1.376	0.000	0.013	4.F04	secondary outcome	0.781	0.649	0.939	0.008	0.439
4.F21	primary outcome	1.298	0.998	1.688	0.052	1.000	4.F21	secondary outcome	3.131	2.377	4.123	0.000	0.000
4.F19	primary outcome	1.299	1.042	1.619	0.020	1.000	4.F19	secondary outcome	1.505	1.135	1.995	0.004	0.233
4.F02	primary outcome	1.731	1.567	1.911	0.000	0.000	4.F02	secondary outcome	2.452	2.167	2.773	0.000	0.000
4.F16	primary outcome	1.764	1.482	2.100	0.000	0.000	4.F16	secondary outcome	2.557	2.113	3.094	0.000	0.000

Table 6a: Discrimination of clusters and co-morbidity indicis for males.

Cluster	Primary outcome			Secondary outcome		
	Cluster	Charlson	Elixhauser	Cluster	Charlson	Elixhauser
All	0.555	0.565	0.558	0.765	0.772	0.775
4.M16	0.543	0.620	0.540	0.750	0.763	0.744
4.M09	0.532	0.516	0.492	0.729	0.761	0.777
4.M15	0.516	0.519	0.529	0.758	0.748	0.736
4.M18	0.590	0.631	0.600	0.603	0.700	0.711
4.M29	0.514	0.493	0.541	0.686	0.723	0.731
4.M23	0.584	0.631	0.612	0.651	0.735	0.738
4.M13	0.552	0.506	0.526	0.813	0.810	0.812
4.M21	0.537	0.490	0.524	0.801	0.788	0.776
4.M27	0.526	0.478	0.463	0.656	0.745	0.693
4.M12	0.587	0.589	0.565	0.751	0.780	0.771
4.M22	0.565	0.522	0.506	0.790	0.812	0.805
4.M24	0.570	0.539	0.564	0.762	0.729	0.715
4.M01	0.527	0.537	0.550	0.701	0.705	0.704
4.M07	0.543	0.560	0.554	0.689	0.812	0.708
4.M04	0.540	0.592	0.590	0.642	0.740	0.673
4.M11	0.478	0.476	0.519	0.698	0.673	0.716
4.M06	0.541	0.551	0.552	0.776	0.794	0.801
4.M30	0.449	0.500	0.426	0.681	0.808	0.837
4.M05	0.496	0.563	0.558	0.665	0.690	0.695
4.M28	0.533	0.503	0.531	0.523	0.574	0.581
4.M03	0.549	0.565	0.562	0.731	0.768	0.756
4.M14	0.561	0.587	0.582	0.757	0.731	0.722
4.M26	0.559	0.572	0.536	0.716	0.723	0.739
4.M31	0.650	0.380	0.320	0.424	0.402	0.391
4.M10	0.533	0.508	0.501	0.650	0.753	0.776
4.M08	0.537	0.572	0.553	0.676	0.685	0.690
4.M17	0.586	0.630	0.602	0.680	0.769	0.776
4.M19	0.519	0.600	0.561	0.747	0.771	0.781
4.M25	0.459	0.479	0.478	0.657	0.702	0.723
4.M02	0.551	0.564	0.552	0.678	0.716	0.723
4.M20	0.555	0.549	0.564	0.662	0.688	0.702

eTable 6b: Discrimination of clusters and co-morbidity indicis for males.

Cluster	Primary outcome			Secondary outcome		
	Cluster	Charlson	Elixhauser	Cluster	Charlson	Elixhauser
All	0.609	0.605	0.594	0.764	0.777	0.771
4.F20	0.605	0.678	0.678	0.604	0.542	0.646
4.F03	0.576	0.547	0.552	0.778	0.827	0.808
4.F01	0.547	0.550	0.567	0.787	0.768	0.753
4.F10	0.488	0.463	0.506	0.757	0.725	0.733
4.F18	0.532	0.526	0.516	0.649	0.632	0.708
4.F24	0.707	0.629	0.680	0.656	0.771	0.777
4.F15	0.570	0.604	0.699	0.642	0.580	0.580
4.F07	0.592	0.582	0.578	0.736	0.781	0.759
4.F08	0.580	0.561	0.563	0.580	0.624	0.607
4.F11	0.659	0.663	0.641	0.665	0.715	0.694
4.F09	0.544	0.567	0.554	0.701	0.767	0.768
4.F12	0.657	0.663	0.635	0.603	0.675	0.640
4.F17	0.538	0.522	0.545	0.625	0.677	0.688
4.F14	0.471	0.397	0.415	0.683	0.727	0.729
4.F23	0.403	0.593	0.376	0.953	0.965	0.919
4.F22	0.658	0.603	0.551	0.728	0.782	0.706
4.F05	0.590	0.607	0.605	0.750	0.752	0.724
4.F13	0.581	0.621	0.552	0.762	0.768	0.794
4.F25	0.621	0.693	0.655	-	-	-
4.F06	0.587	0.603	0.583	0.660	0.741	0.738
4.F04	0.602	0.597	0.604	0.787	0.808	0.803
4.F21	0.561	0.619	0.577	0.828	0.804	0.808
4.F19	0.491	0.494	0.506	0.687	0.706	0.668
4.F02	0.572	0.618	0.585	0.687	0.742	0.744
4.F16	0.453	0.514	0.465	0.628	0.709	0.718

eTable 7a: Direction and P-value of significant PGS in male clusters.

Trait	ICD-10 code	Cluster	Effect direction	P-value (Bonf. adj.)
Atrial fibrillation	I46	4.M04	+	< 0.001
Chronic IHD	I25	4.M01	-	< 0.001
Chronic IHD	I25	4.M 11	+	0.006
LDL cholesterol	-	4.M01	+	0.002
Stroke	I64	4.M 12	-	0.005
Stroke	I64	4.M03	-	0.007
Total cholesterol	-	4.M01	+	< 0.001
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	E11	4.M02	+	< 0.001
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	E11	4.M 14	+	< 0.001
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	E11	4.M 23	-	0.001
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	E11	4.M07	-	0.009
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	E11	4.M04	-	0.024

eTable 7b: Direction and P-value of significant PGS in female clusters.

Trait	ICD-10 code	Cluster	Effect direction	P-value (Bonf. adj.)
Atrial fibrillation	I48	4.F11	+	< 0.001
Autoimmune disease	M35	4.F01	-	0.038
HDL cholesterol	-	4.F24	-	0.028
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	E11	4.F02	+	< 0.001
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	E11	4.F08	-	< 0.001
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	E11	4.F12	-	0.028

eTable 8: ICD-10 codes and descriptions identified in enrichment analysis.

ICD-10 code	Description
C50.9	Malignant neoplasm of breast, unspecified
C61	Malignant neoplasm of prostate
E10.9	Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus without complications
E11.9	Non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus without complications
F10.2	Mental and behavioural disorders due to use of alcohol: dependence syndrome
H36.0	Diabetic retinopathy
I20.1	Angina pectoris with documented spasm
I21	Acute myocardial infarction
I21.3	Acute transmural myocardial infarction of unspecified site
I30.9	Acute pericarditis, unspecified
I34.0	Mitral (valve) insufficiency
I48.1	Persistent atrial fibrillation
I48.2	Chronic atrial fibrillation
I50.1	Left ventricular failure
I63.9	Cerebral infarction, unspecified
I69.4	Sequelae of stroke, not specified as haemorrhage or infarction
I70.8	Atherosclerosis of other arteries
I73.0	Other peripheral vascular diseases
I73.9	Peripheral vascular disease, unspecified
J44.0	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute lower respiratory infection
J44.9	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, unspecified
M62.6	Muscle strain
M75.4	Impingement syndrome of shoulder

eFigure1: Classification of secondary ischemic events. A: Time from index to first revascularization vs. percentage of patients revascularized. Blue corresponds to events related to establishment of IHD. Red corresponds to events considered secondary ischemic events. B: Time from index to first hospitalization for acute myocardial infarction vs. percentage of patients hospitalized. Blue corresponds to events related to index. Red corresponds to events considered secondary ischemic events. C: Distribution of days between revascularization for patients subjected to >1 performed >24 hours apart. Revascularizations performed <2 weeks apart analyzed as one event performed at date of the earliest revascularization. Marked by dashed line. IHD = ischemic heart disease.

Term	x	x	E11.0	E11	R47	IV	x	x	I10.9	I10	R93	I21.0	I21	R94	IX	x	x
Patient	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	0	0

eFigure 2: Example of a patient specific vector. In this example the patient had been assigned the ICD-10 codes E11.0, I10.9 and I21.0 prior to or at establishment of IHD. ICD-10 codes were split into the terms written in the upper row. “x” indicates the terms before chapter IV, between chapter IV and IX, and after chapter IX. The values in the vector are represented in the second row. For this patient these values would be 0 as the patient has none of these codes in this example. Each “x” represents more than one term. In the actual data, the total length of the vector was 5,764 and vectors for males and female patients would be combined into two patient similarity networks, respectively.

eFigure 3: Limiting edge-density and average node degree in sex-specific similarity networks. A: Mean/median number of neighbors against edge-weight cutoff for male (upper) and female (lower) patient similarity network. B: Histogram showing distribution of edge-weights in the unpruned patient similarity network for male (upper) and female (lower) patient similarity networks. By only retaining edges with a weight higher than 0.3, the average node degree gets minimized and in turn leads to a more fine-grained clustering.

A

sex: M, inflation parameter: 1.6

B

sex: F, inflation parameter: 1.6

eFigure 4: Distribution of O/E-ratio per cluster at granularity level four. One boxplot per cluster for males (A) and females (B) displaying the distribution of O/E-ratios for level 4 ICD-10 codes assigned to more than 50 patients at granularity level four. Distinct number of codes: 260. X-axis: Clusters where “C” corresponds “4.M” and “4.F” in (A) and (B), respectively. Y-axis: logarithmic base 10 to the O/E-ratio. Dashed horizontal line with intercept at O/E-ratio = 2 marks enrichment. Solid horizontal line at with intercept at O/E-ratio marks extreme enrichment. O = Overserved. E = Expected.

A

eFigure 6: Hierarchical clustering for assessment of cluster similarity according to biochemical data. Heatmaps show clusters at granularity level four against blood test analytes for males (A) and females (B). Analyses based on the proportion of patients in a cluster with an abnormal blood test up to 90 days before index. Horizontal split of heatmaps according to results of hierarchical clustering. Color bar on the right according to the proportion of patients in a cluster with at least one blood test out of reference (i.e., abnormal). A total of 20,788 males and 12,343 females were included in the analyses.

C | Appendix

Supplementary materials

Polypharmacy and drug dosage modifications:

A longitudinal analysis of 3.5 million electronic health records

Leal Rodríguez, Cristina et al.

This document contains all supplementary tables and figures for the above-mentioned paper.

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Figures

Supplementary figure 1. Polypharmacy and age

Age distribution based on the number of concomitant drugs (1, 2-4, 5-9, ≥ 10). Pearson $\rho: 0.40$, 95% confidence interval CI: 0.39-0.40, p-value $< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$. CI=Confidence Interval.

Supplementary figure 2. Flowchart

Flowchart for the reduction of the initial 1,539 drugs that were prescribed during the study period to 413 drugs fulfilling the selection criteria.

Supplementary figure 3. Characterisation of dosage patterns and co-medications

Stacked barplots representing the proportion of co-medications correlated with co-medications for each index drug. The index drugs with the highest proportion of co-medications with ORs >1 were: piperacillin (J01CR05), cefuroxime (J01DC02), caffeine (N06BC01), insulin glargine (A10AE04), methotrexate (L01BA01) and atorvastatin (C10AA05), consisting of more than 18% of all their co-medications. OR=Odds Ratio.

Supplementary figure 5. Comparison between patient volume, DDI evidence and dosage adjustments

a Boxplots indicating the number of patients and the DDI evidence among co-medication pairs with ORs >1 (Two-sample Mann-Whitney U-test, p-value = 6.28×10^{-18}); **b** Boxplots of the number of publications where co-medication pairs appeared co-mentioned (Two-sample Mann-Whitney U-test, p-value = 1.52×10^{-14}); **c** Boxplots of the odds ratio for dosage (Two-sample Mann-Whitney U-test, p-value = 2.44×10^{-19}). OR=Odds Ratio.

Supplementary figure 6. Comparison between dosage adjustments and DDI evidence

Boxplots indicating the odds ratio (OR) and the DDI evidence among co-medication pairs with ORs >1 across the different index therapeutic drug classes. Two-sample Mann-Whitney U-test, where *: p-value ≤ 0.05 , **: p-value ≤ 0.01 , ***: p-value ≤ 0.001 , ****: p-value ≤ 0.0001 . Therapeutic groups with less than five observations for each DDI class (DDI/Unknown DDI) are not shown.

Supplementary figure 7. Comparison between patient volume and DDI evidence

Boxplots indicating the prevalence (number of patients) and the DDI evidence among co-medication pairs with ORs >1 across the different index therapeutic drug classes. Two-sample Mann-Whitney U-test, where *: p-value ≤ 0.05, **: p-value ≤ 0.01, ***: p-value ≤ 0.001, ****: p-value ≤ 0.0001. Therapeutic groups with less than five observations for each DDI class (DDI/Unknown DDI) are not shown. OR=Odds Ratio.

Supplementary figure 8. Comparison between literature and DDI evidence

Boxplots indicating the number of publications with co-mentioning and the DDI evidence among co-medication pairs with ORs >1 across the different index therapeutic drug classes. Two-sample Mann-Whitney U-test, where *: p-value ≤ 0.05 , **: p-value ≤ 0.01 , ***: p-value ≤ 0.001 , ****: p-value ≤ 0.0001 . Therapeutic groups with less than five observations for each DDI class (DDI/Unknown DDI) are not shown. OR=Odds Ratio.

Supplementary figure 9. Average daily dose

a Acyclovir (J05AB01)

Interval	Frequency	Dose	ATC code	Name	Start	End
1 00:00	8:00, 14:00, 22:00	200 mg	J05AB01	Acyclovir	04-10-2012	05-04-20

b Levothyroxine sodium (H03AA01)

Interval	Frequency	Dose	ATC code	Name	Start	End
7 00:00	Day 1 8:00 Day 3 8:00 Day 5 8:00	50 mcg	H03AA01	Levothyroxine sodium	08-12-2013	28-12-2013
7 00:00	Day 0 8:00 Day 2 8:00 Day 4 8:00 Day 6 8:00	100 mcg	H03AA01	Levothyroxine sodium	08-12-2013	28-12-2013

J Antiinfectives For Systemic Use
H Systemic Hormonal Preparations

Calculation of prescribed dosage as the prescribed average daily dose (ADD). A prescription is a health-care program implemented by a physician or other qualified health care practitioner in the form of instructions that govern the plan of care for an individual patient. The term often refers to a health care provider's written authorization for a patient to purchase a prescription drug from a pharmacist. Prescriptions can be classified into four different groups: (1) **one-time prescriptions**; (2) **scheduled prescriptions**; (3) **Pro Necessitata (PN)** or 'as needed' prescriptions; and (4) **Variable dosage (VAO)** prescriptions. One-time prescriptions consist on the administration of a single dose in a single day. As this type of prescriptions do not allow the possibility to study longitudinal dosage adjustments, we did not consider them for this study. PN consist of drugs only administered if needed and they are indicated with a maximum number of administrations/day that can be taken. An example of a PN prescription is the painkiller paracetamol or other analgesics indicated for the treatment of pain if the patient requires so after e.g. surgery. VAO drugs refer to drugs whose dosage is variable on a biochemical value or another physiological constant of the patient at the time of each administration. For example, this is the case for insulin, whose dosage depends on the blood glucose levels. For PN and VAO drug prescriptions, the ADD was coded categorically as 'PN' or 'VAO'. Henceforth, quantitative ADD was calculated only for scheduled prescription types. Scheduled prescriptions consist of drug indications having an interval or cycle with a defined time pattern for each administration. Among this type, we can find many variations with different intervals and patterns. The figures **a** and **b** exemplify two different examples: **a** Dosing regimen for acyclovir (J05AB01), a drug used to treat infections caused by certain types of viruses (e.g. cold sores, shingles, chickenpox). The prescription regimen is indicated with a daily interval (1 day), a frequency of three administrations following the time pattern at 8 am, 2 pm and 10 pm. The prescribed dose

indicated at each administration is of 200 mg. The final calculated ADD for acyclovir is of 600 mg (**see Equation 1**). **b** A more complex regimen is presented with the medication Levothyroxine sodium (H03AA01), a thyroid hormone medication that is used to treat hypothyroidism and other hormonal conditions. The treatment plan for this drug follows a weekly interval (7 days) and different prescribed doses for every other day. The prescribed dose is 50 micrograms (mcg) for days 1,3,5 and 100 mcg for days 0,2,4,6. The final calculated ADD is 78.57 mcg, which is the sum of the two previous prescribed doses in the same weekly interval.

Supplementary figure 10. Treatment episodes

Construction of concomitant and monotherapy treatment episodes. Patients can have a drug prescribed multiple times during an admission. We constructed concomitant treatment episodes as the intervals of time when two different drug prescriptions were contemporaneously active. Monotherapy treatment episodes were used as the reference treatment episodes as the intervals of time when a drug was not concomitantly given with any other drug.

Supplementary figure 11. Literature co-mentions diagram

Diagram of the full-text article and abstract corpus generation for the text mining of drug-drug interactions. DTU DTM Corpus (~15 million articles), PubMed (~27 million articles) and MEDLINE were used for the collection of full-text articles and abstracts.

Tables

Supplementary table 1: Admission primary diagnosis

ICD-10 chapter	Chapter name	No. unique drugs, median (IQR)
1	Certain infectious and parasitic diseases	8 (4-14)
2	Neoplasms	8 (5-12)
3	Diseases of the blood and blood forming organs and certain disorders involving the immune mechanism	7 (4-11)
4	Endocrine, nutritional and metabolic diseases	8 (4-12)
5	Mental and behavioural disorders	6 (4-9)
6	Diseases of the nervous system	5 (3-9)
7	Diseases of the eye and adnexa	4 (2-7)
8	Diseases of the ear and mastoid process	3 (2-5)
9	Diseases of the circulatory system	8 (4-12)
10	Diseases of the respiratory system	8 (4-13)
11	Diseases of the digestive system	6 (4-10)
12	Diseases of the skin and subcutaneous tissue	4 (2-9)
13	Diseases of the musculoskeletal system and connective tissue	8 (4-11)
14	Diseases of the genitourinary system	6 (3-10)
15	Pregnancy, childbirth and the puerperium	3 (2-5)
16	Certain conditions originating in the perinatal period	2 (1-5)
17	Congenital malformations, deformations and chromosomal abnormalities	4 (2-7)
18	Symptoms, signs and abnormal clinical and laboratory findings, not elsewhere classified	5 (2-9)
19	Injury, poisoning and certain other consequences of external causes	7 (3-12)
20	External causes of morbidity and mortality	5 (3-9)
21	Factors influencing health status and contact with health services	5 (1-9)

Supplementary table 2: Co-medication pairs with associated dosage adjustment

List of co-medication pairs with ORs >1 for dosage adjustment. OR=Odds Ratio.

Supplementary table 3: DDI evidence

List of co-medication pairs with ORs >1 for dosage adjustment and their DDI evidence. OR=Odds Ratio.

Supplementary table 4: Shared CYPs and transporters

List of co-medication pairs with ORs >1 for dosage adjustment and their pharmacokinetic activities: shared metabolism and transport, and associated variants. OR=Odds Ratio.

Supplementary table 5: Literature co-mentions

List of co-medication pairs with ORs >1 for dosage adjustment, DDI evidence and co-mentioning in the literature. OR=Odds Ratio.

Supplementary table 6: One-time drugs

List of excluded index drugs for which the prescription type was 'one-time' or 'single-administration' in more than 70% of the cases.

D | Appendix

Optimizing drug selection from a prescription trajectory of one patient

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Supplementary material

Supplementary figure 1 | Prescriptions redeemed at all Danish pharmacies in the period 1995-2019 stratified by the 14 anatomical ATC groups for males (left) and females (right) and by year of redemption. ATC main group prescription redemption separated for each year and sex in the study (period 1995-2019). It shows the proportion of different ATC groups by age (x-axis) for each year in the study period and separated for males and females.
*Refer to Figure 1 for ATC group legend.

Supplementary figure 2 | Counts of prescriptions redeemed at all Danish pharmacies in the period 1995-2019 stratified by the 14 anatomical ATC groups for males (left) and

females (right) and by year of redemption. ATC main group prescription redemption separated for each year and sex in the study (period 1995-2019). It depicts the number of patients per 1,000 patients redeeming each ATC main group at different ages (x-axis) for each year in the study period and separated for males and females. *Refer to Figure 1 for ATC group legend.

Supplementary figure 3 | Cohort description and workflow of drug pair inclusion. a, drug pair inclusion flow chart. **b,** seasonal graph for each ATC class, where prescription redemption per 1,000 patients displays seasonal patterns. **c,** Lexis diagram representing the population used in this study, including all the patients alive in the period 1995-2019, from the age 0 to 100. **d,** death ratio between male (up) and female (down) across all ages. Ratio is based on prescription redemption by each sex at each age separated by ATC class. Refer to Figure 1 for ATC class legend. *Refer to Figure 1 for ATC group legend.

a**b**

Number of patients with more than one antihypertensive

Supplementary figure 4 | Longitudinal trajectories formed by the same ATC group. a, trajectories formed by drugs from the same anatomical ATC group were included and then horizontally separated by average time between prescription redemptions. Each group of trajectories contains edges that separate the different prescription redemptions, whose height represent the number of trajectories that go from length 2 to length 3, to length N. Each group of trajectories is ordered from shortest to longest (top to bottom). *Refer to Figure 1 for ATC group legend. **b,** Number of individuals redeeming the subgroup indicated on the left side (node size) and how many of these patients redeem another drug used in hypertension (C02, C03, C07, C08, C09) posteriorly (ordered by chemical subgroup in ATC).

Patient group change over time for Poisson model inclusion/exclusion

Year birth	Sex	time	P ₀₀	P ₁₀	P ₀₂	P ₁₂
1991	F	t ₁	5	4	3	5
1991	F	t ₂	4	4	5	5
1991	F	t ₃	4	5	4	3
1991	F	t _n	4	3	1	3

Supplementary figure 5 | Individual grouping for Poisson modelling change over time.

Each group of individuals, separated by sex and year of birth are dynamically allocated to different groups at each time point, depending on their prescription redemption at the time. That process is repeated for each stratum of the data (i.e., for each sex, year of birth and time of prescription), for each drug pair. As an example, women born in 1991 are used in the figure. They enter the study in 1995 (t₁) for prescription redemption pair (P₁→P₂). Some of these individuals redeemed both prescriptions at t₁, so they are directly counted in P₁₂ (P₁₂ = has redeemed P₁ and P₂; P₁₀ = has redeemed P₁ but not P₂; P₀₂ = has redeemed P₂ but not P₁; P₀₀ = has redeemed neither P₁, nor P₂). This individual is then censored from the rest of the years in the model. Other individuals in the same stratum at t₁ will not have redeemed any of the drugs in the pairs under study, P₁ or P₂, hence they will be counted as P₀₀. At each time, the position of the different individuals might change, as they might have redeemed one or both prescriptions, or they might have left the study (emigration or death).

Supplementary figure 6 | Period of inclusion, 1995-2019, for Cox proportional hazard regression model cohort. Individuals who redeemed the prescription before 1995 are excluded from the cohort (left-truncated) and patients who leave the study, either due to end of window of study (2019), emigration or other are censored (right censored). The timeframe is the period for which prescription registry has information (1995-2019), leaving those patients who redeemed the prescription before the beginning of the registry truncated out of the model (Supplementary Fig. 2). Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI)²⁰ was calculated using the ICD-10 coded disease data from the Danish National Patient Registry. Age, sex and CCI were added as covariates in the model and an interaction with them was included if the hazard proportionality assumption was violated – using a test based on Schoenfeld residuals with a p-value lower than 0.0001.

Supplementary table 1 | Cohort characteristics.

	Male	Female
Number of patients (%)	3 586 032 (49 %)	3 669 887 (51%)
Median age 1995, years	30	30
Mean age 1995, years	31.2	32.9
Range age 1995, years	0-106	0-110
Median age 2019, years	44	47
Mean age 2019, years	43.9	47.1
Range age 2019, years	0-110	0-110
Prescription redemption		
Median	11	17
Mean	13.9	19.1
SD	10.7	13.4
Range	1-164	1-129

Supplementary table 2 | Prescription distribution over the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification System.

Age	Male					Female				
	0-14	15-44	45-64	65-84	>85	0-14	15-44	45-64	65-84	>85
ATC mean (SD)										
A	1.3 (0.6)	1.7 (1.1)	2.1 (1.7)	2.5 (1.9)	2.3 (1.6)	1.3 (0.6)	2.0 (1.4)	2.3 (1.8)	2.9 (2.1)	2.7 (1.7)
B	1.0 (0.3)	1.1 (0.4)	1.2 (0.5)	1.4 (0.7)	1.4 (0.6)	1.0 (0.2)	1.2 (0.5)	1.2 (0.5)	1.4 (0.7)	1.4 (0.6)
C	1.3 (0.7)	1.5 (1.1)	2.8 (2.1)	3.2 (2.2)	2.2 (1.5)	1.3 (0.7)	1.5 (1.0)	2.6 (1.9)	3.2 (2.3)	2.4 (1.6)
D	1.9 (1.3)	2.3 (1.7)	2.2 (1.6)	2.2 (1.6)	1.9 (1.3)	2.0 (1.3)	2.7 (2.0)	2.3 (1.6)	2.3 (1.6)	1.9 (1.3)
G	1.0 (0.2)	1.1 (0.3)	1.2 (0.5)	1.4 (0.6)	1.2 (0.5)	1.1 (0.3)	2.1 (1.3)	1.7 (1.0)	1.4 (0.7)	1.2 (0.5)
H	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.2)	1.0 (0.2)	1.1 (0.3)	1.0 (0.2)	1.0 (0.2)	1.1 (0.4)	1.1 (0.4)	1.1 (0.4)	1.0 (0.3)
J	1.0 (1.0)	2.2 (1.3)	2.1 (1.4)	2.5 (1.6)	2.2 (1.4)	1.9 (0.2)	3.3 (1.9)	2.6 (1.7)	2.7 (1.8)	2.4 (1.6)
L	1.1 (0.3)	1.1 (0.3)	1.1 (0.3)	1.1 (0.3)	1.0 (1.8)	1.1 (0.2)	1.0 (0.2)	1.1 (0.3)	1.0 (0.2)	1.0 (0.2)
M	1.1 (0.3)	1.5 (0.7)	1.7 (0.9)	1.7 (0.9)	1.4 (0.7)	1.1 (0.3)	1.6 (0.9)	1.8 (1.1)	1.9 (1.2)	1.5 (0.8)
N	1.3 (0.8)	2.5 (2.3)	2.7 (2.3)	3.0 (2.3)	2.8 (1.9)	1.3 (0.8)	2.7 (2.4)	3.0 (2.5)	3.4 (2.5)	3.1 (2.1)
P	1.0 (0.2)	1.2 (0.5)	1.1 (0.4)	1.1 (0.3)	1.0 (0.2)	1.0 (0.2)	1.3 (0.5)	1.2 (0.5)	1.1 (0.3)	1.0 (0.2)
R	2.0 (1.3)	2.0 (1.3)	1.9 (1.3)	2.2 (1.7)	1.7 (1.1)	1.8 (1.2)	2.4 (1.7)	2.2 (1.7)	2.3 (1.8)	1.7 (1.5)
S	1.5 (0.8)	1.6 (1.0)	1.7 (1.1)	2.1 (1.5)	1.7 (1.1)	1.4 (0.8)	1.7 (1.0)	1.8 (1.3)	2.2 (1.6)	1.9 (1.3)
V	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.2)	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.1)	1.0 (0.1)
Range										
A	1-13	1-23	1-21	1-21	1-14	1-18	1-23	1-22	1-21	1-18
B	1-6	1-7	1-7	1-7	1-6	1-6	1-8	1-8	1-8	1-6
C	1-9	1-19	1-20	1-21	1-15	1-9	1-18	1-20	1-21	1-15
D	1-16	1-21	1-21	1-19	1-15	1-18	1-21	1-19	1-18	1-15
G	1-4	1-7	1-11	1-7	1-5	1-5	1-14	1-11	1-9	1-7
H	1-4	1-5	1-5	1-5	1-4	1-5	1-7	1-6	1-5	1-4
J	1-17	1-20	1-16	1-14	1-11	1-17	1-21	1-16	1-15	1-13
L	1-4	1-5	1-6	1-5	1-3	1-5	1-5	1-5	1-5	1-4
M	1-6	1-9	1-11	1-10	1-7	1-6	1-10	1-11	1-11	1-9
N	1-19	1-33	1-34	1-27	1-18	1-14	1-36	1-30	1-28	1-19
P	1-5	1-6	1-7	1-5	1-3	1-5	1-7	1-6	1-5	1-4
R	1-14	1-17	1-17	1-17	1-13	1-14	1-19	1-19	1-18	1-13
S	1-13	1-16	1-16	1-17	1-13	1-13	1-17	1-16	1-15	1-14
V	1-2	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-2	1-2	1-3	1-3	1-2	1-2

Supplementary table 3 | Relative risk for pairs in figure 2

ATC 1	ATC 12	Number patients	RR	95% CI	P-value
No2AA	No2AB	138 110	2.76	2.74 - 4.13	2.70e-08
Ro3CC	Ro3BA	226 898	2.72	1.86 - 3.99	2.68e-07
CogAA	CogBA	164 680	2.79	1.93 - 4.03	5.22e-08
C07AB	B01AA	125 137	3.17	2.17 - 4.63	2.72e-09
C07AB	C01AA	103 043	3.55	2.31 - 5.47	9.07e-09
A03FA	No2AB	102 783	2.77	1.89 - 4.05	1.42e-07
No6AB	No5AF	116 605	2.86	2.02 - 4.0	4.11e-09
B01AC	C01AA	135 262	2.88	1.89 - 4.38	8.06e-07
No5BA	No2AG	118 223	2.83	2.09 - 3.83	1.83e-11
CogAA	C01DA	137 306	3.14	2.1 - 4.62	8.19e-09
J01CE	D07BB	195 989	2.81	2.19 - 3.61	5.51e-16
M01AB	No2AG	118 272	2.80	2.0 - 3.76	5.61e-12
M01AC	M01AB	121 302	2.73	2.08 - 3.58	3.70e-13
G03AA	J01EB	391 118	3.05	1.93 - 4.82	1.87e-06
J01EB	G01AF	189 887	3.28	2.33 - 4.63	1.19e-11
A02BA	No5BA	138 066	2.89	2.18 - 3.83	1.16e-13
M01AX	C09AA	105 249	2.88	2.06 - 4.04	8.30e-10
C10AA	C03CA	218 656	2.74	1.94 - 3.87	1.17e-08
G03AA	G01AF	279 484	3.98	2.42 - 6.55	5.27e-08
A02BA	A03FA	149 396	2.74	2.06 - 3.64	4.28e-12
D07BB	J01FA	131 233	3.13	2.42 - 4.04	1.93e-18
C10AA	A12BA	232 191	2.85	1.98 - 4.10	1.74e-08
S01GA	Ro6AE	113 185	2.74	2.07 - 3.61	1.27e-12
G03AA	Do6BB	129 086	3.12	2.00 - 4.86	5.17e-07

M01AX	B01AC	113 398	2.98	2.11 - 4.21	5.70e-10
S01GA	S01GX	125 768	2.75	2.06 - 3.68	1.01e-11
C07AB	C03DA	121 672	2.90	1.99 - 4.23	3.44e-08
D07BB	D07AC	112 418	3.43	2.59 - 4.54	7.00e-18
A08AA	M01AB	185 846	2.97	2.28 - 3.87	7.04e-16
A02BA	Ro5FA	126 611	2.87	2.16 - 3.81	3.85e-13
G03AA	J02AC	414 591	2.82	1.76 - 4.53	1.66e-05
D07BB	S01AA	123 584	2.78	2.14 - 3.62	2.15e-14
M01AX	C08CA	111 180	2.95	2.07 - 4.20	2.48e-09
D07BB	D07AB	111 589	3.33	2.50 - 4.45	3.02e-16
D07BB	Do1AC	120 234	3.26	2.47 - 4.29	4.61e-17
M01AX	C03CA	102 801	3.10	2.17 - 4.42	4.24e-10
C03AB	Ro5CB	102 408	2.78	1.92 - 4.03	5.53e-08
D07BB	A10BK	3 349	0.002	1.20e-03 - 3.15e-03	4.44e-142
D07CB	A10BK	1 538	2.27e-03	1.24e-03 - 4.17e-03	2.46e-86
M03BA	A10BK	1 264	2.32e-03	1.24e-03 - 4.35e-03	3.30e-80
S03BA	B01AF	1 505	3.24e-03	1.80e-03 - 5.82e-03	8.93e-82
S03BA	No5CH	1 789	3.25e-03	2.04e-03 - 5.19e-03	1.03e-127
G03CB	B01AF	6 461	3.39e-03	1.74e-03 - 6.62e-03	2.50e-62
S03BA	No5CH	1 789	3.25e-03	2.04e-03 - 5.19e-03	1.03e-127
G03CB	B01AF	6 461	3.39e-03	1.74e-03 - 6.62e-03	2.50e-62
G03CB	No5CH	6 023	3.71e-03	1.91e-03 - 7.18e-03	9.73e-62
C03CB	A10BH	449	6.49e-01	2.74e-01 - 1.53	3.24e-01
G03CB	Ro2AX	1 121	4.01e-03	2.02e-03 - 7.94e-03	2.24e-56
B01AF	No6DX	1 344	4.15e-01	3.74e-01 - 4.60e-01	1.38e-62
A11EA	G03FA	1 009	1.06e+01	8.51 - 13.1	6.12e-102
G01AG	S01CA	1 696	1.06e+01	7.10 - 15.7	3.04e-31
B03AE	A06AD	1 503	1.06e+01	6.51 - 17.1	1.40e-21

So1KA	Mo1AH	1 012	1.08e+01	7.57 - 15.4	1.49e-39
A11EA	Go4CA	1 052	1.09e+01	8.58 - 14.0	3.49e-82
A11EA	Go3CB	1 030	1.10e+01	9.47 - 12.8	8.01e-217
So1KA	Ao2AA	1 081	1.12e+01	7.81 - 16.0	7.48e-40
So1KA	Ao6AD	1 745	1.15e+01	7.85 - 16.7	1.40e-36
A10BB	No2BE	97 371	1.60e+03	1.52e+03 - 1.68e+03	2.22e-308
A10BF	No2BE	3 717	1.66e+03	1.61e+03 - 1.72e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No2AX	68 483	1.67e+03	1.61e+03 - 1.75e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No3AF	4 148	1.70e+03	1.65e+03 - 1.75e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No2AJ	22 433	1.72e+03	1.67e+03 - 1.77e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No3AA	1 403	1.74e+03	1.68e+03 - 1.80e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No2AA	52 922	1.74e+03	1.68e+03 - 1.81e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No3AG	2 891	1.75e+03	1.69e+03 - 1.80e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No2AG	14 877	1.76e+03	1.67e+03 - 1.85e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No2AE	12 015	1.79e+03	1.72e+03 - 1.87e+03	2.22e-308
A10BB	No2AB	17 553	1.79e+03	1.71e+03 - 1.88e+03	2.22e-308
A10BF	No3AX	1 178	1.86e+03	1.82e+03 - 1.90e+03	2.22e-308
A10BH	A10BK	13 699	4.05e-01	3.24e-01 - 5.06e-01	2.34e-15
A10BD	A10BK	12 727	4.06e-01	3.15e-01 - 5.24e-01	3.95e-12
A10BJ	A10BK	13 156	4.19e-01	3.35e-01 - 5.23e-01	1.93e-14
A10BH	A10BJ	13 537	4.55e-01	3.73e-01 - 5.56e-01	1.34e-14
No6DX	No5AD	2 607	4.72e-01	3.90e-01 - 5.70e-01	8.22e-15
A10BH	A10BD	8 676	4.80e-01	3.94e-01 - 5.85e-01	4.16e-13
A10BD	A10BJ	11 035	5.03e-01	4.03e-01 - 6.28e-01	1.24e-09
Bo1AE	Bo1AF	11 838	5.04e-01	4.23e-01 - 6.00e-01	1.41e-14
A10BG	A10BH	1 436	5.25e-01	4.01e-01 - 68.6	2.31e-06
No6DX	No2AB	4 151	5.30e-01	4.48e-01 - 62.7	1.10e-13
A11EA	Ao1AB	2 882	9.20	6.88 - 12.3	1.93e-50

A11EA	A11CA	1 065	9.44	6.95 - 12.8	9.89e-47
Go1AG	Go3DA	1 351	9.57	6.64 - 13.8	8.72e-34
A11EA	A10BA	1 331	9.73	6.71 - 14.1	2.88e-33
So1KA	So1BC	1 116	9.89	6.56 - 14.91	6.24e-28
So1KA	So1XA	1 175	10.28	7.71 - 13.7	9.65e-57
A11EA	A12AX	1 857	10.5	7.97 - 13.85	2.62e-62
Go1AG	Go2BA	2 112	10.70	6.62 - 17.5	8.48e-22
So1KA	So1CA	2 092	10.8	7.11 - 16.4	8.13e-29
Bo3AE	Bo3BA	1 103	9.87	6.78 - 14.37	6.95e-33

Supplementary table 4 | Stratification of patients by prescription trajectories

	ACE treatment with no change	ARB treatment with no change	ACE treatment with change to ARB	ARB treatment with change to ACE
Number of patients	549 436 (49.3)	287 488 (25.8)	229 216 (20.6)	48 054 (4.3)
Age, years				
Mean (SD)	63.3 (13.9)	61.7 (13.3)	60.7 (12.3)	61.0 (13.2)
Median (IQR)	63.7 (20.0)	62.0 (18.9)	61.0 (17.4)	61.2 (18.9)
Sex				
Male	257 099 (46.8)	153 527 (53.4)	122 549 (53.5)	24 484 (51.0)
Female	292 337 (53.2)	133 961 (46.6)	106 667 (46.5)	23 570 (49.0)
Charlson comorbidities				
Myocardial infarction	74 244 (13.5)	14 962 (5.2)	23 253 (10.1)	5 485 (11.4)
Congestive heart failure	90 247(16.4)	13 696 (4.8)	26 115 (11.4)	6 668 (13.9)
Peripheral vascular diseases	59 155 (10.7)	18 643 (6.5)	20 914 (9.1)	5 666 (11.8)
Cerebrovascular disease	102 441 (18.6)	37 758 (13.1)	35 109 (15.3)	9 894 (20.6)
Dementia	29 033 (4.9)	8 387 (2.9)	6 181 (2.7)	2 452 (5.1)
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	77 099 (14.0)	31 317 (10.9)	28 892 (12.6)	7 029 (14.6)
Rheumatoid disease	21 897 (3.9)	10 172 (3.5)	9 500 (4.1)	2 135 (4.4)
Peptic ulcer disease	36 803 (6.7)	13 572 (4.7)	12 545 (5.4)	3 315 (6.9)
Mild liver disease	12 827 (2.3)	5 527 (1.9)	4 739 (2.0)	1 175 (2.4)
Diabetes without complications	90 186 (16.4)	27 143 (9.4)	37 033 (16.1)	8 391 (17.4)
Diabetes with complications	31 608 (5.7)	7 560 (2.6)	12 894 (5.6)	2 806 (5.8)
Hemiplegia or paraplegia	3 633 (0.7)	1 433 (0.5)	1 064 (0.4)	298 (0.6)
Renal disease	29 369 (5.3)	8 112 (2.8)	11 624 (5.1)	3 236 (6.7)
Cancer	102 249 (18.6)	44 873 (15.6)	39 402 (17.1)	9 362 (19.5)
Moderate or severe liver disease	4 272 (0.7)	1 438 (0.5)	1 174 (0.5)	341 (0.7)
Metastatic solid tumour	20 741 (3.7)	8 219 (2.8)	6 841 (2.9)	1 774 (3.7)
AIDS/HIV	295 (0.05)	109 (0.04)	85 (0.03)	23 (0.04)

Data are n (%) unless otherwise specified

Supplementary table 5 | Population continent of origin

	Percentage
Europe	92.50
Asia	2.93
Middle East	1.94
Africa	1.24
North America	0.81
South and Central America	0.39
Oceania	0.16
Not stated	0.03

E | Appendix

Publications and preprints

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